

Ozone levels in relation to its precursors: NO_x, NMVOCs and CH₄

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Summary

Ozone pollution remains a key challenge for European air quality. This report examines how the revised Ambient Air Quality Directive (AAQD) addresses this issue, with a focus on precursor monitoring networks, precursor emission trends, air quality plans, and new approaches to verify emissions.

The revised AAQD significantly strengthens European ozone policy. It aligns the long-term health objective with WHO guidelines (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ by 2050), reduces allowed exceedances for the target values from 25 to 18 days per year by 2030, and mandates ozone-specific air quality plans when target values are exceeded. For monitoring, it expands the list of required VOC species from 30 to 46 (45 NMVOCs plus methane) and, for the first time, explicitly recognises methane as an ozone precursor. These changes reflect advances in scientific understanding of ozone formation chemistry and its health and environmental impacts.

Europe has achieved substantial reductions in ozone precursor emissions over the past three decades. Between 1990 and 2022, NO_x emissions decreased by 64%, NMVOCs by 62%, and CH_4 by 39%, driven by EU regulations, technological improvements, and sectoral policies. However, challenges persist. Emissions from biological waste treatment have grown eightfold, domestic solvent use continues to rise, and four Member States report overall CH_4 increases. Agriculture remains the dominant source of methane, while residential heating, solvent use, coating applications and manure management now account for 56% of NMVOC emissions.

Current monitoring networks are fragmented and require strategic expansion. Long-term measurements are mainly available for aromatic hydrocarbons, while coverage of alkenes, oxygenated VOCs, terpenes, and methane remains limited. Only Germany currently reports CH_4 to the EEA e-reporting database. Nevertheless, compliance with the revised AAQD is technically feasible by building existing programmes and research infrastructures (EMEP, WMO/GAW, ICOS, ACTRIS) through a tiered network design combining core continuous monitoring sites, supplementary coverage, and integration of satellite observations with ground-based measurements.

Monitoring priorities should align with dominant emission sources. For NMVOCs, this means prioritizing BTEX compounds, trimethylbenzenes, and key ketones at urban and industrial sites where solvent use dominates. For methane, monitoring should focus on agricultural regions with high livestock densities, areas with significant biogas production, and regions with remaining fossil fuel infrastructure. Expanding formaldehyde monitoring would also support validation of satellite data.

Few dedicated ozone air quality plans exist, but national efforts are growing. Croatia, France, and Spain have developed comprehensive approaches combining national strategies with regional measures targeting traffic, shipping, industry, and residential emissions. However, most existing plans lack sufficient integration of transboundary contributions. Source apportionment tools, such as the CAMS Air Control Toolbox, now provide daily diagnostics identifying emission contributions for major European cities, supporting evidence-based plan development.

Emerging verification capabilities will strengthen emission monitoring. Methane inverse modelling has achieved high maturity at global and regional scales, while satellite missions (MethaneSAT, GOSAT-GW, Sentinel-5) are expanding observational capacity. Integration of satellite observations with ground-based networks offers promising prospects for improved emission quantification and adaptive policy responses.

Controlling precursor emissions remains the main policy lever available to Member States. Given the transboundary nature of ozone pollution and the complex, non-linear chemistry of ozone formation, coordinated national and international strategies are essential. The convergence of enhanced

monitoring capabilities, improved emission verification, and strengthened air quality plans will be critical to address this persistent challenge and protect public health and ecosystems across Europe.

Country factsheets for the EU27 Member States are provided alongside this report and can be accessed through the links in the table below. These factsheets provide an in-depth analysis of ground-level ozone across the country. They present long-term trends in ozone concentrations (2005-2023), changes in precursor emissions (CH₄, NMVOCs and NO_x) over the period 1990-2023, the contributions of different sectors and regions to daily maximum 8-hour average (MDA8) ozone concentrations in 2023, and projected ozone levels for 2050 under various emission scenarios. This analysis is based on multiple datasets, including both observations (data from EEA database) and modelling data (from chemistry transport models like CHIMERE and EMEP/MSC-W).

Table 1: Links to the country (EU27) ozone factsheets with complementary information

Country	Link
Austria	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-austria-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Belgium	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-belgium-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Bulgaria	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-bulgaria-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Croatia	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-croatia-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Cyprus	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-cyprus-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Czechia	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-czech-republic-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Denmark	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-denmark-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Estonia	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-estonia-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Finland	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-finland-ozone-factsheet.pdf
France	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-france-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Germany	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-germany-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Greece	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-greece-ozone-factsheet.pdf

Hungary	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-hungary-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Ireland	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-ireland-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Italy	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-italy-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Latvia	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-latvia-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Lithuania	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-lithuania-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Luxembourg	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-luxembourg-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Malta	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-malta-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Netherlands	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-netherlands-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Poland	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-poland-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Portugal	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-portugal-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Romania	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-romania-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Slovakia	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-slovakia-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Slovenia	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-slovenia-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Spain	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-spain-ozone-factsheet.pdf
Sweden	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-12-ozone-levels-in-relation-to-its-precursors-nox-nmvocs-and-ch4/etc-he-report-2025-12-sweden-ozone-factsheet.pdf

1 Introduction

Ozone pollution remains a major public health challenge across Europe, with significant mortality impacts despite ongoing air quality efforts. In 2023, European citizens faced an average peak season ozone exposure of 87.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (90 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for EU27 citizens), well above the WHO guideline level of 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. These exposure levels varied considerably across countries, creating a pronounced geographical gradient in health risk. The burden of disease estimates revealed the severe consequences of this pollution, with approximately 70,981 deaths attributable to ozone across 41 European countries, including 62,676 deaths within the EU27 (Soares et al., 2025). At the ecosystem level, high ozone concentrations can lead to biodiversity loss, alter ecosystem structure and degrade habitat quality, while reducing agricultural yields and forest growth. A substantial proportion of European agricultural land remains exposed to harmful ozone levels. The long-term objective for vegetation protection (6,000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ per hour) remains largely unmet, with only 9.2% of European agricultural land meeting this threshold in 2023¹, indicating persistent risk of vegetation damage from ozone exposure.

Unlike other pollutants, ozone is not directly emitted but forms in the atmosphere through photochemical reactions between precursors such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs, including methane - CH_4), with meteorological conditions playing a crucial role in concentration variations. The spatial distribution of ozone levels is closely correlated with temperature and insolation patterns, resulting in higher concentrations in southern Europe countries compared to northern regions. The complex formation process makes ozone pollution particularly challenging to control, as the relationship between precursor emissions and resulting ozone concentrations is not straightforward. This complexity is further intensified by varying ozone production efficiencies across VOC species and differing atmospheric lifetimes among precursors. Consequently, the interplay between these lifetimes and spatial scales represents a critical consideration for understanding and addressing ozone pollution.

Between 2005-2023, European ozone trends (from Gbangou, et al., 2023 and updated for this study) revealed contrasting patterns that create significant air quality management challenges. Annual mean ozone concentrations increased by 2.5-25% at background monitoring sites, while peak ozone episodes decreased by 2-11.7% and the number of days exceeding 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ declined by up to 71%. In contrast, no significant trend is observed for the ozone peak season (-3.2% to +9.7%). This divergence is primarily attributed to hemispheric transport and reduced nitrogen monoxide (NO) titration due to lower NO_x emissions, with urban locations showing stronger increases than rural sites. Geographically, annual mean ozone decreased in Central / Eastern Europe while increasing in Western regions, particularly in Spain, southeastern France and the Benelux, reflecting the complex interplay between changing in precursor emissions and regional atmospheric chemistry across Europe.

This analysis provides initial insights into ozone-precursor relationships and enhances understanding of the regulatory challenges presented by the revised AAQD regarding ozone and its precursors. It outlines the complete pathway connecting regulatory framework with scientific understanding. The report is structured as follows. Section 2 examines the monitoring and assessment requirements for ozone pollution under the revised AAQD, highlighting key changes from the 2008 framework. Building on this regulatory context, Section 3 analyses the implications for sampling points requirements through case studies in selected Member States. Section 4 then presents available tools for ozone source apportionment recognizing the critical role of precursors in ozone formation. Section 5 focuses on volatile organic compound (VOC) monitoring across Europe, providing targeted recommendations for species selections and instrumentation. Section 6 evaluates ozone air quality plans implemented across European countries, integrating information from the e-reporting database to assess compliance and effectiveness. Section 7 presents a comprehensive analysis of precursor emissions

⁽¹⁾ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/exposure-of-europes-ecosystems-to-ozone?activeAccordion=ecdb3bcf-bbe9-4978-b5cf-0b136399d9f8>

(CH₄, NMVOCs and NO_x), examining trends by country and emission sector while reviewing reduction measures and analysing future projections. Finally, Section 8 provides a review of methane inverse modelling methodologies and their applications for emissions estimations.

2 Requirements under the Ambient Air Quality Directive

The revised AAQD represents a significant policy step in aligning European air quality standards closer to the latest scientific evidence, particularly in relation to the health and environmental impacts of ground-level ozone. Recognising ozone as a critical transboundary pollutant with serious public health and ecological consequences, the revised AAQD introduces more stringent requirements for monitoring, reporting, and mitigating ozone and its precursors. This section summarises the main provisions of the revised AAQD that are relevant to ozone. It highlights the key differences compared to the 2008 Directive, with a particular focus on:

- the monitoring of ozone and its precursors;
- the development and implementation of ozone-specific air quality plans;
- the evaluation of transboundary contributions to ozone concentrations.

2.1 Target values, long-term objectives, alert and information thresholds

With the focus on reducing the adverse effects on human health and on vegetation and ecosystems, the revised AAQD progresses towards target values and long-term objectives for ozone that are aligned with scientific evidence, including the WHO guideline recommendations (WHO, 2021). Table 2.1 lists the target values, long-term objectives, alert and information thresholds, and assessment thresholds as defined in the revised AAQD.

Table 2.1: Target values, long-term objectives, alert and information thresholds, and assessment thresholds as defined in the revised AAQD.

Revised AAQD reference	Objective	Averaging period	Value	Number of allowed exceedances	Assessment threshold
Ozone target values to be attained by 1 January 2030					
Annex I, Section 2, Point B	Protection of human health	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	120 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 18 days per calendar year, averaged over 3 years	100 µg/m ³ (99th percentile) ¹
Annex I, Section 2, Point B	Protection of vegetation	May to July	AOT40 (calculated from 1-hour values) 18 000 µg/m ³ x h averaged over 5 years		
Long-term objectives for Ozone (O ₃) to be attained by 1 January 2050					
Annex I, Section 2, Point C	Protection of human health	Maximum daily 8-hour mean within a calendar year	100 µg/m ³	99th percentile ¹	
Annex I, Section 2, Point C	Protection of vegetation	May to July	AOT40 (calculated from 1-hour values) 6 000 µg/m ³ x h		
Alert threshold and information threshold for Ozone					

Annex I, Section 4, Point A. (Article 20)	Alert threshold	1 hour, measured or predicted for 3 consecutive hours	240 µg/m ³		
Annex I, Section 4, Point B	Information threshold	1 hour	180 µg/m ³		

¹⁾ i.e. 3 exceedance days per year.

The revised AAQD sets that:

- A target value for protection of human health that is given as a maximum daily 8-hour mean of 120 µg/m³, not to be exceeded on more than 25 days per calendar year, averaged over 3 years, until 1 January 2030. From then on, the allowed number of exceedances is reduced from 25 to 18.
- A long-term objective for protection of human health, given as a maximum daily 8-hour mean, which is lowered from 120 µg/m³ with no allowed exceedances, to 100 µg/m³ as a 99th percentile, i.e., 3 exceedance days per year, to be attained by 1 January 2050. This objective is aligned with the WHO short-term ozone guideline value to protect human health.
- An assessment threshold for health protection is introduced for ozone, aligned with the AAQD long-term objective for protection of human health and the WHO short-term ozone guideline value.

It is important to note that the objectives for the protection of vegetation and the alert and information thresholds remain unchanged in the revised AAQD.

Europe's air quality status report 2025 (EEA, 2025) shows that while only 16.4% of the population were exposed to concentrations above the target value threshold in 2023, 94.4% of the population were exposed to concentrations above the WHO guideline. Introduction of an assessment threshold aligned with the WHO short-term guideline value may imply an increase in the number of zones where fixed measurements are mandatory and so increase the required number of sampling points.

2.2 Data quality objectives for ozone and related NO and NO₂

Annex V of the revised AAQD defines the data quality objectives of measurements and modelling applications and in terms of the minimum uncertainty in data coverage of the measurements. Both are essential for assessing air quality in a uniform and coherent manner. In addition to relative uncertainty, defined in the 2008 Directive, the revised AAQD requires uncertainty to be expressed as absolute values and specifies that uncertainty is provided for 8-hour mean values. For objective estimation, the revised AAQD states that uncertainty is expressed as a maximum ratio of the uncertainty of modelling applications and objective estimation over the uncertainty of fixed measurements. Table 2.2 lists the data quality objectives for ozone and related NO and NO₂ in the revised AAQD.

Table 2.2: Data quality objectives for ozone and related NO and NO₂ in the revised AAQD.

Revised AAQD reference	Air pollutant, metric	Fixed measurements		Indicative measurements		Objective estimation
		Absolute	Relative	Absolute ¹⁾	Relative ¹⁾	
	Maximum uncertainty	Absolute	Relative	Absolute ¹⁾	Relative ¹⁾	Ratio ²⁾
Annex V, A. Table 2.	Ozone (8h mean)	18 µg/m ³	15 %	30 µg/m ³	25 %	2,2
	Minimum data coverage relative to calendar year					
Annex V, B.	Ozone and related NO and NO ₂ , annual mean	85 % ³⁾		13 %		

Annex V, B.	Ozone and related NO and NO ₂ , 1-hour, 8-hour or 24-hour means ³⁾	85 %	50 % ⁴⁾	
Required proportion of valid data for aggregation of data for ambient air quality assessment				
Annex V, C.	1-hour, 8-hour, maximum daily 8-hour means, or 24-hour means		75%	

¹⁾ When using indicative measurements for other purposes other than compliance assessment, such as, but not only: design or review of the monitoring network, model calibration and validation, the uncertainty may be that established for modelling applications.

²⁾ The uncertainty of objective estimation shall not exceed the uncertainty for indicative measurements by more than the applicable maximum ratio and shall not exceed 85 %.

³⁾ Minimum data coverage requirements are to be met both for the full calendar year and for the periods of April to September and October to March, respectively. Assessment of the AOT40 for ozone minimum data coverage requirements are to be met during the time period defined for calculating the AOT40 value.

⁴⁾ Minimum data coverage applies for the period of April to September (no criterium of minimum data coverage is required during the winter period).

The revised AAQD combines *time coverage* and *data capture* defined in the 2008 Directive into a single term: *data coverage*. Data coverage is defined as the proportion of the calendar year for which valid measurement data are available, expressed as a percentage. The 2008 Directive specified different data coverage requirements for summer and winter for fixed measurements as well as for indicative measurements. In the revised AAQD, the requirement of a minimum 85% data coverage for fixed measurements applies to the calendar year, as well as to the April-September and October-March periods and for AOT40 calculations. For indicative measurements, the data coverage requirement (minimum 13%) applies for April-September, and no minimum data coverage is required during the winter period.

The data coverage requirements in the revised AAQD seem easier to comprehend. For the winter season and for the calendar year, the requirements are, however, stricter than in the 2008 Directive. In line with the reference method, continuous monitoring instruments shall be used at all fixed sampling points. With continuous measurements all year round, the stricter requirements should not be significantly harder to achieve.

2.3 Reference methods for assessment of concentrations in ambient air and deposition rates

In the absence of an EN standard, the revised AAQD gives recommendations for methods for sampling and measuring ozone precursor substances and for modelling applications. Table 2.3 lists the reference methods recommended. Member States may choose the sampling and measuring methods they use, in accordance with the data quality objectives given, including the promotion of harmonised air quality modelling approaches.

Table 2.3: Reference methods for assessment of concentrations in ambient air and deposition rates in the revised AAQD in relation to ozone.

Revised AAQD reference	Pollutant	Reference method	Directive recommendation
Annex VI, A. 11.	Ozone	EN 14625:2012: Ambient air – Standard method for the measurement of	

		the concentration of ozone by ultraviolet photometry	
Annex VI, A. 2.	Nitrogen dioxide and oxides of nitrogen	EN 14211:2012: Ambient air – Standard method for the measurement of the concentration of nitrogen dioxide and nitrogen monoxide by chemiluminescence	
Annex VI, A. 14.	Volatile organic compounds that are ozone precursor substances		In the absence of an EN standard method for sampling and measuring volatile organic compounds that are ozone precursor substances, Member States may choose the sampling and measuring methods they use, in accordance with Annex V and taking into account the measurement objectives, including those set out in Section 3, Point A, and Section 4, Point A, of Annex VII, as applicable. Where international, EN or national standard reference measurement methods or CEN technical specifications are available, these may be used.
Annex VI, E.	Reference air quality modelling applications		In the absence of an EN standard on modelling quality objectives, Member States may choose the modelling applications they use, in accordance with Point G (F) of Annex V

2.4 Monitoring of ozone and its precursors

One of the most notable updates in the revised AAQD is the strengthened focus on monitoring not just ozone itself, but also its key precursors, especially nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), including methane (CH₄). While the 2008 Directive required ozone monitoring at urban and rural sites, the revised AAQD expands this by:

- Requiring more detailed spatial coverage, particularly in areas where vulnerable populations are exposed.
- Enhancing speciation and source identification of VOCs, which are crucial in understanding the chemical mechanisms driving ozone formation.
- Introducing monitoring supersites with specific requirements for precursor monitoring across Member States.

These improvements aim to enable more accurate assessments of ozone formation potential and to support both local and regional mitigation strategies. In the 2008 Directive the minimum required number of sampling points in agglomerations (urban and suburban) were lower than in other zones (suburban and rural). The concept of agglomerations is not continued in the revised AAQD, and the minimum required number of sampling points given for other zones in the 2008 Directive applies to all zones in the revised AAQD. This may increase the number of required sampling points in urban and suburban areas.

Table 2.4 lists the monitoring requirements outlined in the revised AAQD. The revised AAQD introduces two new monitoring requirements. One requirement is related to the fixed measurements of ozone and NO₂ at supersites (Annex VII, Section 1). The revised AAQD defines the concept of monitoring supersites, which are urban or rural background monitoring stations measuring several pollutants over an extended period. The other requirement concerns the measurement of precursors (Annex VII, Section 3).

Table 2.4: Revised AAQD monitoring requirements for ozone and its precursors.

Reference	Pollutant	Requirement
Article 8	O ₃	Fixed measurements are required in all zones classified as above the assessment threshold
Article 9(5)	NO ₂	NO ₂ shall be measured at a minimum of 50 % of the ozone sampling points required.
Article 10 Annex VII, Section 1, Table 1.	NO ₂ , O ₃	Fixed measurements of NO ₂ and ozone at all monitoring supersites at urban background locations.
Article 10 Annex VII, Section 1, Table 2.	NO ₂ , O ₃	Fixed measurements of NO ₂ and ozone at all monitoring supersites at rural background locations.
Article 9(4) Annex VII, Section 3.	NO, NO ₂ , CH ₄ , other VOCs	Measurements of ozone precursor substances at one or more sampling points.
Annex III, C. 2	O ₃	Measurements at rural background locations

Similar to the 2008 Directive, the revised AAQD mandates that measurements of ozone precursor substances including at least NO and NO₂. However, it explicitly states that methane (CH₄) and other VOCs should be measured when appropriate. It also revises and expands the list of recommended VOC compounds, including alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, and terpenes. These compounds are frequently observed in ambient air and are frequently documented in the literature. Terpenes have high reactivity, and their oxidation leads to the formation of oxygenated VOCs (OVOCs) such as alcohols (methanol, ethanol, etc.), ketones (acetone, methyl ethyl ketone, etc.), aldehydes (formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, etc.), carboxylic acids (formic, acetic, etc.) of various volatilities and chemical structures. OVOCs play an active role in the chemical reaction chain of the atmosphere and are precursors of photochemical ozone and secondary organic aerosols, as other VOC chemical families. The World Meteorological Organization (WMO) Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) recommends monitoring OVOCs, including formaldehyde and terpenes (GAW-WMO, 2017).

The revised AAQD, however, does not specify which of the VOCs the Member States should monitor. The selection of compounds should depend on the objective sought and may be complemented by other compounds of interest (Annex VII, Section 3). Table 2.5 lists the VOCs recommended for monitoring by the revised AAQD. The list has been significantly expanded, increasing from 30 species in the 2008 Directive to 46 in the revised version. It is worth noting that benzene, already regulated as a pollutant, is included in this list.

Table 2.5: List of VOCs recommended for monitoring under the revised AAQD.

Group	Compound
Alcohols	Methanol
	Ethanol
Aldehyde	Formaldehyde
	Acetaldehyde
	Methacrolein
Alkynes	Acetylene
Alkanes	Methane

	Ethane
	Propane
	n-Butane
	i-Butane
	n-Pentane
	i-Pentane
	n-Hexane
	i-Hexane
	n-Heptane
	n-Octane
	i-Octane
Alkenes	Ethylene
	Propene / Propylene
	1,3-Butadiene
	1-Butene
	Trans-2-Butene
	cis-2-Butene
	1-Pentene
	2-Pentene
Aromatics	Benzene
	Toluene
	m,p-Xylene
	o-Xylene
	Ethyl benzene
	1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene
	1,2,3-Trimethylbenzene
	1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene
Ketones	Acetone
	Methyl ethyl ketone
	Methyl vinyl ketone
Terpenes	Isoprene
	p-Cymene
	Limonene
	β -Myrcene
	α -Pinene
	β -Pinene
	Camphene
	Δ^3 -Carene
	1,8-Cineol

2.5 Ozone air quality plans

Under the 2008 Directive, Member States were obliged to take all necessary measures that do not entail disproportionate costs to ensure the target values and long-term objectives are attained (Article

17). However, air quality plans were not mandatory as the main reduction target is related to the NEC Directive². The revised AAQD makes the development of air quality plans for ozone compulsory, and a justification must be provided if a plan is not established. In particular, it states that:

- Ozone air quality plans must be updated regularly, particularly when new exceedances occur.
- Measures that specifically target precursor reductions, with links to emission inventories and source apportionment studies must be included.
- Member States can waive the ozone plans only if they can demonstrate that: i) there is no significant potential to reduce ozone concentrations due to regional or hemispheric influences, and ii) additional measures would entail disproportionate economic or social costs.

This clause acknowledges the complex and often non-linear relationship between precursor emissions and local ozone concentrations.

The revised AAQD also expands the concept of air quality plan, adding air quality roadmap. According to the revised AAQD:

- ‘Air quality plan’ means a plan that sets out policies and measures to comply with limit values, target values or average exposure reduction obligations once these have been exceeded.
- ‘Air quality roadmap’ means an air quality plan, adopted ahead of the attainment deadline of limit values and target values, that sets out policies and measures to comply with those limit values and target values within the attainment deadline.
- ‘Short-term action plan’ means a plan that sets out emergency measures to be taken in the short term to reduce the immediate risk or the duration of the exceedance of the alert thresholds.

Table 2.6 summarises the requirements for air quality plans and roadmaps, and short-term plans outlined in the revised AAQD for ozone. Compared to the 2008 Directive, Article 19 in the revised AAQD provides extended and more detailed requirements for the establishment and revision of air quality plans and air quality roadmaps, including timelines and deadlines. When any target value is exceeded, an air quality plan is mandatory, with specific exceptions. Air quality roadmaps are required where the target value is exceeded after 1 January 2026, aiming to achieve compliance with the target value within the attainment deadline. Similar to air quality plans, exceptions for the requirement to establish air quality roadmaps are provided for ozone. Detailed justification for the decision not to establish air quality plans or roadmaps must be submitted.

The revised AAQD expands the requirements for public involvement and engagement in planning compared to the 2008 Directive. In establishing and updating air quality plans, air quality roadmaps and short-term action plans, consulting the public and the competent authorities before their finalisation is mandatory. Encouraging active engagement of the interested parties is also required.

In addition, the revised AAQD recognises that air quality plans may be done on a territorial unit, covering at least one air quality zone. Planning and measures can be implemented at a regional level, covering several air quality zones.

⁽²⁾ National Emission Reduction Commitments Directive; 2016/2284/EU.

Table 2.6: Revised AAQD requirements for different plans targeting reduction of ozone and its precursors.

Reference	Requirements	Time	Aim	Exceptions (Need justification)
Air quality plans				
Article 19, Point 2	Required when any O ₃ target value is exceeded in territorial units, covering at least one zone.	No later than 2 years after the exceedance year.	To achieve the target value and to keep the exceedance period as short as possible	When an air quality roadmap already covers the exceedance Where there is no significant potential to reduce ozone concentrations and where the measures would entail disproportional costs.
Article 19, Point 2	Reassessment of potential for reduction of concentrations	Every 5 year		
Programme prepared pursuant to article 6 of Directive (EU) 2016/2284				
Article 19, Point 2.	When O ₃ target value is exceeded		Ensure that the programme includes measures addressing ozone precursors	
Air quality roadmaps				
Article 19, point 4.	Required where the target value is exceeded after 1 January 2026	As soon as possible and no later than 2 years after the exceedance was recorded. Update of plans and more effective measures are required if exceedances persist during the third calendar year after the deadline for the establishment of the plan	To attain the target value by the expiration of the attainment deadline	When the baseline scenario, according to Point A, point 5, of Annex VIII, demonstrates that the measures already in force will be sufficient to achieve the limit or target value, including when the exceedance is caused by temporary activities influencing the levels of pollutants in a single year
Article 19. point 7.	Obligation to consult the public and competent authorities	Prior to finalization of air quality plans and roadmaps and prior to significant updates.		
Article 19. point 7.	Encourage active involvement of all interested parties	In preparation, implementation and updates.		
Article 19, point 8	Communication to the Commission	Within 2 months of their adoption.		
Short-term action plans				

Article 20, Point 1	Required when there is a risk of exceeding the alert threshold		Indicate the emergency measures to be taken in the short term in order to reduce the risk or duration of such an exceedance	When there is no significant potential, taking into account national geographical, meteorological and economic conditions, to reduce the risk, duration or severity of such an exceedance
Article 20, Point 3	Obligation to consult the public and competent authorities	On draft plans and significant updates.		
Article 20, Point 4	Make results of investigation on feasibility, content of plan and information on implementation available to the public and appropriate organisations.	When plan is established		
Article 20, Point 5	Communication to the Commission	Within 1 year of their adoption.		
Article 20, Point 6	Member States may request the Commission to organise an exchange of best practices			

2.6 Transboundary air pollution

Recognising ozone as a transboundary pollutant, the revised AAQD places greater emphasis on understanding and quantifying the contribution of air pollution from outside a given Member State. New provisions include:

- Obligations to conduct source attribution studies for instance based on chemical transport models and back-trajectory analyses to assess the origin of elevated ozone episodes.
- Encouragement of regional coordination and information-sharing through EU-wide mechanisms. The 2008 Directive addressed transboundary pollution with provisions and requirements for cooperation and joint activities to remove exceedances and reduce precursor emissions, and inviting the Commission to assist. The revised AAQD elaborates the provisions further and introduces a timeline for the progress and involvement of the Commission.
- Improved integration with the NEC Directive and other sectoral regulations, ensuring that ozone control is considered within the broader context of cross-border air pollution policy.

This approach not only reflects scientific consensus on ozone's regional behaviour but also helps inform realistic target-setting and cost-effective mitigation planning.

When transboundary pollution contributes significantly to exceedances, the revised AAQD introduces provisions for notifying the Commission and the Member State from which pollution originates and gives a list of minimum contents of such notices. The revised AAQD also gives more extensive details and clarification on cooperation, joint efforts and coordination between Member States, and involvement and information to the Commission. The Commission may consider further action on the European Union level to reduce precursor emissions.

Table 2.7 lists the requirements for transboundary air pollution set by the revised AAQD.

Table 2.7: Revised AAQD requirements for transboundary air pollution.

AAQD 2024/2881 reference	Action	Requirements	Timeline	Aim	Involvement of the Commission
Article 21, point 1 and 2	Notification	Notify the originated MS and the Commission when transboundary air pollution contributes significantly to exceedances of target value or alert threshold	Shall respond to each other in a timely manner and inform the Commission, no later than 3 months after being notified		Commission shall be notified
Article 21, point 6.	Notification	Suggested content in notification			
Article 21, point 2. and 3.	Cooperation	Cooperation between MS		Remove such exceedances, including establishing joint teams of experts to identify sources and their contribution, measures to be taken and to coordinate activities such as air quality plans	The Commission shall be informed, and invited to be involved in the cooperation
Article 21, point 3.	Cooperation	Cooperation between MS			The Commission may request an update on progress in implementing any coordinated activities
Article 21, point 3.	Cooperation	Cooperation between MS			Where appropriate, the Commission shall, taking into account the reports established pursuant to Article 11 of Directive (EU) 2016/2284, consider

						whether further action shall be taken at Union level in order to reduce precursor emissions responsible for transboundary pollution.
Article 21, point 4.	Short-term action plans	Member States shall, where appropriate prepare and implement coordinated short-term action plans covering neighbouring zones in other Member States.				
Article 21, point 4.	Information regarding short-term action plan	Member States shall ensure that neighbouring zones in other Member States receive all appropriate information regarding those short-term action plans	Without undue delay.			
Article 21, point 5.	Information to neighbouring MS of exceedance of alert- or information thresholds	When alert- or information thresholds in zones close to national borders are exceeded, the competent authorities in the neighbouring Member State concerned shall be informed as soon as possible and the information shall be made available to the public.	As soon as possible			
Article 21, point 7.	Coordinated air quality plans and short-term	Member States shall, where appropriate, endeavour to	When establishing			Member States may, where appropriate, request

	action plans, information to the public	pursue cooperation with third countries, and in particular with candidate countries.			technical support from the Commission.
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2.7 Section highlights

The revised AAQD represents a significant step forward in European policy by strengthening monitoring requirements, tightening air quality standards, and reinforcing the framework for cross-border cooperation. Key changes include **the alignment of the long-term objective for human health to be attained by 1st January 2050 with the WHO guideline (100 µg/m³), the introduction of a health-based assessment threshold, and the mandatory development of ozone-specific air quality plans** when exceedance of the target value occurs.

The expanded monitoring provisions, particularly the establishment of supersites and the significantly **extended list of VOC precursors (from 30 to 46 species – 45 NMVOCs plus methane)**, reflect a deeper understanding of ozone formation, including the role of biogenic emissions and oxygenated compounds. The explicit **inclusion of methane as a precursor** to be monitored also acknowledges its growing importance in tropospheric ozone formation.

Additionally, **the revised AAQD recognizes the inherently transboundary nature of ozone pollution** by establishing clearer mechanisms for notification, cooperation, and coordinated action between Member States. This regional approach is essential given that local reductions of emissions alone are often insufficient to achieve ozone targets.

The revised AAQD sets clear deadlines, 2030 for target values and 2050 for long-term objectives, requiring Member States to address ozone pollution through multiscale precursor reduction strategies.

3 Implications of the revised AAQD on the number of sampling points requirement (case studies)

One of the indirect implications of the new requirements set out in the revised AAQD, as discussed in the previous section, is its impact on the number of sampling points. This issue is discussed in the following.

The revised AAQD does not change the minimum number of sampling points required per population threshold. Thus, changes in the number of sampling points (SPO) needed in a zone are expected only if the population grows sufficiently to move the zone into a higher category in Annex III of the revised AAQD, or the zone's classification relative to ozone levels above the assessment threshold (AT) changes, triggering mandatory fixed-monitoring requirements. However, under the 2008 Directive (Annex V), agglomerations benefited from one fewer required sampling points in several population ranges compared to standard air quality zones. As mentioned in section 2.4, the revised AAQD eliminates the agglomeration concept, treating all areas solely as air-quality zones. As a result, zones that previously held agglomeration status may now be required to operate one additional sampling point to meet the Annex III minimum requirements for their population class.

Therefore, the combined effect of revised thresholds and zone definitions may implicate changes in the number of sampling points per zone. The revised percentile-based AT is generally more sensitive to recurring high-ozone episodes than the former long-term objective (LTO) metric. This may result in:

- more zones qualifying for mandatory fixed measurements if at least one sampling point shows exceedance under the new AT;
- limited changes in zones where ozone levels remain consistently low, as sampling points will fall below both the old LTO and the new AT;
- some sampling points and therefore zones remaining undecided, especially where data completeness was limited, though this does not usually alter fixed-monitoring obligations.

To assess how the revised AAQD may affect the required number of ozone sampling points, an evaluation was carried out using monitoring data for the period 2019-2023 in Germany, Norway, Spain and the Netherlands. The period chosen reflects the latest five years of validated data reported to the EEA. Five years are the (maximum) number of years needed for reviewing the zone classification and the number of years exceedances should be assessed (Article 7). The countries were chosen to include different latitudes, as southern and northern countries are affected differently (Norway vs. Spain) but also how central European countries may need a different number of sampling points due to a changing climate. It was also considered countries where many agglomerations will have to be considered as regular zones, and therefore the requirement of the number of sampling points per population may change (point A and C of Annex III in the revised AAQD and Point A.1 in Annex V in 2008/50/EC).

For assessing the impact on the ozone sampling points due to the revised AAQD, 2008 Directive's ozone LTO was compared with the revised AAQD's assessment threshold. Maximum daily 8-hour means (for comparison with the 2008 Directive's long-term objective, LTO) and the 99th percentile of the daily 8-hour means (for comparison with the revised AAQD's assessment threshold) were extracted from the EEA's Air Quality Statistics Viewer³ between 2019 and 2023. Only years with at least 85% data coverage were included to ensure robust and comparable statistics. Each sampling point was treated individually and analyzed across all valid years.

For each SPO, the number of years with ≥85% data coverage was first determined. The SPO was then classified according to whether it exceeded the 2008 Directive's LTO. This step provides a baseline reflecting how zones were previously assessed under the 2008 Directive, where exceedance of the LTO triggered the requirement for at least one mandatory fixed measurement in the zone:

- An SPO was marked "above LTO" if in *any* valid year the rounded annual maximum daily 8-hour mean exceeded 120 µg/m³.
- SPOs with fewer than five valid years were still classified as above LTO if any exceedance occurred.
- If no exceedance was found but the SPO had an incomplete dataset or insufficient years to confidently conclude compliance, it was recorded as "undecided".
- SPOs with five full years and no exceedances were classified as "below LTO".

A second classification was conducted following the criteria of the revised AAQD. For each SPO, the annual 99th percentile of the daily maximum 8-hour mean, rounded to the nearest integer, was evaluated:

- An SPO was classified as "above the revised assessment threshold" if three or more years exceeded 100 µg/m³.
- SPOs with only one or two valid years were automatically labelled "undecided" due to insufficient evidence.

⁽³⁾ https://discomap.eea.europa.eu/App/AQViewer/index.html?fqn=Airquality_Dissem.b2g.AirQualityStatistics

- SPOs with three or four valid years were labelled above, below, or undecided depending on whether the pattern of exceedances was conclusive.

Each SPO was associated with its corresponding air quality zone, and, for every zone, the following were summarised:

- Number of SPOs above, below, or undecided for the 2008 LTO
- Number of SPOs above, below, or undecided for the revised AAQD AT

A zone was considered to require mandatory fixed measurements if at least one sampling point exceeded the LTO (2008 Directive) or the AT (revised AAQD). This mirrors how zones are operationally assessed for compliance obligations.

Table 3.1 summarises the analysis for the four countries assessed. The revised AAQD results in relatively limited changes to ozone monitoring obligations, with most zones retaining their existing requirements. In Spain, 129 of 135 zones remain unchanged, while one zone without previous exceedances now requires an additional sampling point under the revised assessment threshold, and two zones no longer require fixed monitoring at their four sampling points due to no exceedance under the new criteria; three zones could not be classified due to insufficient data. Of Spain’s 44 former agglomerations, population-based rules mean that 34 now require one additional SPO. In Norway, four of seven zones remain unchanged, one zone no longer requires fixed measurements, two zones lack sufficient data for assessment, and one former agglomeration with fewer than 250 000 inhabitants may need an additional SPO. For Germany, 67 of 68 zones show no change, with one zone unclassified due to missing data; however, among its 34 former agglomerations, 23 require one extra SPO under the revised population-based rules. In the Netherlands, all nine zones remain unaffected by the revised thresholds, though of the six former agglomerations, three require an additional SPO. Overall, most zones see no change due to pollutant thresholds, while the discontinuation of the agglomeration concept drives the majority of additional SPO requirements.

Table 3.1: Implication of the revised AAQD on the number of sampling points (SPOs) in four countries.

Country	Number of Zones							Number of zones impacted by revised AAQD	
	Total	No change		Change		Not enough data	Agglomerations 2008 Directive	Decrease in required SPOs	Increase in required SPOs
		above AT	below AT	above to below AT	below to above AT				
Spain	135	127	2	2	1	3	44	2	37
Norway	7	4	0	1	0	2	3	1	1
Germany	68	67	0	0	0	1	34	0	23
Netherlands	9	9	0	0	0	0	6	0	3

Note: 2008 Directive required fewer SPOs in agglomeration than in other zones.

3.1 Section highlights

The revised AAQD does not introduce changes to the minimum number of sampling points required per population threshold. The expected change in results is mainly due to two factors. First, there has been **a shift from a threshold based on the long-term objective to an assessment threshold** based on the 99th percentile, which is more sensitive to recurring high-ozone episodes. Second, the **agglomeration concept has been removed**.

An evaluation was conducted for the period 2019-2023 in four Member States (Germany, Spain, Norway, the Netherlands). Results show that **the impact of the revised thresholds remain limited**. Most zones retain their current obligations (129/135 in Spain, 4/7 in Norway, 67/68 in Germany, 9/9 in the Netherlands). Only a few zones change classification, with roughly equal cases of increased and decreased requirements.

By contrast, **discontinuing the agglomeration status is the main reason for the requirement of additional sampling points**: 37 former Spanish agglomerations, 23 German agglomerations, one Norwegian agglomeration and three Dutch agglomerations will require an additional sampling point in order to comply with the new population-based rules.

4 Source apportionment of ozone concentrations

As highlighted in Section 2, the revised AAQD recognises the importance of transboundary contributions to ozone pollution. When target values are exceeded, Member States are now required to develop ozone-specific air quality plans supported by source attribution studies using chemistry-transport model. This requirement responds to a key challenge for policymakers: the lack of quantitative understanding of whether ozone originates from local or cross-border sources. Source apportionment techniques are therefore essential tools for identifying emission contributions and informing effective mitigation strategies.

The Copernicus CAMS Policy Support Service⁴ provides day-to-day and annual statistics of model source apportionment diagnostics to help understand the main drivers of air pollution episodes. The Air Control Toolbox (ACT, Colette et al., 2022) is an interactive visualization tool allowing assessing how a custom emission scenario targeting primary pollutants and precursors through uniform and long-term Europe-wide reductions translates in terms of ozone and particulate matter pollution, therefore including the secondary pollutants. The tool is based on a surrogate model of the full CHIMERE (Menut et al., 2024) Chemistry-Transport Model (CTM). To develop this approach, it has been demonstrated that the CTM could be approximated by a second order polynomial redefined every day according to forecasted meteorological conditions and trained by a limited number of full models runs widely selected. As of January 2024, the training of ACT is based on the CHIMERE-Fast model (Couvidat et al., 2025) based on Chimere v2020r3 (Menut et al., 2021). This methodology reproduces the sensitivity when reducing anthropogenic emissions, referred to as potential impacts in terms of ambient air concentrations. The spatial resolution of the model is 0.2°x0.1° (approximately 15 km) over Europe. The targeted activity sectors are traffic, industry, residential, agriculture, shipping, and others (including solvents, aviation, offroad, waste and the GNFR sector “others”). Reductions are applied to the mapped emissions over the whole Europe and for a given activity sector, which means that there is still some geographical variability in emission changes (e.g. traffic and agriculture emission have different patterns). This allows limiting the number of training scenarios to a dozen. It should be stressed that it is only because the training of the surrogate model is repeated every single day based on full CHIMERE simulations that the ACT model can capture the complex non-linearity of chemistry and the real-world meteorological forecasts.

⁽⁴⁾ <https://policy.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/>

The results are provided as maps of air pollutant concentrations (daily means for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and O₃ and daily maxima for O₃ and NO₂). The total concentrations as well as the concentrations attributable only to European anthropogenic emissions are available. Absolute and relative differences with a reference scenario are available. Relative differences can be computed either relative to the total concentrations, or relative to the European anthropogenic fraction alone. Diagnostics interpolated at the location of 80 target cities (up to 120 cities since January 1, 2026) with more than 500,000 habitants are also available. Those include source apportionment and chemical regimes, as well as a scenario view which also relies on the country source allocation simulated with the EMEP model. An example is given in Figure 4.1 for ozone daily maximum 8-hours average, showing the source apportionment in Nice during the peak season (from April to September) in 2024. Substantial contribution is estimated from the natural and hemispheric sector (64.8%) followed by shipping (9.8%) and traffic (7.9%).

Figure 4.1: Example of the CAMS Policy Support Service figures from ACT results in Nice for ozone daily maximum 8-hours average (MDA8) during the peak season (from April to September) in 2024.

In addition to ACT, two source attribution methods are available in the CAMS service. The emission perturbation method (based on EMEP MSC-W - Pommier et al., 2020), referred to as "Potential Impact", compares a baseline simulation with simulations where emissions from targeted sources (city, country, shipping) are reduced by 15%, with the resulting concentration differences scaled to 100% to estimate the full contribution of each source. The tagging method (LOTOS-EUROS – Kranenburg et al., 2013), referred to as "Contribution", tracks the origin of pollutants throughout the simulation by labelling each compound according to its emission source, with secondary aerosol mass (e.g. ammonium nitrate) equally attributed to both precursor sources. The key difference lies in their approach: the EMEP method estimates the potential impact of emission reductions, whereas the LOTOS-EUROS method directly traces pollutant origins in the atmosphere. Both methods provide 4-day forecasts of hourly time series with source allocation for the top 10 emission sources. The Potential Impact method (EMEP) covers PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and ozone, while the Contribution method (LOTOS-EUROS) is available for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. Daily time series from 2019 to the present, based on the first forecast day, are also available for both methods. For ozone source apportionment specifically, the

EMEP and ACT methods are complementary: EMEP provides geographical source attribution (city, country, shipping), while ACT enables sectoral source attribution (traffic, industry, agriculture, etc.), offering a comprehensive understanding of both the origin and the activity sectors contributing to ozone pollution.

In this work, the CAMS policy service data from ACT will be integrated with the EEA dashboard⁵ to present spatial and sectoral contributions of emissions to urban background PM_{2.5} levels. These contributions are calculated by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) using the SHERPA tool (Pisoni et al., 2024) and they are presented in the Urban PM_{2.5} Atlas (Thunis et al., 2023). This integration provides enhanced understanding of how different sectors and geographical areas contribute to health-related externalities. A preliminary development has been implemented to extract ACT estimates of ozone source apportionment for cities included in the Burden of Disease assessment (EEA, briefing 16/2025) over a full year, representing the ozone peak season indicator. These data have been linked with the 2023 burden of disease results for ozone (Soares et al., 2025), following the same methodology applied for PM_{2.5}.

4.1 Section highlights

The revised AAQD now requires ozone source apportionment studies to identify the causes of high-concentration episodes. The **CAMS Policy Support Service** addresses this need through the **Air Control Toolbox (ACT)**, a surrogate model of the CTM CHIMERE that provides daily source apportionment diagnostics for major European cities across six emission sectors.

For example, ozone MDA8 concentrations in Nice during the 2024 peak season show dominant contribution from the **natural and hemispheric background (65%)**, followed by **shipping (10%)** and **traffic (8%)**. These ACT outputs will be integrated with the **EEA dashboard** and linked to the **Burden of Disease assessment**, connecting emission sources to health impacts.

5 Monitoring ozone precursors

This section examines in-situ VOC monitoring across Europe. Such monitoring provides essential data to support the design and evaluation of ozone mitigation measures under the revised AAQD requirements.

5.1 NMVOC in-situ monitoring

Systematic monitoring of NMVOC in Europe has evolved over several decades, reflecting growing scientific understanding and policy attention to their role in ozone formation and air quality. NMVOC measurements began in the late 1980s and early 1990s, primarily within scientific research and localised monitoring efforts. These early activities focused on selected urban environments and rural background sites to assess photochemical smog formation, with particular attention to non-methane hydrocarbons (NMHC) and oxygenated VOC (OVOC). Programmes such as the European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP) under the UNECE Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP) and the VOC monitoring activities under the WMO GAW played a pivotal role in establishing systematic observations of these pollutants. EMEP, GAW and the later years, ACTRIS (Aerosol, Clouds, and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure) have played a key role in developing measurement methodologies and QA/QC procedures for VOC observations in regional and remote areas across Europe. WMO/GAW, EMEP and ACTRIS are co-located at most European regional monitoring sites, and data from all programmes are reported to the EBAS database.

⁽⁵⁾ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/in-depth/air-pollution/fine-particulate-matter-pm2-5-concentrations-in-european-cities-spatial-and-sector-specific-contributions-and-costs-of-premature-deaths-1>

A significant policy development occurred in 1996, when VOC emissions were formally addressed under the CLRTAP. This culminated in the adoption of the Gothenburg Protocol in 1999, which introduced emission ceilings for VOCs and encouraged countries to improve monitoring in support of emission inventories and compliance tracking. In 2002, Directive 2002/3/EC on ozone in ambient air incorporated VOCs more explicitly into EU legislation, i.e., required indicative measurements of ozone precursor substances where necessary to support exceedance management and planning.

In Europe, a more integrated framework emerged with the 2008 Directive, which maintained the requirement for ozone precursor monitoring. However, Member States must report only one sampling point measuring NMVOC precursors, not the full list as specified in the revised AAQD. The revised AAQD expands the list of target compounds (Section 3.b of Annex VII) to include alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, and terpenes, and for the first time references CH₄ as an ozone precursor monitoring. This reflects both updated scientific understanding and the EU's commitment to harmonised, comprehensive monitoring to support more effective ozone mitigation strategies. However, it also states that nitrogen oxides shall be included, and when appropriate, both CH₄ and NMVOC.

The revised AAQD explicitly states that NMVOC should be measured when appropriate; the monitoring strategy should depend on the prevalent sources contributing to ozone formation in the region. This can be challenging for Member States to define national strategies that also integrate the EMEP/WMO GAW sites. To that end, it is important to be familiar with the monitoring strategies of the various programmes and the characteristics of the NMVOC listed in the revised AAQD.

The network design should follow criteria such as:

- Geographical considerations: emission sources, land-use, ecosystems and population density.
- Atmospheric behaviour and impacts: lifetime, reactivity, and potential for ozone formation and secondary organic aerosol (SOA).
- Spatial and temporal variation: continuous monitoring for diurnal and seasonal VOC distribution – typically allows for the highest quality measurements, or monitoring using flask and canister sampling – reducing time resolution but allowing a simpler and cheaper approach, allowing for an increase in the number of sampling points.
- Existing programs and infrastructure: coordination with existing GAW, EMEP and ACTRIS monitoring infrastructure to reduce sampling and analysis costs and ensure trained staff for maintenance of the network.

These criteria are discussed in the following subsections.

5.1.1 NMVOC importance for tropospheric chemistry and ozone formation

NMVOC play a major role in tropospheric air quality and atmospheric oxidation capacity, as they contribute to ozone and secondary organic aerosol formation. Table 5.1 provides an overview of the atmospheric lifetime, ozone formation potential, and its importance for atmospheric processes for the VOCs listed in the revised AAQD (see Table 2.5). This table combines information on VOCs required for monitoring under the revised AAQD, and information on their atmospheric lifetime, maximum incremental activity (MIR), the main sources and importance in tropospheric processes.

MIR is a measure of the amount of ozone that a specific VOC can form under worst-case, VOC-limited air conditions, used by regulators to prioritize pollutants for smog reduction. The MIR values presented are taken from the calculation of Venecek et al. (2018), using the SAPRC box model, which simulates a representative urban atmosphere in United States of America. Comparing MIR with the Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential (POCP) based on emissions from the United Kingdom (Derwent et al., 1996) shows that VOCs with high MIR also have high POCP values. Though it is important to note that ozone reactivity varies with atmospheric composition and meteorological conditions (e.g. season, NO_x levels,

and VOC/NO_x ratios), these metrics provide a useful approximation of the relative importance of different VOCs for ozone formation, as their relative ranking remains broadly consistent.

Table 5.1: Approximate lifetime, maximum incremental reactivity (MIR) and importance for atmospheric processes regarding ozone formation of VOCs required by the AAQD.

Chemical family	Compound	Approximate lifetime	MIR (g O ₃ /g VOC emitted) (Venecek et al, 2018)	Importance in tropospheric processes (GAW (2007), unless stated)
Alcohols	Methanol ¹	12 days	0.67	Plant emissions, oxidation product from methane and other VOC, exchange with ocean.
	Ethanol ¹	4 days	1.53	Plant emissions, tracer for biofuel production and use.
Aldehyde	Formaldehyde ¹	1 day	9.46	Atmospheric oxidation product and emissions from biomass burning, indicator of isoprene oxidation, source of free radicals in remote areas.
	Acetaldehyde	10 hours	6.54	Oxidation product of hydrocarbons and ethanol emission from biomass burning; an important precursor of peroxyacetyl nitrate (PAN); a source of free radicals in remote areas. ²
	Methacrolein	8 hours	6.01	Major first-generation oxidation product of isoprene; key precursor to organic nitrates and SOA; contributes to radical recycling. ³
Alkynes	Acetylene ¹	15 days	0.95	Motor vehicle emissions, biomass burning, ratio to other hydrocarbons (age of plume air), regional trends
Alkanes	Ethane ¹	1.5 months	0.28	Natural gas exploration and extraction, biomass burning, tracer for methane sources, hemispheric fossil fuel emission trends
	Propane ¹	11 days	0.49	Natural gas exploration and extraction, biomass burning, tracer for methane sources, regional fossil fuel emission trends
	n-Butane ¹	5 days	1.15	Petrochemical exploration and processing, tracer for natural gas extraction and use ⁴
	i-Butane ¹		1.23	
	n-Pentane ¹	3 days	1.31	Petrochemical exploration and processing, isomeric ratio indicates impact of NO ₃
	i-Pentane ¹		1.45	
	n-Hexane	3 days	1.24	Fossil-fuel/solvent-related alkanes; ozone precursors via OH oxidation (RO ₂ formation); oxidation products can also contribute to SOA under polluted conditions ⁵
	i-Hexane	3 days	1.5	
	n-Heptane	1.5 days	1.07	
	n-Octane	1.3 days	0.9	
i-Octane	3 days	1.26		
Alkenes	Ethylene	1.5 days	9	Major petrochemical/combustion alkene; important urban ozone

Chemical family	Compound	Approximate lifetime	MIR (g O ₃ /g VOC emitted) (Venecek et al, 2018)	Importance in tropospheric processes (GAW (2007), unless stated)
				precursor due to rapid OH addition and RO ₂ chemistry ⁵
	Propene / Propylene	11 hours	11.66	Highly reactive alkene; strong driver of rapid ozone production in high-NO _x conditions ⁵
	1,3-Butadiene	4 hours	12.61	Traffic/industry sources; strong ozone precursor; forms oxygenated products that can contribute to SOA ⁵
	1-Butene	9 hours	9.73	Reactive alkenes; promote fast ozone formation and radical cycling; short lifetimes make them indicators of nearby fresh emissions ⁵
	Trans-2-Butene	9 hours	15.16	
	cis-2-Butene	8 hours	14.24	
	1-Pentene	7 hours	7.21	
2-Pentene	7 hours	10.47		
Aromatic hydrocarbons	Benzene ¹	10 days	0.72	Petrochemical and industrial emissions, tracer of fossil and biofuel combustion, biomass burning
	Toluene / Methylbenzene ¹	2 days	4	Petrochemical and industrial emissions, precursor of organic aerosol, ratio with benzene used to determine the age of plume air
	Ethyl benzene	1.6 days	3.04	Reactive aromatics from fuels/solvents; major contributors to urban ozone formation and important SOA precursors through multi-generation oxidation ⁵
	m + p-Xylene	20 hours	9.75 (m), 5.84 (p)	
	o-Xylene	18 hours	7.64	
	1,2,4-Trimethylebenzene	10 hours	8.87	
	1,2,3-Trimethylebenzene	10 hours	11.97	
1,3,5-Trimethylebenzene	12 hours	11.76		
Ketones	Acetone ¹	1.7 months	0.36	Oxidation product from other VOCs, source of free radicals in the upper troposphere
	Methyl ethyl ketone	7 days	1.48	Secondary oxidation product of alkanes; contributes to radical chemistry ⁶
	Methyl vinyl ketone	2 hours	9.65	Isoprene oxidation, participates in HO _x recycling; precursor to SOA and organic nitrates; influences ozone formation in forested regions ⁷
Terpenes ¹	Isoprene	3 hours	10.61	Plant emissions, sensitive to temperature, land use, and climate change, precursors of ozone and formaldehyde
	p-Cymene	1-5 hours	4.44	Plant emissions, sensitive to temperature, land use, and climate change, precursors of SOA
	Limonene		4.55	
	b-Myrcene		-	

Chemical family	Compound	Approximate lifetime	MIR (g O ₃ /g VOC emitted) (Venecek et al, 2018)	Importance in tropospheric processes (GAW (2007), unless stated)
	a-Pinene		4.51	
	b-Pinene		3.52	
	Camphene		4.51	
	D3-Carene		3.24	
	1,8-Cineol		-	

Notes: 1) NMVOC included in the GAW Reactive Gases Programme (GAW, 2007)
2) Singh et al. (2001), Seinfeld & Pandis (2016), Atkinson (2000) ;
3) Wennberg et al. (2018), Carlton et al. (2009) ;
4) Parrish et al. (1998), Seinfeld & Pandis (2016)
5) Atkinson & Arey (2003),
6) Singh et al. (1995), Atkinson & Arey (2003)
7) Wennberg et al. (2018), Paulot et al. (2009),

Table 5.1 shows that alkenes are the VOC group with the highest MIR, followed by most of the aromatic hydrocarbons, except benzene; alcohols, alkynes and alkanes have the lowest. In terms of lifetime, the shortest lived are terpenes, followed by alkenes and aromatics, with some exceptions: ethylene for alkenes and benzene, toluene and ethyl benzene for aromatics. The longest lived are alkanes, particularly ethane, then alkynes and alcohols. The long-lived VOCs will have an important role in long-range transported pollution and serve as a source of free radicals in remote areas; short-lived VOCs can impact ozone formation closer to sources and SOA formation.

A study is presented in Salameh et al. (2024), on the Maximum Ozone Formation Potential (MOFP). MOFP represents the maximum amount of ozone that can be formed from a given VOC under conditions favourable for ozone production and was obtained by multiplying the MIR (Carter, 2010; Venecek et al., 2018) by the measured concentration of each species. This provides a quantitative indicator of the relative importance of ambient VOCs for potential ozone formation. Salameh et al. (2024) show the results for an analysis including 20 VOCs most measured in 21 ACTRIS monitoring sites across Europe (see Figure 5.1), including Belgium (7 sites), Finland (2 sites), France (7 sites), Switzerland (1 site), Spain (1 site), and the UK (3 sites). The dataset comprised 3 industrial, 2 traffic (TR), 15 urban background (UB), and 1 suburban background (SUB) site (Figure 5.1). However, there is a limitation for data comparison due to the different protocols used for VOC measurements, and the disparity of VOC species measured at each site. The results showed that, on average across sites, toluene, m,p-xylene, 1-butene, n-butane, and i-pentane collectively accounted for more than 50% of the total MOFP (calculated as the sum of the individual 20 MOFPs), attributable to their relatively high concentrations and MIR values. The individual contributions for these VOCs are of 15% ± 9%, 13% ± 7%, 9% ± 8%, 9% ± 6%, and 7% ± 5%, respectively.

Figure 5.1: Individual contributions of 20 VOCs to the total (sum of the 20 VOCs) to MOFP (right), as averages for the datasets collected in 21 sites. The box represented the 5th–95th percentiles of ratios. The middle line and middle square represented the median values and mean values of ratios, respectively (Salameh et al., 2024).

5.1.2 Standard methods for sampling and measuring NMVOC

Historically, standard methods have been used to monitor VOCs. Back in the 90s, one standardized method for NMHCs based on manual sampling in steel canisters and subsequent lab analyses, and another standardized method for sampling oxygenated VOCs using DNPH tubes followed by analyses with HPLC in the lab, were used. During the years, a variety of instruments and measurement principles have been applied, including PTR-MS, Medusa monitors, specialised online GC monitors and adsorption tubes for aromatic species. The types of VOC species have also expanded from C2-C6 NMHC and a few light oxygenated VOCs at the start of the period to a very wide spectrum of species, including terpenes, alcohols, C7-C9 NMHC, acetonitrile and numerous branched saturated and unsaturated NMHC. For oxygenated VOCs (OVOCs), the original EMEP method based on sampling in DNPH adsorption tubes with subsequent lab analyses is still the method used at one site in Spain (ES0001). In addition, oxygenated VOCs are now measured by PTR-MS and by the GC-GC FID/FID system at Beromünster, Switzerland.

As mentioned in Section 2.3, though standard methods have been used for over 30 years, no method has been recognized as the reference method for sampling and measuring VOCs, other than benzene (see Annex VI A. 6 of the revised AAQD), by the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN). CEN is one of three European standardisation organisations in the EU, listed in ANNEX I of the Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012⁶. Within the CEN, standards are drafted by Technical Committees of particular scope on the basis of national participation by the CEN members, i.e. the National Standardisation Bodies of the European Union member states and some additional European countries. The technical decision-making body within the CEN system working on standardisation in the field of air quality and ozone precursors and benzene, CENTC264/WG13, is currently developing six European standards for the determination of a selection of VOC ozone precursors in ambient air (listed in Table 5.2):

- Automatic pumped sampling, preconcentration and online analysis by thermal desorption gas chromatography (TD/GC) with Flame Ionisation Detector (FID) and/or Mass Spectrometry Detector (MSD) for non-methane hydrocarbons (alkynes, alkanes, alkenes, aromatic hydrocarbons) with exclusion of formaldehyde

⁽⁶⁾ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2012/1025/oj/eng>

- Manual or automatic pumped sampling, followed by offline TD/GC with FID and/or MSD for non-methane hydrocarbons (alkynes, alkanes, alkenes, aromatic hydrocarbons) with exclusion of formaldehyde.
- Manual or automatic canister sampling, followed by offline TD/GC with FID and/or MSD for non-methane hydrocarbons (alkynes, alkanes, alkenes, aromatic hydrocarbons) with exclusion of formaldehyde.
- Diffusive sampling, followed by offline TD/GC with FID and/or MSD for non-methane hydrocarbons (alkynes, alkanes, alkenes, aromatic hydrocarbons) with exclusion of formaldehyde.
- Manual or automatic pumped sampling of formaldehyde on DNPH, followed by offline HPLC/UV.
- Diffusive sampling of formaldehyde on DNPH, followed by offline HPLC/UV.

A technical support document on the use of reference and non-reference methods, and on the quality assurance process to meet relevant data quality objectives for regulated air pollutants (EC, 2025) was published to provide guidance to the Member States. Although this technical support document is not legally binding, it provides an overview of current knowledge and best practices on air quality monitoring, including NMVOC, based on the CEN working group's work. Many of the considerations in this technical support document are based on the RI-URBANS/ACTRIS guidance document produced by Salameh et al. (2024).

Table 5.2 shows the recommended applicability of the six standards considered by the CEN working group on VOC ozone precursors, depending on the VOC to be monitored. This table is based on Table 6-2 in EC (2025). Table 5.2 shows that automated online GC analysis is the method capable of measuring all VOCs listed in Annex VII of the AAQD (see Table 2.5), except Formaldehyde. For the latter, only pumped/diffusive sampling in DNPH cartridges is suitable.

Salameh et al. (2024) has compiled information on the advantages and drawbacks of the six standards and their general features, which is also available in Tables 6-4 (online measurement methods) and 6-5 (offline measurement methods) in EC (2025) and reproduced here in Table 5.3. The documents also describe other technical aspects regarding quality assurance and quality control. This information is crucial for Member States to decide on the methods to monitor VOCs that they can support technically and financially. Salameh et al. (2024) concludes that the recommended analytical techniques for measuring VOCs require multiple instruments, since no single system can detect all 45 NMVOC species listed in the revised AAQD. In practice, even the most comprehensive RI-URBANS urban supersites measure up to 33 of these species. The recommendations are that, beyond instrument cost and maintenance, effective VOC monitoring depends on the availability of appropriate calibration standards and skilled personnel. As a result, many sites should rely on specialised research groups to perform these measurements for their AQ networks.

Table 5.2: Recommended applicability of future reference measurement methods for VOC ozone precursors listed in Annex VII of the AAQD (see Table 2.5), based on Table 6-2 of EC (2025). Dark green: method is suitable; light green: method is suitable with caveats; red: method is not suitable or not recommended.

Chemical family	Compound	Automated on-line GC analyses	Canister sampling	Pumped sampling in sorbent tubes	Diffusive sampling in sorbent tubes	Pumped/diffusive sampling in DNPH cartridges
Alcohols	Methanol					
	Ethanol					

Chemical family	Compound	Automated on-line GC analyses	Canister sampling	Pumped sampling in sorbent tubes	Diffusive sampling in sorbent tubes	Pumped/diffusive sampling in DNPH cartridges
Aldehyde	Formaldehyde					
	Acetaldehyde					
	Methacrolein					
Alkynes	Acetylene					
Alkanes	Ethane					
	Propane					
	n-Butane					
	i-Butane					
	n-Pentane					
	i-Pentane					
	n-Hexane					
	i-Hexane					
	n-Heptane					
	n-Octane					
i-Octane						
Alkenes	Ethylene					
	Propene / Propylene					
	1,3-Butadiene					
	1-Butene					
	Trans-2-Butene					
	cis-2-Butene					
	1-Pentene					
	2-Pentene					
Aromatic hydrocarbons	Benzene					
	Toluene / Methylbenzene					
	Ethyl benzene					
	m + p-Xylene					
	o-Xylene					
	1,2,4-Trimethylebenzene					
	1,2,3-Trimethylebenzene					
1,3,5-Trimethylebenzene						
Ketones	Acetone					
	Methyl ethyl ketone					
	Methyl vinyl ketone					
Terpenes	Isoprene					
	p-Cymene					
	Limonene					
	b-Myrcene					
	a-Pinene					
	b-Pinene					
	Camphene					
	D3-Carene					
1,8-Cineol						

Table 5.3: Overview of current and emerging online and offline measurement methods for VOC ozone precursors, pros and cons and general features based on Tables 6-4 and 6-5 of EC (2025).

Sampling and analysis techniques	Advantages	Drawbacks	General features and considerations
Online measurements			
Gas Chromatography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable for most VOC species, except for formaldehyde • Medium cost • High sensitivity • Excellent reproducibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slower time resolution (if more than a few species are measured) • Difficult to identify more polar, surface sticky compounds • Sensitivity might decrease with time, prone to retention time shifts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depending on ambient conditions, consider the use of moisture, ozone, CO₂ traps and particulate filters. • Sampling times: 20-90 min, limits of detection: low pmol/mol range • Use of pre-concentrator and FID/MSD/PID detectors
Proton Transfer Reaction Mass Spectrometer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trace gases analysed shortly after sampling, continuous meas. • Soft ionization & limited fragmentation • Large resolving power, high sensitivity, high time resolution • Powerful to detect oxy-VOCs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blind to alkanes • No selective measurements of most alkenes and alcohols • No isomeric separation • High cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ionization based on proton affinity (reagent ions: H₃O⁺, NH₄⁺), • Sampling times: down to hundreds of milliseconds • Limits of detection: low pmol/mol range
Selected ion flow tube mass spectrometry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soft ionization technique (softer than PTR-MS) • Fast analysis of specific trace gases in polluted atmosphere and exhaled breath 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unit mass resolution • Lower sensitivity than PTR-MS • Larger losses of reagent ions than PTR-MS • High cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dilution with helium • Reagent ions: H₃O⁺, NO⁺, and O₂⁺ • Sampling times: seconds • Limits of detection: nmol/mol range
Chemical ionization mass spectrometer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trace gases analysed shortly after sampling, continuous meas. • Soft ionization & limited fragmentation • Large resolving power, high sensitivity, high time resolution • Powerful to detect oxy-VOCs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No isomeric separation • No isobaric separation • High cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ionization based on charge transfer or hydride abstraction (reagent ions: Br⁻, I⁻, Cl⁻, CF₃O⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SF₆⁻)
Offline measurements			
Diffusion sampler with sorbent material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extended range of different VOC families (captured simultaneously) by axial or radial diffusion into a sampler containing typically one sorbent material low sampling costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relative low sampling rates and large uncertainties • Sampling of VOCs is sorbent specific (no universal solution) • Possible influence of humidity and temperature • Need of protection shields; limitation in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When selecting a suitable sorbent consider: sorbent sampling rate for the specific VOC, artefacts, hydrophobicity, inertness, thermal stability and fragility • Sampling periods of 1 day - 4 weeks, analyses thermal or solvent desorption by GC-FID/MS

		desorption efficiency (solvent desorption) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slower time resolution (if more than a few species are measured) 	
Pumped sampler with sorbent material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extended range of different VOC families (captured simultaneously) with single or multi-layered sorbent-packed tubes with up to four different adsorbents, good adsorption properties, low sampling costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible instability of the particles of the adsorbent, possible degradation during preparation or over time, possible losses due to stickiness or through aerosol formation and/or back-diffusion of target compounds • Limitation in desorption efficiency (solvent desorption) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When selecting a suitable adsorbent or adsorbent combination consider: adsorbent strength, breakthrough and safe sample volume for each VOC, artefacts, hydrophobicity, inertness, thermal stability and fragility • Typical sampling times: few hours – 7 days, sampling flows: 50-200 mL min⁻¹, analyses thermal or solvent desorption by GC-FID/MS
Pumped with DNPH cartridge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific for carbonyl compounds that cannot be sampled in sorbent materials • Low sampling costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible contamination during preparation, storage at dark and at <4 oC, biases due to humidity impact on ketones and ozone interferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sampling times: 1-24h, sampling flow 1 L/min • Liquid extraction and analysis by HPLC/UV
Miniaturized adsorbent-based air sampling techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy operation, short sampling times small sampling volumes, small/no organic solvent consumption, automation of analytical operations, and on-line coupling with analytical instruments • Low sampling costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage instability, possibly not quantitative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Techniques: needle trap microextraction, in-tube extraction, sorption trap, solid-phase microextraction (fibre, Arrow, retracted fibre), thin-film microextraction, solid-phase dynamic extraction, and stir bar sorptive extraction • Analyses by GC/MS, PTR/MS
Canisters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whole air sampling, filled canisters are either analysed on-site or transported to analytical laboratory • Medium sampling costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible contamination (memory effects) • Adsorptive losses of larger or more functionalized compounds (>C7) during storage or transport • Potential interactions with co-collected water vapour and oxidants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider using canisters with passivated inner surface when sampling reactive VOCs • Sampling times: grab samples or time averaged samples from 30 minutes up to one day • Analyses by GC-FID/MS

5.1.3 NMVOC data in the e-reporting database

Information on NMVOC reported by Member States is submitted to the air quality (AQ) e-reporting database hosted by the EEA⁷. The AQ e-reporting database gathers observational raw data since 2013 and provides statistics calculated by EEA, time series of observations and metadata associated with the observations⁸. These metadata provide useful information such as the organisation responsible of the measurements, the type of the station (background, industrial or traffic), the area of the station (rural, urban or suburban), the location of the station (latitude, longitude and altitude), as well as information on the measurement methodology (sampling equipment, analytical methods).

The e-reporting database contains measurements for several NMVOC, of which 33 are listed in the revised AAQD. Table 5.4 lists the VOCs mentioned by the revised AAQD and their respective pollutant identification numbers in the EEA vocabulary⁹. If the compound is not listed in the EEA vocabulary on pollutants, it is indicated as NA under pollutant ID EEA in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Ozone precursor listed in Annex VII and the respective pollutant identification number in the EEA vocabulary.

Group	Compound	Pollutant ID EEA
Alcohols	Methanol	NA
	Ethanol	NA
Aldehyde	Formaldehyde	25
	Acetaldehyde/Ethanal	427
	Methacrolein	318
Alkynes	Acetylene	432
	Ethane	428
	Propane	503
	n-Butane	394
	i-Butane	447
	n-Pentane	486
	i-Pentane	450
	n-Hexane	443
	i-Hexane	316
	n-Heptane	441
	n-Octane	475
	i-Octane	449
Alkenes	Ethylene	430
	Propene / Propylene	505
	1,3-Butadiene	24
	1-Butene	6005
	Trans-2-Butene	6006
	cis-2-Butene	6007
	1-Pentene	6008
	2-Pentene	6009
Aromatics	Benzene	20

⁽⁷⁾ cdr.eionet.europa.eu

⁽⁸⁾ <https://eeadmz1-cws-wp-air02-dev.azurewebsites.net/>

⁽⁹⁾ <https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabularies?expand=true&expanded=&folderId=1#folder-1>

	Toluene	21
	m,p-Xylene	464
	o-Xylene	482
	Ethyl benzene	431
	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	6011
	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	6012
	1.2.5-Trimethylbenzene	6013
Ketones	Acetone	NA
	Methyl ethyl ketone	NA
	Methyl vinyl ketone	NA
Terpenes	Isoprene	451
	p-Cymene	NA
	Limonene	NA
	β -Myrcene	NA
	α -Pinene	NA
	β -Pinene	NA
	Camphene	NA
	Δ^3 -Carene	NA
	1,8-Cineol	NA

Figure 5.2 Figure 7.1 shows the number of time series available at the EEA database and accessed via the EEA's AQ portal per year per VOC groups defined in Annex VII and Table 5.5 discretises those numbers per compound. Since 2013, the aromatics have been the most frequently reported VOC group, with benzene the most frequently reported compound, as expected since it is a regulated pollutant, followed by toluene. Ethyl benzene, m,p-Xylene and o-Xylene are also reported for many sampling points, as these three aromatic hydrocarbons, together with benzene and toluene - BTEX, are common aromatic hydrocarbons found in petroleum, used as industrial solvents, and known for their distinct odours, high volatility, and flammability, posing health risks like carcinogenicity (benzene) and neurological effects (IARC, 2018; Bolden et al, 2015). The alkanes are the second group, with most measurements, though orders of magnitude lower than the aromatics. However, independently of the group, the data show that the number of time series has decreased over the past decade.

A positive note, most of the time series are for compounds with the highest of the MOFPs, toluene and m,p-xylene (aromatics), as discussed in Section 5.1. However, the other three compounds - i-pentane, n-butane (alkanes) and 1-butane (alkene), have seen the number of sampling points being reduced since 2013; currently, only 2/sampling points actively report these to EEA.

Figure 5.2: Number of time series reported in the AQ e-reporting database from 2013 to 2023 per chemical group defined in the AAQD.

Table 5.5: The number of time series per compound reported to the EEA from 2013 to 2023.

Compound	Group AAQD	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Acetaldehyde/ Ethanal	Aldehyde	8	2	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
Formaldehyde	Aldehyde	8	2	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
i-Hexane	Alkanes	7	7	7	7	6	7	6	7	3	3	3
i-Octane	Alkanes	9	9	7	8	6	8	7	8	4	4	4
Ethane	Alkanes	8	7	5	6	4	5	5	5	2	2	2
n-Hexane	Alkanes	10	9	7	8	6	7	6	7	3	3	3
n-Heptane	Alkanes	10	10	7	8	6	8	7	8	4	4	4
n-Octane	Alkanes	9	9	7	8	6	8	7	8	4	4	4
n-Pentane	Alkanes	9	9	7	8	6	8	7	8	4	4	4
i-Butane	Alkanes	9	8	6	6	5	6	5	6	2	2	2
i-Pentane	Alkanes	9	9	7	7	6	7	6	7	3	3	3
n-Butane	Alkanes	9	8	6	6	5	6	5	6	2	2	2
Propane	Alkanes	7	7	5	6	4	5	5	5	2	2	2
Propene / Propylene	Alkenes	7	7	5	6	4	5	5	5	2	2	2
1,3- Butadiene	Alkenes	10	9	7	7	6	7	6	7	2	2	2
1-Pentene	Alkenes	10	9	7	8	6	8	7	8	4	4	4
1-Butene	Alkenes	9	8	6	7	5	6	5	6	2	2	2
Ethylene	Alkenes	7	7	5	6	4	5	5	5	2	2	2
2-Pentene	Alkenes	3	3	2	2	3	4	2	4	3	3	3
cis-2- Butene	Alkenes	9	8	6	6	5	6	5	6	2	2	2

Trans-2-Butene	Alkenes	8	8	6	6	5	6	5	6	2	2	2
Acetylene	Alkynes	7	7	5	6	4	5	5	5	2	2	2
1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	10	9	7	8	8	10	9	10	6	6	6
1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	10	9	7	8	8	10	9	10	6	6	6
1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	13	10	9	9	9	11	10	11	7	7	7
Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	172	141	72	49	46	92	85	87	72	72	70
Toluene	Aromatics	268	229	151	107	97	158	148	142	120	113	109
Benzene	Aromatics	597	550	576	608	593	616	555	571	598	535	521
m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	191	159	89	68	67	103	100	95	77	76	74
o-Xylene	Aromatics	191	159	88	57	53	103	100	100	91	90	87
Isoprene	Terpenes	8	8	6	8	5	7	6	7	3	3	3

The data reported show that there is more consistency across time for aromatics, as expected, but also for alkanes and alkenes. Considering only the sampling points with data reported for more than two years, the analysis of the data reported shows that (see Table A1.1 and Figures A1.1 – A1.11 in Annex 1 for the full data):

- Aldehydes (see Figure A1.1): only France reports, but only one station reports for more than two years of data.
- Alkanes (see Figure A1.2): measured in Austria (1), Denmark (1), Spain (1), Poland (1), Sweden (4), and UK (4), these include only stations with more than two years of data. All the stations measure several alkanes.
- Alkenes (Figure A1.3): measured in Austria (1), Denmark (1), Spain (1), Poland (1), Sweden (4), and UK (4), these include only stations with more than two years of data. All the stations measure several alkenes.
- Alkynes (acetylene, see Figure A1.4): continuous reporting for acetylene (alkynes) and isoprene (terpene) between 2013 and 2023 for a station in Sweden and another in Poland. There are also data for stations located in the UK (4) until 2020.
- Aromatics:
 - 1.2.3/1.2.4/1.3.5-trimethylbenzenes (see Figure A1.5) are measured in Austria (1), Bulgaria (1), Denmark (1), Finland (1), Poland (1), Spain (1), Sweden (1), and UK (4). All of them, except the Finnish station, measure the three compounds.
 - Benzene (see Figure A1.6) is measured in 947 stations, with 361 measuring for more than 10 years across Europe: Austria (6), Belgium (15), Germany (22), Estonia (4), Finland (1), France (24), Croatia (3), Italy (122), Lithuania (1), Malta (1), Norway (7), Poland (31), Portugal (1), Slovenia (2), Slovakia (9), Spain (86), and Sweden (3). Other countries with stations reporting data for more than two years are Bulgaria (1), Czechia (24), Cyprus (1), Denmark (1), Ireland (1), Greece (7), Luxembourg (1), and UK (37).
 - Ethyl benzene (see Figure A1.7) has been reported for more than 10 years in Austria (1), Croatia (12), Germany (3), Finland (1), France (1), Italy (4), Poland (1), Slovenia (2), and Spain (11). Other countries with stations reporting data for more than two years are Ireland (1), Denmark (1), Greece (1), and Sweden (1).

- m.p-Xylene (see Figure A1.8) has been reported for more than 10 years in Austria (1), Croatia (11), Germany (13), Finland (1), France (1), Italy (2), Malta (1), Poland (1), Slovenia (2), and Spain (11). Other countries with stations reporting data for more than two years are Ireland (1), Denmark (1), Greece (1), and Sweden (1).
- o-Xylene (see Figure A1.9) has been reported for more than 10 years in Austria (1), Croatia (11), Germany (13), Finland (1), France (1), Italy (8), Malta (1), Poland (1), Slovenia (2), and Spain (11). Other countries with stations reporting data for more than two years are Ireland (1), Denmark (1), Greece (1), and Sweden (1).
- Toluene (see Figure A1.10) has been reported for more than 10 years in Austria (1), Croatia (12), Germany (25), Finland (1), France (1), Italy (9), Malta (1), Poland (1), Slovenia (2), and Spain (11). Other countries with stations reporting data for more than two years are Ireland (1), Denmark (1), Greece (1), Latvia (1), Lithuania (1), Portugal (1), Sweden (2), Switzerland (2), and UK (5).
- Terpenes (isoprene, see Figure A1.11): same as acetylene (same stations), and there is continuous monitoring in Spain (until 2020) and in Denmark, both countries with a single station.

5.1.4 EMEP and GAW monitoring program

VOC data from the EMEP VOC monitoring program, research projects and field campaigns are hosted in EBAS¹⁰. The database allows querying the data, provides time series and metadata associated with the observations. Most of the institutions providing VOC data are participating in the ACTRIS infrastructure, which results in an extensive effort with data checking.

The latest EMEP report on VOC (Solberg et al., 2024) shows the status of the network over the 2003-2022 period. In 2022, the EMEP VOC program included 19 measurement sites, see Figure 5.3. The measured VOCs consist of various groups of species (see Table 5.6), which could be split into NMHC and oxygenated species (OVOC). Monitoring of NMHC is carried out at all sites except at the Spanish site, whereas OVOC are measured at fewer sites.

Beginning in the early 1990s with standardised techniques involving manual sampling in steel canisters and adsorption tubes analysed in laboratories, the range of methods now includes various instruments and measurement principles, such as automated continuous monitors and manual flask samples. The VOC monitoring at EMEP sites has become more diverse with time in terms of methods and instrumentation. Figure 5.4 shows the number of time series available during the 1992-2022 period and per chemical group or instrument type, and Figure 5.5 shows, for the same period, the data availability per station and per instrument.

Table 5.6: Description of the VOC species used in each category described in the analysis.

General name	Lumped species
NMHC	ethane, propane, n-butane, 2-methylpropane, n-pentane, 2-methylbutane, 2-2-dimethylpropane, ethene, propene, butenes, 1-butene, trans-2-butene, cis-2-butene, pentenes, cis-2-pentene, trans-2-pentene, 1-3-butadiene, 2-methylpropene, 2-methyl-1-butene, 3-methyl-1-butene, butenes, 1-pentene, 2-methyl-2-butene, 1-pentene, ethyne, propyne, 1-butyne, n-hexane, n-heptane, n-octane, n-nonane, 2-2-4-trimethylpentane, 2-2-dimethylbutane, 2-methylhexane, 2-methylpentane, 3-methylpentane, 2-2-4-trimethylpentane, 2-2-dimethylpentane, 2+3-methylheptane, isohexanes, isoheptanes, 2-2-dimethylbutane, 2-3-dimethylbutane, 2-3-dimethylpentane, 3-methylheptane, unresolved_C6_hydrocarbons, cyclo-hexane, methyl-cyclohexane, methyl-

⁽¹⁰⁾ ebas.nilu.no

	cyclopentane, 1-hexene, cyclo-pentene, 2-4-dimethylpentane,3-3-dimethylpentane, 2-2-3-trimethylbutane)
OVOC	methanal, ethanal, propanal, 2-methyl-propenal, 2-oxopropanal, 2-propenal, benzaldehyde, butanals, pentanal, hexanal, 2-methylpropenal, ethanedial,3-methylbenzaldehyde, 2-butenal, 4-methylbenzaldehyde, 3-buten-2-one, butanone, propanone, valeraldehyde_o-tolualdehyde, 3-methylbutanal, 2-methylbenzaldehyde
Aromatics	benzene, toluene, o-xylene, m-p-xylene, ethylbenzene, 1-2-4-trimethylbenzene, 1-3-5-trimethylbenzene, 1-2-3-trimethylbenzene, 1-ethyl-3-methylbenzene, 1-ethyl-4-methylbenzene, 1-3-5-trimethylbenzene, 1-2-4-trimethylbenzene
BVOC	isoprene, eucalyptol, camphene, p-cymene, beta-pinene, 3-carene, alpha-pinene, limonene, monoterpenes
Alcohols	2-propanol, methanol, ethanol, n-propanol

Figure 5.3: VOC monitoring sites in 2022 (Solberg et al., 2024).

Figure 5.4: VOC monitoring (number of timeseries) during the 1992-2022 period per chemical group (Solberg et al., 2024).

Figure 5.5: VOC monitoring (number of timeseries) during the 1992-2022 period per instrument (Solberg et al., 2024).

Figure 5.6: VOC monitoring during the 1992-2022 period per site (Solberg et al., 2024).

Figure 5.4, Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6 are relevant to understanding the magnitude of the data available and the continuity of the time series per individual station. The data analysis shows that the VOC data available varies on a yearly basis, and most of the data available is for NMHC. The data shows many stations with long-term monitoring, which correlates well with the amount of data available and the increase in the use of online continuous monitoring. However, when discretising the data per component, it can be hard to access the data for a continuous and long period of time.

According to the official emission data, there have been marked reductions in anthropogenic emissions of VOCs during the last few decades in Europe. On the same token, several studies using EMEP data have revealed a decline in the measured concentrations:

- Derwent et al. (2014) showed substantial declines in C2-C8 hydrocarbons concentration in the UK, mostly at urban/suburban locations, with recent levels close to an order of magnitude below the levels in the early 1990s. Exponential declines in concentration of approximately -11% y^{-1} to -22% y^{-1} were observed during 1994-2012. They also found a marked difference between ethane and propane, which showed relatively stable levels, whereas other alkanes showed pronounced declines.
- Sauvage et al. (2009) and Waked et al. (2016) reported clear decreases in most NMHCs at French EMEP rural sites (see Figure 5.7). Ethane was an exception to this and showed more stable levels.
- Analyses of the twenty years of NMHC monitoring at the EMEP/GAW site Pallas in the Finnish Arctic revealed a significant downward trend only for ethyne (Hellen et al., 2015), concluding that other source regions than the EU were dominating the NMHC levels at the site.
- Solberg et al. (2024) showed the decrease of NMHC levels measured at Hohenpeissenberg (DE0043) during the period 2003-2022, see Figure 5.8. The figure is based on results from the AirGAM model (Walker et al., 2023) which is a nonlinear regression model that adjusts the trends to discount the effects of meteorology developed at NILU in cooperation with the EEA.

Figure 5.7: Annual trend rate (% year⁻¹) for selected key VOC tracers and representatives of major VOC's families (Alkanes, Alkenes, aromatics, etc ...) in French urban (Paris, Strasbourg and Lyon) and rural (Peyrusse-Vieille, Tardière and Donon) atmospheres. Trend results presented in white color are not significant (level of confidence below 90%), from Waked et al., 2016.

Figure 5.8: Meteorological adjusted trend in relative concentrations of NMHCs at Hohenpeissenberg 2003-2022 as calculated by the AirGAM model (Solberg et al. (2024)).

5.2 Methane in-situ monitoring

Although methane has a low MIR (0.0144 g O₃/g VOC), it has a very long atmospheric lifetime (~10 years, Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). Methane is also classified as a greenhouse gas, with a 100-year global warming potential 28 times that of carbon dioxide and 84 times that of carbon dioxide on a 20-year timescale (IEA, Methane Tracker 2021). The main methane-emitting sectors are agriculture (40%), fossil fuels (35%), and waste management (20%) (CCAC, 2021).

The primary goals of measuring ozone precursors like methane include analysing trends in these precursors, assessing the effectiveness of emission reduction strategies, verifying the consistency of emission inventories, supporting the understanding of ozone formation and dispersion processes, evaluating photochemical models, and identifying emission sources responsible for observed pollution concentrations.

There are non-reference methods for measuring methane. Methane is typically measured by GC-FID, used for online monitoring of methane and NMVOC. However, laser spectroscopy techniques, such as cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) and direct absorption spectroscopy (DAS) or Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, are increasingly utilised. Zellweger et al. (2016) show that laser spectroscopy has a higher temporal data coverage and better repeatability and linearity. the

Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) network has been using CRDS wisely. The quality assurance and quality control requirements are available in GAW report 185 (GAW, 2009).

Methane data have been reported to EBAS since 2013 in 35 stations across 11 European countries (AT, BE, CZ, DE, ES, FR, GB, IE, IT, MT, NO) under the WMO/GAW and EMEP programmes. The ICOS network is one of the major coordinated methane monitoring infrastructures in Europe, focused on high-quality, long-term greenhouse gas measurements, including methane, with data from 39 stations across 13 European countries available at the ICOS data portal¹¹. In terms of e-Reporting, the methane pollutant ID is given in Table 5.7 and the evolution of reported time series from 2013 to 2023 is presented in Table 5.8. As illustrated in Figure 5.9, methane reporting remains limited to Germany, where ten stations currently submit measurements to the EEA.

Table 5.7: Ozone precursor – methane - listed in Annex VII and the respective pollutant identification number in the EEA vocabulary.

Group	Compound	Pollutant ID EEA
Alkanes	Methane	41

Table 5.8: The number of time series for methane reported to the EEA from 2013 to 2023.

Compound	Group AAQD	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Methane	Methane	0	0	0	7	7	7	9	9	9	10	10

Figure 5.9: Methane time series reported to EEA.

Although global in scope, the Total Carbon Column Observing Network (TCCON) also includes several European stations that provide precise column-averaged methane measurements (and other gases). TCCON data are often used to validate satellite methane products and to complement surface

⁽¹¹⁾ <https://data.icos-cp.eu/portal/>

measurements with vertical column information. The data have been available since 2004 for many European stations¹² as shown in Figure 5.10.

Figure 5.10: CH₄ monthly medians from all TCCON sites, including 14 European sites (TCCON, 2025).

5.3 Remote sensing

Satellite remote sensing has emerged as a critical tool for observing the spatial and temporal distribution of VOCs and their oxidation products. Although most VOCs cannot be retrieved directly from space due to weak absorption features or short lifetimes, certain species, particularly formaldehyde (HCHO) and methane, serve as effective proxies for short-lived species. Formaldehyde is a ubiquitous intermediate in the oxidation chains of most non-methane VOCs, and because its atmospheric lifetime is on the order of hours, enhanced HCHO columns from satellite measurements provide meaningful information about underlying VOC emissions (De Smedt et al., 2018). Modern satellite VOC retrieval relies on UV–visible spectroscopy, where backscattered sunlight is measured at high spectral resolution. Formaldehyde exhibits distinct UV absorption features, making it suitable for operational remote sensing. Retrieval algorithms correct for interfering with absorbers, aerosols, clouds, and surface reflectance.

Global observations of methane from space began with the SCIAMACHY instrument in 2003 and continued through 2014 and have since been supported by the TANSO-FTS instrument aboard GOSAT since 2009, supporting methane emission inventories (Jacob et al., 2022).

The first spaceborne observations of formaldehyde were achieved using instruments such as GOME on ERS-2 and SCIAMACHY on ENVISAT. These sensors demonstrated the feasibility of global VOC proxy monitoring but had limited spatial resolution (tens of kilometers), restricting the ability to resolve fine-scale emission patterns. OMI, launched in 2004, significantly advanced the field by providing daily global coverage with improved resolution. Its data forms a crucial bridge connecting past and present VOC time series. However, the true breakthrough came with the launch of TROPOMI in 2017, offering more than an order-of-magnitude improvement in resolution compared to OMI—down to 3.5 × 5.5

⁽¹²⁾ <https://tcon-wiki.caltech.edu/>

km² and later 3.5 × 3.5 km². The development of such high-resolution satellite spectrometers has revolutionized the ability to observe short-lived species with unprecedented detail, with consistency across missions has been improved through harmonized methodologies (De Smedt et al., 2021).

Missions such as Sentinel-4 launched in July 2025 and Sentinel-5 in August 2025 will further enhance temporal coverage, while geostationary observations promise near-continuous monitoring over selected regions. Sentinel-4, positioned in geostationary orbit on MTG-S1, now provides hourly observations over Europe and North Africa. This temporal resolution captures diurnal cycles in VOC emissions, particularly those from biogenic sources influenced by solar radiation and temperature – HCHO and glyoxal (CHOCHO); it also observes ozone and CH₄ (ESA, 2017). Sentinel-5, aboard MetOp-SG A1, offers daily global coverage with enhanced spectral and radiometric performance on constituents of the atmosphere such as ozone, HCHO, CHOCHO and CH₄ (ESA, 2020). It continues and improves upon TROPOMI's measurements of formaldehyde and other trace gases critical for atmospheric composition studies.

For methane specifically, the expanding constellation of satellites, including TROPOMI, MethaneSAT (launched in 2024), and GOSAT-GW (launched in June 2025), is progressively improving detection capabilities from global mapping to facility-scale monitoring (see Section 8 for a detailed assessment). Using TROPOMI data from 2019 to 2023, Pendergrass et al. (2025) assessed trends and seasonality of global methane emissions and found that emissions in Europe have decreased by less than 8% per year. Regarding formaldehyde, De Smedt et al. (2021) report that HCHO levels are lower in Europe than in Asia or the United States of America, but some urban areas remain detectable in Southern European countries. Monthly and yearly averaged HCHO columns from October 2004 to December 2020 show a stable level of this VOC proxy over Europe.

Despite significant progress, remote sensing of VOCs remains limited to a few proxy species, primarily formaldehyde. Clouds, aerosols, and low surface reflectance reduce retrieval sensitivity (Kylling et al, 2018). While formaldehyde provides valuable information on total VOC oxidation and biogenic emissions, it cannot distinguish between individual NMVOC species with different reactivities and source signatures. Similarly, satellite observations alone cannot fully characterise all methane emission sources, particularly small and diffuse sources such as agricultural activities. This limitation underscores the complementarity role of in-situ monitoring networks (Section 5.1), which remain essential for characterizing the full spectrum of VOC species listed in the revised AAQD, assessing source specific contributions and supporting the development of targeted emissions control strategies. An integrated monitoring strategy combining satellite observations with ground-based networks and in-situ VOC measurements (see Section 5.1) is therefore necessary to support both ozone mitigation and top-down verification of methane emissions.

5.4 Section highlights

This section demonstrates that establishing a **European monitoring network for methane and NMVOC** that is compliant with the **revised AAQD** is technically feasible but requires **strategic prioritization, coordination with existing infrastructures, and a phased implementation approach**.

Europe already benefits from several long-standing and well-established monitoring programmes and research infrastructures, including **EMEP, WMO/GAW, ICOS, and ACTRIS**, which collectively provide high-quality measurements of many ozone precursors, including methane and a substantial subset of NMVOC. These programmes provide a strong foundation in **measurement expertise, quality assurance procedures, trained personnel, and data management systems**, thereby significantly reducing the need to build an entirely new monitoring infrastructure.

The revised AAQD introduces an **expanded list of NMVOC species** and, for the first time, explicitly references **methane as an ozone precursor**, reflecting advances in scientific understanding of ozone formation and atmospheric chemistry. While the AAQD requires NMVOC and methane measurements only **“when appropriate”**, the analysis shows that many of the compounds listed—particularly **aromatics and alkenes with high ozone formation potential**—are already measured at several sites across Europe and reported through the EEA e-reporting system. This demonstrates that **partial compliance already exists**, especially for compounds most relevant to urban ozone formation.

However, **the current monitoring landscape is fragmented**, with large differences in the number of compounds measured, temporal coverage, and applied methodologies across Member States. Long-term, continuous time series are mainly available **for aromatic hydrocarbons** (e.g. benzene, toluene, xylenes), while measurements of **alkenes, alkanes, oxygenated VOCs, terpenes, and methane** are more limited in spatial coverage and continuity. This heterogeneity poses challenges for the **harmonized implementation** of the revised AAQD, and assessment of policies implemented at the European level.

Aligning monitoring priorities with dominant emission sources is essential to maximize the effectiveness of network design. As detailed in Section 7.2, **residential heating, solvent use, coating applications and manure management now account for 56% of EU NMVOC emissions**. Based on the EMEP/EEA Guidebook, these activities release a characteristic suite of compounds including aromatic hydrocarbons (toluene, xylenes, ethylbenzene, benzene, trimethylbenzenes), ketones (acetone, methyl ethyl ketone), alcohols (ethanol, methanol), and alkanes used as propellants or solvents (propane, butane, n-hexane, n-heptane). Most of these compounds are included in Annex VII of the revised AAQD, **with toluene and m,p-xylene alone contributing approximately 28% to the Maximum Ozone Formation Potential** (Salameh et al., 2024). For regions where these sources dominate, monitoring strategies should therefore prioritize **BTEX compounds, trimethylbenzenes, and key ketones** at urban and industrial sites. Such targeted monitoring would provide essential data to assess the effectiveness of emission reduction measures.

It could also be beneficial to implement **BTEX monitoring more broadly across Europe**, as these compounds pose a **significant health burden, have a high ozone formation potential**, and are good **indicators of petrochemical and wood-burning emissions**. Other networks could be established to focus on specific sources, such as **biogenic emissions (terpenes)**, to further understand their impact on the formation of ozone. However, their high reactivity may hinder the investment as they require online monitoring and technical personnel with experience in these NMVOC. Finally, **the lack of formaldehyde data** may hinder efforts to validate satellite-derived concentration levels. It would be beneficial to obtain additional in-situ data for this compound.

The same principle applies to **methane monitoring**. As detailed in Section 7.1, **EU CH₄ emissions have decreased by 39% since 1990**, but trends vary considerably across sectors and Member States. **Agriculture remains the dominant source**, with enteric fermentation accounting for the largest share of total emissions, while the waste and energy sectors have achieved significant reductions. However, **emissions from biological waste treatment are rising** as composting and anaerobic digestion expand. Given this sectoral distribution, CH₄ monitoring strategies should prioritize: **(1) agricultural regions with high livestock densities; (2) areas with significant biogas production and biological waste treatment facilities; and (3) regions with remaining fossil fuel infrastructure**. Currently, **only**

Germany reports CH₄ measurements to the EEA e-reporting database, highlighting the need for expanded monitoring coverage. Existing research infrastructures and programmes provide a foundation for expanding CH₄ monitoring: **ICOS** focuses on greenhouse gas observations, **EMEP** and **WMO/GAW** offer long-term background measurements, and **TCCON** provides valuable benchmarks for validating satellite-derived data. Leveraging these networks would support a more comprehensive monitoring approach aligned with the revised AAQD requirements.

Beyond strategic prioritization, **technical considerations** are central to network design. The section shows that **no single analytical technique can cover all NMVOC species** listed in Annex VII, confirming that compliance will require a combination of methods, including **automated online gas chromatography, targeted offline sampling (e.g. canisters or sorbent tubes), and DNPH-based techniques for carbonyls**. Gas chromatography can also be used for methane, though other techniques are gaining ground. The ongoing development of **CEN standards** and the availability of guidance from EC (2025) and ACTRIS/RI-URBANS provide a clear pathway to harmonized, quality-assured measurements that meet regulatory data quality objectives.

Overall, the findings indicate **that compliance with the revised AAQD is achievable** through a **tiered network design**, combining:

- **Core, continuous monitoring sites** (e.g. urban background and regional background stations) equipped with advanced online instrumentation,
- **Supplementary sites** using simpler or lower-cost methods to improve spatial coverage,
- **Strong integration with existing European research infrastructures** to optimize costs, ensure methodological consistency, and sustain long-term data availability.
- **Integration of satellite observations with ground-based measurements** to enhance spatial coverage and support top-down verification of emission inventories.

Such an approach would allow Member States to align regulatory air quality monitoring with scientific best practice, **improve understanding of ozone formation drivers**, and support **more effective ozone mitigation strategies** across Europe.

6 Overview of ozone air quality plans

The implementation of adapted VOC monitoring strategy is essential for establishing and monitoring the effectiveness of precursor reduction measures. This strategy must account for local emissions sources, VOC species most relevant to ozone formation, and appropriate measurement instrumentation. Such precursor reduction measures, along with the comprehensive regional and national ozone plans that integrate all mitigation measures, have become mandatory under the revised AAQD when target values are exceeded as outlined before. The following section summarizes existing plans across Member States to document current efforts and identify remaining actions needed.

A common framework for transboundary cooperation on air pollution (CLRTAP) was established at international level along with the negotiation of the Gothenburg protocol to Abate Acidification,

Eutrophication and Ground-level Ozone. In line with these international commitments, the NEC Directive sets national emission reduction for Member States and the EU for ozone precursors (NO_x and NMVOCs) and other major pollutants (SO₂, NH₃ and PM_{2.5}) in the aim of decreasing their concentrations in ambient air. To meet these commitments at national level, air quality plans targeting ozone must be designed, and appropriate measures must be implemented to reduce the frequency of occurrence of ozone peak concentrations and exceedances of target values. Indeed, the revised AAQD established long-term and short-term standards for ozone such as detailed in section 2, table 2.1. Ozone mitigation strategies are not straightforward as it is a secondary pollutant characterized by non-linearity in the chemical processes involving NO_x, NMVOCs (from local and remote emissions) and CH₄ (from global background) as main precursors. This represents a real challenge for countries depending on their territory (meteorological conditions, geographical location, insolation and dominant activities leading to precursors emissions), to define such a plan and that often requires preliminary studies. In this context, this section provides an overview of some of the ozone plans implemented by European countries and makes the link with ozone target values exceedances in the e-reporting database.

In this purpose, an Eionet consultation was launched to the Thematic Group on Air to gather information on existing national or regional air quality plans for ozone currently in place or under development, scientific studies or research projects related to ozone formation and any relevant policies or measures implemented to address ozone pollution in the EEA member countries. Twelve countries responded, including Croatia, France and Spain which have developed or already implemented air quality plans for O₃ as summarized in Table 6.1. Boxes are coloured grey when information has been provided defining the category of documents.

Table 6.1: Summary of the feedback of the Member States to the EIONET consultation for air quality ozone plans.

Country	AQ plans for ozone	Measures	Scientific studies	Communication	Other
Croatia					
France					
Spain					
Germany					
Switzerland					
Bulgaria					
The Netherlands					
Ireland					
Estonia					
Malta					
Austria					
Poland					

Most of the countries conducted scientific studies and research projects with the following main objectives: the prediction of surface ozone levels, the understanding of the mechanism of ozone formation, the qualification of the potential contribution of precursors to O₃ formation, the source apportionment on O₃ precursors and the impact of climate change on ozone levels in the ambient air. In addition, actions for communication are carried out in France by offering educational video online on ozone pollution and on actors involved in regional plans. Switzerland produced online factsheets to inform and present the situation of the country regarding ozone pollution.

In the following, the main air quality plans for ozone that are under development and already implemented in Croatia, France and Spain, are presented. Those are put into perspective with the exceedances of the target value that were reported in the e-reporting database.

6.1 Air Quality Plans for Ozone in Croatia

The Action Plan for the Reduction of Ground level Ozone Pollution¹³ has been implemented at national level in Croatia. This plan focuses on two main lines of action:

1. Reducing emissions of hitherto unregulated or poorly regulated sources of ozone precursor emissions such as maritime, ocean and aviation, which are steadily increasing. Emissions in these sectors are projected to increase significantly in the coming decades.
2. Continue rigorous application of existing measures to reduce emissions of ozone precursors, with a focus on further reducing emissions of NO_x compounds and methane, as a priority in the most sensitive areas. In addition, it is essential to link the activities of all major sectors so that emission control measures cover cumulative and not only individual effects of emissions from these sectors.

In this regard, the effectiveness of measures to reduce emissions of ozone precursors in Croatia from different sections on ground level ozone concentrations were analysed based on modelling study (EMEP4HR¹⁴). It emerged that tackling ozone requires international, national and local efforts to effectively reduce emissions of ozone precursors (NO_x and NMVOCs). At national level, emissions are regulated by the NEC Directive on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants, amending Directive 2003/35/EC and repealing Directive 2001/81/EC, which has been transposed into Croatian legislation through the Regulation on national obligations to reduce emissions of certain air pollutants in the Republic of Croatia (Official Gazette 76/18) which sets national emission quotas for ozone precursors.

In this context, Croatia developed three regional plans for the areas of the city of Labin¹⁵, the city of Zagreb¹⁶ and the city of Pula¹⁷. The implementation of the improvement measures in terms of ozone level in ambient air started in 2014. In this report, we will focus on the plan of the city of Pula which is the most elaborate and the most documented plan. It aims at defining a framework and action plan for effective air quality management to achieve levels of air pollution below the target and long-term

⁽¹³⁾ DHMZ, 2012.

⁽¹⁴⁾ High resolution environmental Modelling and Evaluation Programme for Croatia (2006-2009).

⁽¹⁵⁾ [11. Mjere za smanjivanje razina prizemnog ozona_EN.docx](#)

⁽¹⁶⁾ [Mjere za smanjivanje razina prizemnog ozona 2023-2028_EN.docx](#)

⁽¹⁷⁾ [akcijski plan ozon grad pula svibanj 2022 zadnje_EN.docx](#)

values for ground level ozone in the city of Pula. The plan was implemented following the adoption in 2019 of the “Protocol of action in case of exceeding the information and alert threshold for ground level ozone in the city of Pula”. It was demonstrated that the ozone target value as well as the long-term objective for ground-level ozone were exceeded in 2017, 2018, 2019 and 2020 at the measuring stations in Pula (two suburban background measuring stations, which are representative of the Istria County air quality situation). Indeed, in addition to emissions from traffic, the ozone pollution in Pula is closely linked with the industrial and the port activities, the presence of the airport along with a favourable climate characterized by dry and warm summers.

Before implementing the air quality plan, air quality assessment, especially source apportionment and quantification of the impact of envisaged measures of pollutant concentrations are required. In the region of the city of Pula, this is based on (i) the measurements of pollutant concentrations from two air quality monitoring stations, (ii) the reported emissions data from stationary sources in the city of Pula in the Environmental Pollution Register, (iii) the NMVOC emissions data from the NMVOC of the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development database and (iii) the spatialization of the precursor’s emissions. This way, the main sources responsible for pollution have been listed for NO₂ and NMVOCs. An increase in NO₂ emissions is shown between 2015 and 2020. NMVOCs emissions in the city of Pula depend on the year but they were the highest in 2018. Emissions from service stations, waste, household have been analysed as well as the activity related to road transport, maritime and air transport sectors. Furthermore, the spatialization of emissions was performed in the EMEP network resolution 0.1° x 0.1° for the Republic of Croatia and its five zones and distribution in the high-resolution network 500m x 500m for four agglomerations. A portal of spatial distribution of emissions¹⁸ has been launched that allows the visualization of the distribution of the emissions of NO_x and NMVOCs in Istria County showing the highest level of emissions around the city of Pula. In this area, it was demonstrated that the main contributors for emissions of NO_x are industry (64%), road transport (15%), shipping (7%) and small fireboxes (5%). NMVOCs emissions are mainly from the solvents (67%), small fireboxes (13%) and the industry (7%). In addition, regional and background pollution has been analysed based on the EEA annual report on pollutant concentrations in the EU and the EMEP reports on Transboundary particulate matter, photooxidants, acidifying and eutrophying components.

Based on this air quality assessment, the action plan of the city of Pula was elaborated and the following measures were implemented during the period 2020 to 2024:

1. Information and education of the public:
 - o Public reporting on air quality
 - o Information of the citizens of the occurrence and cessation of exceedance of the information threshold and alert threshold for ozone
 - o Education of citizens on actions and recommendations for protection during the heat wave
 - o Raising awareness of ground-level ozone issues
 - o Education of citizens and promotion of proper use of biomass fireboxes
2. Measures aimed at reducing emissions from road transport:

⁽¹⁸⁾ <https://emep.haop.hr>

- o Greening of roadside belts
- o Greening according to General Urban Plan provisions
- 3. Measures aimed at reducing emissions from maritime transport:
 - o Installation of electrical connections for the supply of electricity to stationary ships and for cargo transshipment
 - o Determination and prescription of the permitted parameters for vessels using the port
- 4. Measures targeting energy efficiency and use of renewable energy sources
 - o Continue with the implementation of measures according to the Energy Efficiency Action Plan of the City of Pula for the period 2020-2022
 - o Encouraging cooperation on EU projects

No information on measures for ozone pollution reduction or the implementation of ozone plan has been provided in the e-reporting database.

Nevertheless, Croatia has reported exceedances that are summarized in Table 6.2 and Figure 6.1 from 2019 to 2023 with a focus on the days when maximum daily eight-hour mean exceeded 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ averaged over 3 years as the reporting metric.

Table 6.2: Number of days with maximum daily eight-hour mean above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (as defined for the target value - TV) as reported in the e-reporting database for Croatia from 2019 to 2023.

Year	Area classification	SPO	Location	Population exposed	Number of days above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
2019	suburban	SPO_992	Istra	25000	57
	rural-remote	SPO_475	Dalmacija	0	53
	urban	SPO_745	Zagreb	31553	30
2020	rural-remote	SPO_475	Dalmacija	0	42
2021	suburban	SPO_992	Istra	25000	40
	rural-remote	SPO_475	Dalmacija	0	37
2022	suburban	SPO_992	Istra	56500	41
	rural-regional	SPO_475	Dalmacija	0	26
2023	suburban	SPO_992	Istra	56500	28
	rural-regional	SPO_475	Dalmacija	0	78

Figure 6.1: Number of days with ozone maximum 8-hours mean above 120 µg/m³ depending on the year and the sampling point in Croatia.

The three-year average 8 hours daily maximum has been mostly exceeded in 2019 and 2023. The sampling point “SPO_992” (number of days represented in orange in Figure 6.1 and in Table 6.2) is in the city of Pula and shows significant number of days above 120 µg/m³ (166 days between 2019 and 2023) depending on the year. That number tends to slightly decrease over the period 2019 to 2023, which corresponds to the period of the implementation of the action plan of the city of Pula. The two other sampling points “SPO_745” and “SPO_475” are respectively classified as suburban and rural. These SPO are in other regions of Croatia (Zagreb and Dalmacija, respectively) and record days with maximum 8-hours mean above 120 µg/m³, especially “SPO_475” sampling point with 236 days from 2019 to 2023.

6.2 Air Quality Plans for ozone in France

In France, various planning tools have been developed. The national plan for reducing air pollutant emissions (PREPA)¹⁹ has been established for 2022-2025 defining the actions to be implemented to achieve the national targets for reducing emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants (SO₂, NO_x, NMVOC, NH₃, PM_{2.5}) for the years 2025 and 2030. At the inter-municipal level, measures are defined in the Atmosphere Protection Plans (PPA) and the Territorial Climate Air Energy Plans (PCAET)²⁰ in line with the PREPA actions²¹. As communicated in response to the EIONET consultation, PPA have been established with a few measures focusing on ozone reduction. In the Grand Est region, the PPA of Strasbourg defines only one action related to the reduction of NMVOCs. In the Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur (PACA) region, the PPA of Bouches-du-Rhône and the PPA of Var allow the implementation of

⁽¹⁹⁾ <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/publications/PREPA%20JORF.pdf>

⁽²⁰⁾ <https://outil2amenagement.cerema.fr/outils/plan-protection-atmosphere-ppa>

⁽²¹⁾ <https://outil2amenagement.cerema.fr/outils/plan-climat-air-energie-territorial-pcaet>

measures for controlling NMVOC emissions (especially from the industrial sector) and the improvement of knowledges on ozone formation and climate change impacts on ozone levels in ambient air. In addition, emergency measures have been implemented in the Alpes-Martimes PPA, their effects are still hard to quantify.

The implementation of these actions in the PPA is reflected in the information in air quality plans reported by France in the e-reporting database. Actions for ozone pollution reduction are reported since 2012 in PPA from most regions of France (for instance, Rhône Alpes, Provence-Alpes-Côte d’Azur, Occitanie, Martinique, Haute Normandie, Languedoc Roussillon, Champagne Ardenne Reims, Strasbourg, and Ile de France regions).

Moreover, a regional action plan for ozone²² is carried out since 2021 in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (AURA) region according to the EIONET consultation response. In this region, NO_x of anthropogenic origin come mainly from the road transport sector (63%), ahead of industry (15%) and the residential sector (8%). NO_x concentrations have been decreasing sharply (-4% per year) over the past ten years. Regarding NMVOCs, 70% are of biogenic origin, with a strong influence from plant species and sunlight. NMVOC emissions of anthropogenic origin come mainly from the residential sector (63%), ahead of industry (24%). Concentrations have been decreasing (-1.5% per year) over the past ten years. Finally, agricultural activities, particularly livestock farming, generate the highest methane emissions (63%), ahead of the waste sector (26%), which includes household waste landfills. Methane emissions are also declining in the region (-1.2% per year), but concentrations are increasing.

The entire AURA region is affected by ozone pollution with a well identified transport of ozone from neighbouring regions; therefore, the development of the regional ozone plan is essential. It enabled the elaboration of action sheets addressing various objectives and targets. The preparatory work highlighted the need to deepen the knowledge base to better target action levers. It also emerged that informing and communicating, in an educational manner, to all target groups in the region is important. Finally, the action plan offers a series of operational levels to reduce ozone precursor emissions.

First, a transversal action sheet has been produced that aims at seeking funding and partnerships to implement the ozone plan. Then, action sheets targeting the main sectors of ozone precursor emissions were produced as presented in Table 6.3.

Table 6.3: List of action sheets produced in the regional plan for ozone of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region.

Sector	Titled	Action sheet	Diffusion tool
Agriculture	A.1	Mobilize tools and devices that promote animal feed that reduces ozone precursor emissions.	PPA, PCAET
	A.2	Integrate ozone pollution issues into the low-carbon label animal feed sheet.	The low carbon label sheet
	A.3	Conduct a complementary study to the ADEME guide on good agricultural practices to improve air quality.	PPA, PCAET, Chamber of Agriculture Network
	A.4	Raise awareness of the impact of livestock effluent on ozone precursor emissions.	PPA, PCAET, Chamber of Agriculture Network

⁽²²⁾ [1_plan_regional_ozone_v-nov2024_EN.docx](#)

Forest	F.1	Integrate ozone pollution issues into the reforestation sheet low carbon label.	Low Carbon Label Sheet “afforestation” and “reforestation”
	F.2	Present to the Regional Forestry and Timber Commission the issues of ozone pollution in the forestry sector.	PPA, PCAET
	F.3	Creation of a guide on trees that absorb ozone / trees that emit less VOCs.	PPA, PCAET
	F.4	Identify operational levers for taking ozone into account in forest renewal/development.	PPA, PCAET
Transports	T.1	Reduce traffic speeds.	PPA, PCAET
	T.2	Raise awareness among employers about the use of the sustainable mobility package and teleworking in the context of company negotiations.	PPA, PCAET, Low-carbon label information sheet, CCI Mobility Advisors, Local Economic Development Services, Pollution Episode Management System
	T.3	Extend Crit’Air stickers to the entire vehicle fleet in the region	PPA, PCAET, Pollution Episode Management System, Town hall and prefecture services (websites and notices in these locations)
	T.4	Promote and generalize the principle of incentive pricing in the event of pollution peaks to make public transport more attractive.	PPA, PCAET, Pollution Episode Management System
	T.5	Encourage administrative structure to implement a voluntary commitment approach to sustainable urban logistics.	PPA, PCAET
	T.6	Fight against Ad-Blue fraud.	PPA, PCAET
Industrial and craft activities	AIA.1	Improving knowledge of NMVOCs and their impact on ozone production to better target actions towards the VOCs that have the greatest impact.	PPA, PCAET
	AIA.2	Reducing NMVOC emissions in companies subject to Directive 2010/75/EU on industrial emissions (IED).	PPA, PCAET
	AIA.3	Promote the adoption of BAT for reducing NMVOCs in companies not subject to Directive 2010/75/EU on industrial emissions (IED).	PPA, PCAET
	AIA.4	Support the deployment of warm mix asphalt, particularly through public procurement.	PPA, PCAET
	AIA.5	Anticipate communication during conditions favourable to ozone production.	Pollution and heatwave alert orders
	AIA.6	Reducing diffuse methane emissions in non-hazardous waste storage facilities.	PPA
Residential and buildings	RB.1	Improve knowledge of impacts, encourage the use of lower-emission materials in public procurement and support the development of professional skills.	PPA, PCAET
	RB.2	Develop a communication brochure on VOC emissions from biomass combustion.	PPA, PCAET
	RB.3	Deploy communication aimed at the public on the right actions to take when carrying out domestic work.	PPA, PCAET

These actions are implemented at the local level (mainly in several PPA and PCAET) particularly through local projects led by communities, which can act as powerful relays for the regional plan.

More generally, France has reported days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above 120 µg/m³ (as defined for the target value exceedances) over the last years that are summarized in Table 6.4 and Figure 6.2.

Table 6.4: Number of days with maximum daily eight-hour mean above 120 µg/m³ (as defined for the target value - TV) as reported in the e-reporting database for France from 2019 to 2023.

Year	Area classification	Number of SPOs	Location	Number of days above 120 µg/m ³
2019	suburban	1	ZAG PARIS	27
	rural-regional	1	ZR CENTRE-VAL DE LOIRE	29
	suburban	1	ZAR BELFORT-MONTBELIARD	31
	suburban urban	2	ZAR BESANCON	44
	suburban urban	3	ZR BOURGOGNE-FRANCHE-COMTE	32
	suburban	1	ZAG BLDV	26
	urban suburban	2	ZAG STRASBOURG	35
	suburban	1	ZAG METZ	28
	suburban	1	ZAG NANCY	26
	rural-regional suburban urban rural-nearcity	10	ZR GRAND-EST	35
	suburban	2	ZAG MONTPELLIER	34
	urban	1	ZAR NIMES	28
	suburban rural-nearcity	2	ZR OCCITANIE	55
	suburban urban	6	ZAG LYON	35
	suburban urban	5	ZAG GRENOBLE	41
	suburban	1	ZAG SAINT-ETIENNE	30
	suburban	1	ZAG CLERMONT-FERRAND	27
	urban	5	ZAR PAYS-DE-SAVOIE	40
	urban suburban	5	ZAR VALLEE-DU-RHONE	46
	urban	1	ZAR VALLEE-DE-LA-TARANTAISE	40
	rural-nearcity suburban urban rural-remote	5	ZR AUVERGNE-RHONE-ALPES	47
	suburban urban	9	ZAG MARSEILLE-AIX	51
	suburban	2	ZAG NICE	44
	urban	2	ZAG TOULON	39
	urban suburban	2	ZAG AVIGNON	61
	suburban	1	ZAR FREJUS-DRAGUIGNAN	51
rural-nearcity suburban rural-remote urban rural-regional	8	ZR PROVENCE-ALPES-COTE D'AZUR	77	
rural-regional	1	ZR CORSE	32	
2020	suburban	2	ZAG PARIS	31
	rural-regional suburban	3	ZR ILE-DE-FRANCE	29
	rural-regional	1	ZR CENTRE-VAL DE LOIRE	26
	suburban	1	ZAR BELFORT-MONTBELIARD	34
	suburban	2	ZAR DIJON	30
	suburban urban	2	ZAR BESANCON	47

	suburban urban	3	ZR BOURGOGNE-FRANCHE-COMTE	34
	urban suburban	3	ZAG BLDV	34
	suburban	1	ZAR ARRAS	27
	rural-nearcity	1	ZR HAUTS-DE-FRANCE	26
	urban suburban	2	ZAG STRASBOURG	37
	suburban	1	ZAG METZ	27
	suburban	1	ZAG NANCY	26
	suburban urban	2	ZAR REIMS	28
	rural-remote rural-regional suburban urban	12	ZR GRAND-EST	41
	suburban	2	ZAG MONTPELLIER	36
	urban	1	ZAR NIMES	29
	rural-nearcity	1	ZR OCCITANIE	58
	suburban urban	5	ZAG LYON	36
	suburban urban	3	ZAG GRENOBLE	38
	urban suburban	2	ZAG SAINT-ETIENNE	29
	urban	5	ZAR PAYS-DE-SAVOIE	32
	urban suburban	4	ZAR VALLEE-DU-RHONE	50
	urban	1	ZAR VALLEE-DE-LA-TARANTAISE	29
	urban	1	ZAR MOULINS	29
	rural-regional rural-nearcity suburban urban rural-remote	7	ZR AUVERGNE-RHONE-ALPES	44
	suburban urban	9	ZAG MARSEILLE-AIX	57
	suburban	2	ZAG NICE	43
	urban	2	ZAG TOULON	37
	urban suburban	2	ZAG AVIGNON	57
	suburban	1	ZAR FREJUS-DRAGUIGNAN	41
	rural-nearcity suburban rural-remote urban rural-regional	7	ZR PROVENCE-ALPES-COTE D'AZUR	74
2021	suburban	1	ZAR BESANCON	34
	suburban	1	ZAR REIMS	26
	rural-regional suburban urban	4	ZR GRAND-EST	30
	suburban	1	ZAG MONTPELLIER	29
	rural-nearcity	1	ZR OCCITANIE	40
	suburban	1	ZAG LYON	29
	suburban	2	ZAR VALLEE-DU-RHONE	36
	rural-nearcity suburban	2	ZR AUVERGNE-RHONE-ALPES	34
	suburban urban	4	ZAG MARSEILLE-AIX	44
	suburban	2	ZAG NICE	29
	urban suburban	2	ZAG AVIGNON	43
	suburban	1	ZAR FREJUS-DRAGUIGNAN	28
rural-nearcity suburban rural-remote urban rural-regional	7	ZR PROVENCE-ALPES-COTE D'AZUR	58	
2022	suburban	1	ZAR BESANCON	35
	suburban	1	ZAG STRASBOURG	27
	urban suburban rural-regional	4	ZR GRAND-EST	31
	rural-nearcity	1	ZR OCCITANIE	34
	suburban	2	ZAG LYON	31
	suburban	2	ZAR VALLEE-DU-RHONE	37
	suburban rural-nearcity	3	ZR AUVERGNE-RHONE-ALPES	32

	urban suburban	6	ZAG MARSEILLE-AIX	42
	suburban	2	ZAG NICE	31
	urban	1	ZAG TOULON	31
	suburban	1	ZAG AVIGNON	43
	urban suburban rural-regional rural-nearcity	7	ZRE PROVENCE-ALPES-COTE-D-AZUR	57
2023	suburban	1	ZAR BESANCON	37
	urban suburban	2	ZAG STRASBOURG	32
	suburban	1	ZAG METZ	29
	urban suburban rural-regional	4	ZR GRAND-EST	30
	rural-nearcity	1	ZR OCCITANIE	30
	suburban	2	ZAG LYON	28
	suburban	2	ZAR VALLEE-DU-RHONE	32
	suburban rural-nearcity	2	ZR AUVERGNE-RHONE-ALPES	31
	urban suburban	7	ZAG MARSEILLE-AIX	41
	urban suburban	3	ZAG NICE	36
	urban	1	ZAG TOULON	26
	suburban	1	ZAG AVIGNON	42
	urban suburban rural-regional rural-nearcity	7	ZRE PROVENCE-ALPES-COTE-D-AZUR	50

Figure 6.2: Number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (as defined for the target value) depending on the year and the assessment zone in France.

In Figure 6.2, the number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is presented for each administrative monitoring zone. Among those zones, ZAG is defined as high-risk zone which includes a built-up area with a population of over 250,000, as defined by the decree provided for in article L. 222-4 of the Environment Code, or with a population density per square kilometre more than a threshold set by the French Ministry of the Environment. Then, ZAR is defined as high-risk zone, outside built-up area, which does not meet the criteria for a ZAG and in which the air quality standards mentioned in article R. 221-1 of the Environment Code are not met or are at risk of not being met. Finally, ZR covers the rest of the region.

According to the exceedances of the target value reported in the AQ e-reporting database, the maximum number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (316) between 2019 and 2023 is reported in ZR Provence-Alpes-Cote d'Azur in the Southeast of France. ZAG Avignon, ZAG Marseille-Aix and ZAG Nice, three zones in the same geographical and administrative region, reported 246, 235 and 183 days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively, during this period. In the south of France, ZAG Occitanie reported many days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (217). The AURA region is also one of the regions most affected by ozone pollution, with 201 days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in ZAR Vallee-du-Rhone and 188 in ZR Auvergne-Rhone-Alpes.

6.3 Air Quality Plans for ozone in Spain

In Spain, national actions for reduction of ambient air pollutants are carried out under the PNIEC (the National Integrated Energy-Climate Plan, 2021 - 2030)²³ and the PNCCA (the First National Program to combat Air Pollution, 2023 - 2030)²⁴. However, these measures are not focused on ozone while this is a major concern. Indeed, Spain is in the Mediterranean basin where ozone exceedances of the long-term objective and the target value occurred frequently, especially because of the prevailing weather conditions in warm seasons of the year, the topography and vegetation together with high solar incidence. Several regions in Spain are strongly affected by ozone pollution such as the Madrid basin, the north of Barcelona, the Guadalquivir basin, the Puertollano basin, the interior of the Valencian Community, the North of Tarragona and the regions adjoining the first two areas and the north of Portugal.

In this context, the Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge commissioned several research institutes to develop the scientific bases to elaborate the future National Ozone Plan by the end of 2024. The resulting scientific study provides an analysis of the ozone trends from 2008 to 2023 to identify the episodes of ozone pollution and the conditions of their occurrences. That analysis shows no significant national changes, but notable variations in hotspots areas. Trends varied across regions, with continued high levels in the Madrid basin and rising O_3 at lower concentration levels in urban areas. A comprehensive study of ozone precursors (NO_x and NMVOCs) was carried out based on ground-based measurements from the regulatory monitoring

⁽²³⁾ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/prensa/pniec.html>

⁽²⁴⁾ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/en/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/temas/emisiones-a-la-atmosfera/emisiones-pncca-.html>

network, satellite data, NMVOCs measurements campaigns in specific regions and the elaboration of accurate emission inventories. From these results, a detailed identification of the NMVOCs with the greatest potential contribution to ozone formation was done and a consensus list of NMVOCs prioritization to reduce emissions and the associated key sectors was generated. In addition, four regions in the country associated with specific ozone patterns have been defined based on a characterization of ozone pollution episodes. In this way, appropriate measures could be proposed in each region. Finally, the impact on ozone pollution of implementing measures already provided by other Spanish plans and those recommended in the scientific study was assessed based on air quality modelling studies. These numerical simulations showed that although scenarios yield relevant reductions, the EU 2008 long-term target for O₃ remains unmet. The study underscores the importance of combining national and international strategies, refining NMVOC inventories, and focusing on high-impact sectors such as traffic and shipping to effectively mitigate O₃ pollution.

The recommended actions based on this scientific study are listed in the following:

1. Adopt the regionalization proposed in the scientific study and develop specific policies depending on the phenomenology of the episodes in each area.
2. Prioritize the implementation of precursor emission reduction measures especially in ozone hotspots and in other areas to reduce ozone background levels.
3. Implement precursor emission reduction measures (NO_x and VOCs) in summertime.
4. Prioritize measures for the reduction of VOCs with high O₃ training capacity.
5. Require the implementation of the best available technologies to ensure minimum emissions of VOCs in biomass combustion plants.
6. Include specifically in the environmental impact assessment (EIA) studies of biomass combustion plants a binding study of their potential impact on O₃ levels.
7. Promote and consolidate electric mobility models in high road traffic areas.
8. Promote internationally coordinated measures to address precursor emission reduction plans to reduce O₃ background levels.
9. Encourage non-combustion based renewable energy.
10. Propose the designation of the Mediterranean Sea as an emission control area for NO_x and SO_x.
11. Ensure compliance with the planned reductions in road traffic in the framework of the PNIEC and PNCCA together with the final implementation of the ZBE (low emission zone in Barcelona).
12. Implement precursor reduction measures in port areas.
13. Make mandatory the application of VOC absorbers in all vehicle fuel supply facilities.
14. Strengthen inspections at gas stations to ensure compliance with current regulations.

The National Ozone Plan has now been drafted and was submitted to public consultation from 10 December 2025 to 2 February 2026. The substantial work carried out in the preparatory scientific study

provides a solid basis and reinforces confidence in the effectiveness of the recommended measures. The draft plan is available in MITECO (2026), *Proyecto para el Plan Nacional de Ozono*²⁵.

Specific measures to reduce ozone pollution that are implemented in air quality plans (such as the Andalusian Air Quality Strategy, the National Air Quality and Atmospheric Protection Plan 2017-2019: Plan AIRE 2, and the Air Quality Improvement Plan for the Region of Murcia 2016-2018) have been reported in the e-reporting database between 2013 and 2017. However, no information on ozone plans or measures to reduce ozone pollution have been reported in the recent year (from 2018 to 2023).

Reported exceedances of ozone target values during the last years in the e-reporting database reflects the situation in Spain. A sample of these exceedances is presented in Table 6.5 with a focus on the days when maximum daily eight-hour mean exceeded 120 µg/m³ averaged over 3 years as the reporting metric.

Table 6.5: Number of days with maximum daily eight-hour mean above 120 µg/m³ (as defined for the target value - TV) as reported in the e-reporting database for Spain from 2019 to 2023.

Year	Area classification	Number of SPOs	Location	Number of days above 120 µg/m ³
2019	urban suburban rural	1	CORDOBA	57
	urban suburban rural	2	ZONA INDUSTRIAL DE CARBONERAS	35
	urban suburban rural	1	GRANADA Y AREA METROPOLITANA	42
	urban suburban rural	1	MALAGA Y COSTA DEL SOL	29
	urban suburban rural	1	NUEVA ZONA INDUSTRIAL DE HUELVA	29
	urban suburban rural	2	NUEVA ZONA DE NUCLEOS DE 50.000 A 250.000 HABITANTES	61
	urban suburban rural	6	NUEVAS ZONAS RURALES	64
	urban suburban rural	1	NUEVA ZONA SEVILLA Y AREA METROPOLITANA	32
	urban suburban rural	1	NUEVA ZONA INDUSTRIAL DE PUENTE NUEVO	46
	urban suburban rural	1	VALLE DEL EBRO	26
	urban suburban rural	1	MENORCA-MAO-ES CASTELL	31
	urban suburban rural	1	RESTO MALLORCA	35
	urban suburban rural	3	RESTO DE CASTILLA-LA MANCHA 2	34
	urban suburban rural	1	CORREDOR DEL HENARES	29
	urban suburban rural	2	MONTAÑA SUR DE CYL	38
	urban suburban rural	1	AREA DE BARCELONA	33
	urban suburban rural	2	PLANA DE VIC	49
	urban suburban rural	1	COMARQUES DE GIRONA	30
	urban suburban rural	1	EMPORDA	29
	urban suburban rural	2	PREPIRINEU	39
urban suburban rural	2	CERVOL-ELS PORTS. AREA INTERIOR	58	

⁽²⁵⁾ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/content/dam/miteco/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/sgalsi/atm%20c3%b3sfera-y-calidad-del-aire/participaci%20n-p%20c3%bablica-/calidad-del-aire/Proyecto%20de%20un%20Plan%20Nacional%20de%20Ozono.pdf>

	urban suburban rural	1	TURIA. AREA INTERIOR	32
	urban suburban rural	1	JUCAR-CABRIEL. AREA INTERIOR	56
	urban suburban rural	1	BETICA-SERPIS. AREA INTERIOR	31
	urban suburban rural	1	CACERES	40
	urban suburban rural	1	NUCLEOS DE POBLACION DE MAS DE 20.000 HABITANTES	26
	urban suburban rural	6	MADRID	51
	urban suburban rural	7	CORREDOR DEL HENARES	56
	urban suburban rural	6	URBANA SUR	46
	urban suburban rural	3	URBANA NOROESTE	35
	urban suburban rural	3	SIERRA NORTE	66
	urban suburban rural	2	CUENCA DEL TAJUÑA	67
	urban suburban rural	1	CIUDAD DE MURCIA	29
	urban suburban rural	1	CUENCAS INTERIORES	26
2020	urban suburban rural	1	CORDOBA	38
	urban suburban rural	1	ZONA INDUSTRIAL DE CARBONERAS	27
	urban suburban rural	1	GRANADA Y AREA METROPOLITANA	28
	urban suburban rural	1	MALAGA Y COSTA DEL SOL	29
	urban suburban rural	1	NUEVA ZONA INDUSTRIAL DE HUELVA	27
	urban suburban rural	2	NUEVA ZONA DE NUCLEOS DE 50.000 A 250.000 HABITANTES	45
	urban suburban rural	6	NUEVAS ZONAS RURALES	50
	urban suburban rural	1	NUEVA ZONA INDUSTRIAL DE PUENTE NUEVO	35
	urban suburban rural	1	ZARAGOZA	26
	urban suburban rural	1	SIERRA DE TRAMUNTANA	31
	urban suburban rural	1	AGLOMERACIÓN DE GUADALAJARA	29
	urban suburban rural	1	GUADALAJARA	29
	urban suburban rural	3	NORTE DE TOLEDO	29
	urban suburban rural	2	MONTAÑA SUR DE CYL	35
	urban suburban rural	1	VALLE DEL TIÉTAR Y ALBERCHE	26
	urban suburban rural	2	PLANA DE VIC	39
	urban suburban rural	1	COMARQUES DE GIRONA	29
	urban suburban rural	1	PREPIRINEU	52
	urban suburban rural	3	CERVOL-ELS PORTS. AREA INTERIOR	56
	urban suburban rural	1	MIJARES-PEÑAGOLOSA. AREA INTERIOR	34
	urban suburban rural	1	TURIA. AREA COSTERA	32
	urban suburban rural	1	TURIA. AREA INTERIOR	37
	urban suburban rural	1	JUCAR-CABRIEL. AREA INTERIOR	39
	urban suburban rural	1	BETICA-SERPIS. AREA INTERIOR	31
	urban suburban rural	1	CACERES	37
	urban suburban rural	2	EXTREMADURA RURAL	32
	urban suburban rural	6	MADRID	48
	urban suburban rural	6	CORREDOR DEL HENARES	51
	urban suburban rural	5	URBANA SUR	39
	urban suburban rural	2	URBANA NOROESTE	30
	urban suburban rural	3	SIERRA NORTE	56
	urban suburban rural	1	CUENCA DEL ALBERCHE	26
urban suburban rural	1	CUENCA DEL TAJUÑA	50	
urban suburban rural	1	CUENCAS INTERIORES	27	
2021	urban suburban rural	1	CORDOBA	29

	urban suburban rural	2	NUEVA ZONA DE NUCLEOS DE 50.000 A 250.000 HABITANTES	37
	urban suburban rural	3	NUEVAS ZONAS RURALES	30
	urban suburban rural	1	NUEVA ZONA INDUSTRIAL DE PUENTE NUEVO	42
	urban suburban rural	1	AGLOMERACIÓN DE GUADALAJARA	26
	urban suburban rural	1	GUADALAJARA	26
	urban suburban rural	1	NORTE DE TOLEDO	29
	urban suburban rural	1	MONTAÑA SUR DE CYL	28
	urban suburban rural	1	PLANA DE VIC	27
	urban suburban rural	1	PREPIRINEU	51
	urban suburban rural	1	CERVOL-ELS PORTS. AREA INTERIOR	62
	urban suburban rural	1	MIJARES-PEÑAGOLOSA. AREA INTERIOR	27
	urban suburban rural	1	JUCAR-CABRIEL. AREA INTERIOR	28
	urban suburban rural	1	CACERES	27
	urban suburban rural	4	MADRID	40
	urban suburban rural	7	CORREDOR DEL HENARES	45
	urban suburban rural	3	SIERRA NORTE	51
	urban suburban rural	1	CUENCA DEL ALBERCHE	36
	urban suburban rural	1	CUENCA DEL TAJUÑA	38
2022	urban suburban rural	2	NUEVA ZONA DE NUCLEOS DE 50.000 A 250.000 HABITANTES	27
	urban suburban rural	1	RESTO MALLORCA	29
	urban suburban rural	2	PLANA DE VIC	31
	urban suburban rural	1	COMARQUES DE GIRONA	33
	urban suburban rural	1	PREPIRINEU	39
	urban suburban rural	2	MADRID	34
	urban suburban rural	6	CORREDOR DEL HENARES	44
	urban suburban rural	3	SIERRA NORTE	44
	urban suburban rural	1	CUENCA DEL ALBERCHE	46
	urban suburban rural	1	CUENCA DEL TAJUÑA	31
2023	urban suburban rural	1	NUEVA ZONA DE NUCLEOS DE 50.000 A 250.000 HABITANTES	28
	urban suburban rural	1	RESTO MALLORCA	47
	urban suburban rural	1	AGLOMERACIÓN DE GUADALAJARA	27
	urban suburban rural	1	GUADALAJARA	27
	urban suburban rural	2	PLANA DE VIC	32
	urban suburban rural	1	COMARQUES DE GIRONA	29
	urban suburban rural	1	PREPIRINEU	40
	urban suburban rural	1	JUCAR-CABRIEL. AREA INTERIOR	26
	urban suburban rural	1	EXTREMADURA RURAL	37
	urban suburban rural	5	MADRID	39
	urban suburban rural	7	CORREDOR DEL HENARES	51
	urban suburban rural	1	URBANA NOROESTE	30
	urban suburban rural	3	SIERRA NORTE	52
	urban suburban rural	1	CUENCA DEL ALBERCHE	51
urban suburban rural	2	CUENCA DEL TAJUÑA	40	

Figure 6.3: Number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above 120 µg/m³ (as defined for the target value – TV) depending on the year and the assessment zones in Spain.

According to the exceedances of the target values reported in the AQ e-reporting database (Figure 6.3), the area with the greatest number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above 120 µg/m³ (269) from 2019 to 2023 is Sierra Norte in the province of Seville. Then, Corredor del Henares, Cuenca del Tajuña, Madrid and Cuenca del Alberche areas that are in the same geographical region in Spain (Madrid and surroundings) reported high number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above 120 µg/m³, 276, 226, 212 and 159, respectively, during this period. The Prepirineus area, which are the foothills of the Pyrenees, reported 221 number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above 120 µg/m³ during this period. In addition, areas classified as new zone of 50,000 to 250,000 inhabitants and new rural areas are associated with large number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above 120 µg/m³ (198 and 144, respectively from 2019 to 2023).

The number of days with ozone maximum 8-hour mean above 120 µg/m³ over the entire country has decreased by 40% from 2019 to 2023. However, the adoption of the revised AAQD, involving stringent thresholds for number of days of exceedances, requires efficient actions to continue the decline.

6.4 Section highlights

Under the revised AAQD, ozone-specific **air quality plans become mandatory** when target values are exceeded. These plans must include **precursor reduction measures** and be supported by **appropriate VOC monitoring** strategies tailored to local emissions sources and ozone-forming species. At international level, the **CLRTAP Gothenburg Protocol** and the **NEC Directive** set national emissions ceilings for ozone precursors (NO_x and NMVOCs) to guide these efforts.

An Eionet consultation gathered **information from 12 countries on existing ozone plans**, measures, and scientific studies. Most countries have conducted research on ozone formation mechanisms, source apportionment, and climate change impacts. Three countries – **Croatia, France and Spain** – have developed or implemented dedicated **air quality measures or plans for ozone**.

Croatia adopted a **national action plan and regional plans for cities** including Pula, where ozone exceedances are linked to traffic, port activities and favorable meteorological conditions. Measures focus on public information, greening transport corridors, shore power ships and energy efficiency. Monitoring data suggests a **slight decrease in exceedance days over 2019-2023**, coinciding with plan implementation.

France combines **national (PREPA) and local instruments (PPA and PCAET)**, with **ozone related actions** reported since 2012. **The Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region developed a comprehensive ozone plan in 2021** with sector-specific action sheets covering agriculture, forestry, transport, industry, and residential sources. Southern regions (Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, Occitanie) remain the most affected, recording the highest number of exceedance days.

Spain faces significant ozone pollution, particularly in the Madrid basin, Catalonia, and the Mediterranean coast. **A comprehensive scientific study was completed in 2024 to support future national ozone plan**. It identified regional ozone patterns, **prioritized high-impact NMVOCs**, and recommended measures targeting traffic, shipping, biomass combustion and port areas. The study emphasizes the **need for coordinated national and international strategies**, as modelling shows that current scenarios still fail to meet the EU long-term objective.

Reported exceedances across these three countries confirm that **ozone pollution remains a persistent challenge in Europe, particularly in southern regions**. While few dedicated ozone plans exist to date, this overview highlights growing national efforts to improve understanding of ozone formation processes and develop effective mitigation strategies. Ongoing scientific work will provide the foundation for future plans, which will necessarily focus on controlling precursor emissions. **An in-depth knowledge of precursors (NO_x, NMVOCs and CH₄) sources and their evolution, combined with robust precursor monitoring as outlined in Section 5, is therefore essential**. These constitute the main policy levers available to Member States for reducing ozone concentrations through targeted measures in their air quality plans.

7 CH₄, NMVOC and NO_x emissions

In this section the precursor gases for ground-level ozone methane, non-methane volatile organic compounds and nitrogen oxides are analysed, looking at historic and projected emission trends at the European level and trying to identify underlying drivers.

As detailed in section 5, VOCs occur in many different chemical gaseous forms, such as hydrocarbons, alcohols, aldehydes, and organic acids. They are released in biological processes but are also a result

of anthropogenic activities. The formation of ground-level ozone is relying on the availability of precursor gases (such as VOCs and NO_x) and sunlight. Under sunlight, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) can undergo photolysis breaking down into nitrogen oxide (NO) and a free oxygen atom which then reacts to atmospheric oxygen to form O₃. However, the newly formed ozone molecule can quickly react with NO, regenerating NO₂ and O₂. This cycle results in no net ozone accumulation. When VOCs are present in polluted atmosphere, NO can be transformed during their oxidation, resulting in ozone build-up. Conversely, when NO levels are very high (under certain conditions such as low VOC concentrations or limited sunlight, especially near emissions sources, in winter or at night), ozone can be depleted. This process is known as ozone titration (Colette, 2024).

Therefore, the ongoing surveillance not only of atmospheric concentrations but also of emission levels of VOCs are of importance, but their interpretation in terms of ozone formation is complex and without linear correlation. Firstly because, the monitoring of emission levels for these substances is only done for anthropogenic sources (biogenic VOCs are not covered²⁶), secondly because ozone episodes are rather regional in scale and spatially restricted events and thirdly because the specific effect of individual VOCs. Biogenic VOC sources are natural emissions, primarily from plants, which are released into the atmosphere by biological processes influenced by light, temperature and vegetation types. Indeed, VOCs come from various sources and undergo different chemical reaction pathways, causing their oxidation rates to vary by several orders of magnitude. This leads to significant differences in their atmospheric lifetimes and their efficiency in producing ozone. For the longer lived NMVOCs (e.g. ethane has a global lifetime of about 3 months, with a minimum in summer of 2 months and a maximum in winter of 10 months²⁷), and for CH₄ (which has a lifetime of about 12 years in the atmosphere), a much broader geographical scale should be considered for action.

Within the EU, Member States are required to annually report on their national CH₄ emissions, as part of their GHG emission inventories under the Energy Governance Regulation²⁸, and national NMVOCs and NO_x emissions, as part of their reporting under the NEC Directive²⁹. As NMVOCs and NO_x are also part of the four indirect Greenhouse Gases (GHGs), contributing to increased tropospheric ozone concentrations and hereby to increased radiative forcing, they are also reported in the GHG inventories.

There are also international reporting obligations, which are the reporting of GHGs to the UNFCCC (United Framework Convention on Climate Change) and reporting of air pollutants under the CLRTAP³⁰. This convention has been extended by eight protocols, one of them Gothenburg Protocol Abate Acidification, Eutrophication and Ground-level Ozone. As mentioned in section 5, this protocol establishes national emission ceilings for SO₂, NO_x, NMVOCs, and NH₃ for the year 2020 and beyond. The scientific community now discusses an amendment of the Gothenburg Protocol also including CH₄.

In the following sections, the trends and underlying drivers for CH₄, NO_x and NMVOCs emissions are presented and discussed, covering a timeframe from 1990 to 2022. It shall be noted that data is only available on total NMVOC emissions, and distinction to specific substances cannot be made.

⁽²⁶⁾ Biogenic VOC sources are natural emissions, primarily from plants, which are released into the atmosphere by biological processes. In contrast, anthropogenic VOC sources are man-made, originating from human activities like vehicle exhaust, industrial processes, fuel combustion, and the use of solvents and paints.

⁽²⁷⁾ Earth System Science Data, 2022: Northern hemispheric atmospheric ethane trends in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (2006–2016) with reference to methane and propane; <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-14-4351-2022>

⁽²⁸⁾ Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action

⁽²⁹⁾ Directive (EU) 2016/2284 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2016 on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants

⁽³⁰⁾ <https://unece.org/environmental-policy/air/convention-and-its-achievements>

7.1 Methane (CH₄)

Methane is primarily known as a very potent greenhouse gas, having a global warming potential of 28 considering a timeframe of 100 years, i.e. its radiative force is 28 times higher than for carbon dioxide (CO₂). The lifetime of CH₄ in the atmosphere is about 12 years, which is in comparison to other greenhouse gases, rather short. But in comparison with other air pollutants (hours for NO_x, days or weeks for O₃ and aerosols), this is long (Myhre et al, 2013). The role of CH₄ in ground-level ozone formation is becoming increasingly acknowledged (JRC, 2024, Colette, 2024 and EEA Briefing No 01/2025), leading to the recommendation of the Working Group on Strategies and Review of the UNECE Air Convention to include CH₄ in the next revision of the Gothenburg protocol (UNECE, 2025). Currently, there is no obligation in the EU to reach a specific CH₄ emission target. But given its relevance as a GHG, it is part of the GHG emission reduction targets, which includes the aggregate of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and F-gases (NF₃, PFC, SF₆, HFCs).

During the Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC in 2021, the EU and the US launched the Global Methane Pledge. As CH₄ is a short-lived climate pollutant, reduction results in near-term benefits to limit global warming, bringing also along co-benefits on public health and agricultural productivity. Participants joining the Pledge agree to take voluntary actions to contribute to a collective effort to reduce global methane emissions at least 30 percent from 2020 levels by 2030. This is a global, not a national reduction target³¹.

7.1.1 Trends by Member States

Methane emissions decreased in the EU27 from 23,787 kt to 14,597 kt, which is a reduction of 38.6 % between 1990 and 2022. The total EU emission trend is largely determined by Germany, France, Italy and Poland (see Figure 7.1), The observed decrease at EU level is dominated by Germany, Poland and Romania – the countries with the largest absolute reductions between 1990 and 2022. A few countries also report emission increases during that time, which is Cyprus, Spain, Ireland and Malta (Table 7.1).

Figure 7.1: Trend of CH₄ emissions across EU Member States from 1990-2022.

Note: the figure displays the 10 biggest contributors to CH₄ emissions in the EU. 'Other' sums up all other remaining countries; data source: EEA, 2024f.

⁽³¹⁾ <https://www.globalmethanepledge.org/#pledges>

Table 7.1: Information on trend and share of CH₄ emissions of EU Member States.

	Share in 1990	Share in 2005	Share in 2022	Absolute Change 1990-2022 [kt CH ₄]	Relative Change 1990-2022	Trend 1990-2022
AT	1.7%	1.7%	1.6%	- 172.23	-42.5%	
BE	1.9%	1.9%	1.9%	- 187.25	-40.6%	
BG	2.2%	1.5%	1.6%	- 287.54	-55.0%	
CY	0.1%	0.2%	0.3%	10.76	38.8%	
CZ	4.0%	3.2%	3.2%	- 491.16	-51.3%	
DE	21.0%	15.6%	12.7%	- 3 135.40	-62.8%	
DK	1.4%	1.9%	2.1%	- 26.46	-7.8%	
ES	6.2%	8.8%	10.4%	48.35	3.3%	
EE	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	- 36.69	-46.2%	
FI	1.5%	1.5%	1.3%	- 175.53	-47.6%	
FR	11.8%	14.5%	14.4%	- 696.82	-24.8%	
GR	1.9%	2.5%	2.9%	- 25.98	-5.8%	
HR	0.8%	0.8%	0.9%	- 42.00	-23.5%	
HU	2.1%	2.2%	2.2%	- 181.04	-36.5%	
IE	3.1%	4.0%	5.3%	45.60	6.3%	
IT	8.4%	10.7%	11.3%	- 343.52	-17.3%	
LT	1.2%	0.9%	0.8%	- 166.08	-59.2%	
LU	0.1%	0.1%	0.2%	- 1.20	-4.9%	
LV	0.7%	0.5%	0.7%	- 64.34	-39.3%	
MT	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	3.13	62.8%	
NL	5.5%	4.4%	4.5%	- 637.46	-49.1%	
PL	10.6%	10.2%	9.9%	- 1 080.44	-42.7%	
PT	1.6%	2.4%	2.6%	- 12.46	-3.2%	
RO	8.9%	7.2%	6.2%	- 1 197.30	-56.8%	
SK	1.3%	1.0%	0.9%	- 163.17	-54.9%	
SI	0.4%	0.5%	0.5%	- 33.22	-32.7%	
SE	1.3%	1.4%	1.2%	- 140.56	-44.4%	
EU-27	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	- 9 190.00	-38.6%	

Source of data: CRT Sept 2024 submissions³², consistent with EU NID 2025, total incl. LULUCF; EEA, 2024c.

In the following table the emission trends of countries with a specifically high decrease or an increase and the underlying reasons are described in more detail:

Countries with substantial decreases
<p>Germany (-62.8%)</p> <p>Germany achieved the largest reduction in CH₄ emissions due to changed waste management practices in the category 5.A – Solid waste disposal. According to the German National Inventory Report 2024³³, the substantially reduced amount of municipal solid waste deposited is caused by an increased separate collection of biogenic waste, and an increase of waste incineration and mechanical biological treatment. The number of landfills for municipal waste decreased by about 50% since 2004. As the waste deposited since 2006 only contains very small amounts of degradable carbon, future emissions will stabilise on a very low level.</p>

⁽³²⁾ <https://unfccc.int/ghg-inventories-annex-i-parties/2024>

⁽³³⁾ <https://iir.umweltbundesamt.de/2024/>

Countries with substantial decreases

The other category of high relevance is the coal mining and handling, which decreased since 1990 by 99%. Underground mining of anthracite was continuously decreasing and finally stopped in 2018. Surface mining of lignite has a very low CH₄ emission rate and is therefore not as relevant. The little remaining emissions after 2020 are a result of abandoned underground mines and lignite surface mines.

Emissions from enteric fermentation of cattle decreased by 30% since 1990 determined by decreasing number of livestock and better digestibility of the feed, which is partly compensated by increasing gross energy intakes as a result of higher milk yields and animal weights.

Poland (-42.7%)

In Poland, the reductions achieved were highest in the category solid waste disposal, caused by the closing or modernisation of unmanaged and uncategorised landfill sites. These closures led to temporary increase of CH₄ emissions from managed landfill sites peaking in 2007 but followed by a continuous substantial decrease.

Fugitive Emissions from coal mining have also decreases since 1990 by 36%, mainly caused by the declining demand for coal and lignite.

The decrease in emission from cattle arising from enteric fermentation, decreased by 30%, which is caused by a decrease in population numbers by the same extent.

Romania (-56.8%)

In Romania, the decrease of CH₄ emissions since 1990 of 57% is mainly a result of reduced fugitive emissions from use of fossil fuels. In 1990, highest CH₄ emissions were emitted during the production and gathering of natural gas, but these were reduced by 96% due to less natural gas processed and improved technologies preventing losses. The technological improvements are reflected in the calculation by applying from 2000 onwards a lower emission factor, valid for developed countries. The downturn in emission from oil are very similar to the ones for natural gas (less exploration, better technologies). Coal mining activities were substantially reduced, leading to a decrease of CH₄, which is mostly counterbalanced by emissions from abandoned underground mines.

CH₄ emissions from cattle decreased in Romania by 59% since 1990, with decreasing cattle numbers of 66%.

Countries with increasing CH₄ emissions**Cyprus (+38.8%)**

In Cyprus emissions from the disposal of solid waste increased since 1990 by 95%. A major share of emissions still originates from unmanaged waste disposal sites, and managed waste disposal was only started in 2007 and has been increasing since. An underlying reason is that the EU Landfill Directive³⁴ ((EU) 2018/850) although transposed in national legislation, is still not fully implemented yet. Only, 46% of the closed landfills are rehabilitated so far (CY NIR 2024).

Also, CH₄ emissions from cattle related to enteric fermentation, increased by 80%, which is caused by increase in the number of cattle (+49%), as well as increase in gross energy intake and milk yield.

Malta (+62.8%)

Malta saw the highest increases in CH₄ emissions from solid waste disposal, by 263%. The operation of unmanaged landfills was only stopped in 2004, and managed landfills are taking over. The amount of municipal waste generated has been increasing over the years, and in lack of alternative treatment methods, the largest part of generated waste is still landfilled.

Ireland (+6.3%)

The increase in Ireland is a result of increasing CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation of cattle (+28%). The number of cattle increased by 7%, as well as the emission factors (mainly influenced by animal weight, gross energy intake and mild yields).

⁽³⁴⁾ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legaGotherl-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32018L0850>

Countries with increasing CH₄ emissions

Spain (3.3%)

Spain reported significant increases in CH₄ emissions from solid waste disposal and enteric fermentation of cattle. While emissions from unmanaged waste disposal decreased, emissions from managed waste disposal increased by 112%. A result of increasing amounts of municipal waste, and almost half of the generated waste is landfilled.

7.1.2 Trends by Categories

The source of methane is either related to combustion activities, which includes the leakage of gas during mining, transportation and storage, venting and flaring, and the anaerobic decomposition of organic matter, which occurs in the agriculture and waste sector. This also becomes apparent when looking Figure 7.2, which shows the trend per category from 1990 to 2022. Total CH₄ emissions have decreased in the EU by almost 39%, whereby the largest reduction has been achieved by the minimisation of fugitive emissions in the energy sector.

The largest share of CH₄ emissions (Table 7.27.2) is the result of a high CH₄ emission rate due to the ruminant digestive system, expressed in the category 'enteric fermentation'. Methane emissions from manure management are smaller, and are mostly associated with confined animal management operations, where manure is handled in liquid-based systems (IPCC 2006 Guidelines, Vol.4, Chapter 10). The reductions achieved since 1990 of almost 24% from enteric fermentation are largely a result of reduced number of livestock and changed feeding practises.

Figure 7.2: Trend of CH₄ emissions per sector 1990-2022.

Source of data: EEA, 2024c.

CH₄ emissions from the waste sector, are mainly a result of the decomposition of organic carbon in landfill under anaerobic conditions. The EU Landfill Directive³⁵ prescribes that waste must be pre-treated before being landfilled to achieve a degradable content of less than 5%, as well as setting

⁽³⁵⁾ Directive 1999/31/EC: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/1999/31/oj>

technical standards for landfill sites (e.g. landfill gas collection systems, oxidation layer). This led to a significant decrease of CH₄ emissions, and this trend is expected to continue as the decay of waste takes decades and the amount of degradable carbon is continuously decreasing. In opposition to this trend, is the increase in methane resulting from biological waste treatment, which may be either anaerobic digestion or mostly aerobic composting. Both processes may produce methane, depending largely on the operating conditions. As biological treatments are becoming more popular, also regarding its use as a renewable energy source and circular economy principles, it is important to define operating standards minimising CH₄ emissions during waste treatments.

Table 7.2: Trend and share of sectors contributing to EU total CH₄ emissions.

	Share in 1990	Share in 2005	Share in 2022	Absolute Change 1990-2022 [kt CH ₄]	Relative Change 1990-2022	Trend 1990-2022
Energy Industries (1A1)	0.2%	0.4%	0.9%	96.31	258.9%	
Energy consumption (1A2, 1A4, 1A5)	3.7%	3.9%	4.5%	217.09	-24.8%	
Transport (1A3)	0.9%	0.5%	0.3%	179.92	-79.9%	
Fugitive Emissions (1B)	21.9%	16.7%	10.1%	3 739.97	-71.9%	
Industrial Processes (2)	0.3%	0.4%	0.4%	11.69	-17.7%	
Enteric Fermentation (3A)	35.7%	36.9%	44.3%	2 016.10	-23.8%	
Manure Management (3B)	8.2%	9.5%	11.0%	348.65	-17.9%	
Other Agriculture (3C-3J)	0.7%	0.8%	1.1%	0.32	0.2%	
4 LULUCF	2.5%	3.1%	3.8%	41.06	-6.9%	
Solid Waste disposal (5A)	20.3%	22.7%	18.2%	2 175.30	-45.0%	
Biological Waste treatment (5B)	0.1%	0.4%	1.2%	158.37	855.2%	
Waste Incineration (5C) and other (5E)	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	3.01	17.4%	
Waste water treatment (5D)	5.4%	4.5%	4.0%	716.00	-55.4%	
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	9 187.77	-38.7%	

Source of data: EEA, 2024c.

However, the overall decreasing emission trend at EU level, is not valid for all countries. The analysis of emission trends for the years between 1990-2022 shows, that among countries the picture is quite diverse (see Figure 7.3 below). Table 7.3 displays the categories where the highest absolute changes between 2005 and 2022 – decreases or increases, occurred, and list the number of countries for which the category is among the top 3.

Table 7.3: Most relevant categories in Member States for increasing and decreasing CH₄ emissions.

	Number of Member states, where the category is among the top 3 increasing categories	Number of Member states, where the category is among the top 3 decreasing categories
Public electricity and heat production	6	0
Coal mining and handling	0	7
Natural gas (venting, flaring, all other)	1	10
Enteric Fermentation - Cattle	10	11
Manure Management - Cattle	10	0
Solid Waste Disposal	7	17
Biological treatment of waste	13	0
Waste water treatment	1	15

Source of data: EEA, 2024c.

Fugitive emissions as a result from coal mining are overall decreasing, as a result in the ambition of phasing out coal and the use of “greener” energy sources. But also, CH₄ emissions from the exploration/production/processing/distribution of natural gas are largely decreasing, with the only exception of Bulgaria. For CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation, the number of livestock but also the emission factors are decisive. Emission Factors are depending on animal weight, gross energy intake and milk yields, the higher these are the more emissions can be expected. For this reason, the trends across Member States are quite diverse, this is also displayed in Figure 7.3. Generally, CH₄ emissions are following the cattle population number, but for some countries (Cyprus, Denmark, Ireland, Finland) the differences are quite large, indicating a significant influence of the underlying emission factors.

Figure 7.3: CH₄ Emissions from Enteric Fermentation – CH₄ emissions and cattle numbers expressed as relative change between 1990 and 2022.

Source of data: EEA, 2024c.

Manure Management has a share of 11.1% in 2022 in total EU CH₄ emissions. In 10 countries this category is among the top 3 increasing categories. The trend is largely determined by Germany, Spain, France, Italy and the Netherlands, whereby all countries reported decreases except for Spain. Manure from cattle and swine are the most significant contributors. Decisive for the amount of CH₄ emitted is the applied manure management practise, with anaerobic treatments, e.g. in lagoons, ponds, tanks or pits, resulting in the highest emissions, while the deposition of manure on pastures or ranges result in the lowest emissions. Another factor is the climate zone, the higher the temperature, the higher are the resulting emissions. The maximum methane producing capacity of the manure varies by species and diet, which influences also the excretion rate of volatile solids depending on the digestibility of the feed intake.

In the waste sector, methane emissions decreased by 44% in the EU, this is mainly due to the implementation of the EU Landfill Directive, leading to a reduced content of organic carbon in the deposited waste and establishing technical standards for waste disposal sites. Also, emissions from wastewater handling decreased, as anaerobic wastewater treatment, like in septic tanks, is becoming rare. The connection of households to the sewage system is constantly increasing and advanced

wastewater treatment run aerobically. Anaerobic digesters for sludge or waste are a source of CH₄ emissions and should therefore be covered to allow the recovery of the generated gas.

Emissions from the biological treatment of waste are currently eight times as much as in 1990, which is a result of the increased use of this waste treatment method. For example, in 1990 only six countries reported emissions from anaerobic waste digestion, and in 2022 this increased to 24 countries. Greece and Finland reported the highest increases in anaerobic digestion emissions in biogas facilities, accounting of the unintentional leakages of produced gases.

The highest increase in emissions from composting can be observed for Lithuania. Here, the establishment of regional waste management systems and construction of new waste management facilities resulted in significant intensification of waste composting activities. In 2016 several regional mechanical-biological treatment (MBT) facilities were put into operation resulting in another upsurge of waste composting activities (LTU NID 2024).

7.1.3 Analysis of relevant policies and measures at MS level

According to the Energy Governance regulation³⁶ Member States are required to report biannually on their policies and measures. The information submitted by Member States is accessible at the EEA website³⁷, and provided for each measure information like name, description, objective, policy type, implementation status, etc.

To assess to what extent policies and measures are included, only measures which target CH₄ are selected. In total 727 measures out of 3 325, target CH₄ alone or a combination of GHGs including CH₄ (see Figure 7.4). When CH₄ among other GHGs is targeted, PAMs (Policies and Measures) affect mostly the energy consumption and energy supply, followed by waste management. If the PAM only addresses CH₄, it becomes apparent that waste management and agriculture are the most affected sector, which is fully reasonable as these are the major emitting sources.

Figure 7.4: Allocation of CH₄ relevant policies and measures to sectors.

Source of data: EEA, 2024a.

⁽³⁶⁾ REGULATION (EU) 2018/1999 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 11 December 2018 on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action.
⁽³⁷⁾ <https://pam.apps.eea.europa.eu/>

For a further analysis on Member State level, the relevant policies are identified by the selected objectives. Policies and measures, which seem to be especially relevant regarding their potential impact, are described in more detail.

Relevant PAMs addressing fugitive CH₄ emissions from the energy sector

In the sector energy supply, **the objective to control of fugitive emissions from energy production** is most relevant, this objective has been selected in 11 PAMs reported by eight Member States. The following paragraph summarises the most promising policies:

Croatia reported three relevant measures for which the implementation is planned. One foresees the modernisation of the existing infrastructure so that the techniques of extraction, transshipment and construction of a transport network with very low fugitive emissions can be applied during the oil and gas extraction process and in transshipment and transport. Another one is seeking to increase energy efficiency is achieved by implementing measures that contribute to reducing energy intensity through more rational use of energy and raw materials, by adding additives and by altering production processes and equipment at pumping stations and refineries, which contributes to reducing fugitive emissions. And thirdly, it is planned to stop venting of CH₄ emissions by installing torches for flaring.

Denmark has implemented a Tax on methane emissions from natural gas fired power plants - equal in terms of CO₂ equivalents to the CO₂ tax. As of 1 January 2011, a tax on methane emissions - equal in terms of CO₂ equivalents to the CO₂ tax - from natural gas fired power plants was introduced. This is expected to reduce methane emissions from gas engines through behavioural changes such as changing from motor operation to boiler operation and establishing mitigation measures. Consumption is also expected to fall as the price of heat will increase. These behavioural changes will result in falls in the emissions of unburned methane from power stations. In addition, CO₂ emissions will fall, and consumption of natural gas will fall. In total, a decline of 0.06 million tonnes CO₂ equivalent emissions in 2 out of 5 years is expected, corresponding to an average annual reduction effect of approximately 0.02 million tonnes CO₂ equivalent per year in 2008-12.

Poland has implemented a research program in field of methane removal from coal mine using directional boring (DD-MET Project) technology to reduce risk and eliminated greenhouse gases emissions. It is planned to develop a profitable and environment friendly technology of methane removal during operation of coal mines using boring in mines and replace expensive ventilation tunnels build above coal extractions tunnels and other supportive methane removal technologies.

Spain developed a biogas roadmap, providing a series of measures aimed at promoting and fostering it, and leveraging the European consensus on the role this energy vector should play in the context of the green recovery.

Relevant PAMs addressing CH₄ emissions from the agriculture sector

The reporting of PAMs requires Member States to select from a list of predefined one or more objectives, which is / are addressed by the reported policy. Figure 7.5 presents the objectives selected by Member States, showing that improved livestock management and improved animal waste management systems are predominant. Changes in livestock management - especially ruminant animals – and changes in animal waste management systems are both decisive for the amount of methane generated.

Figure 7.5: Policies and Measures reported by EU Member States for the agriculture sector and the selected objective(s).

Note: The number in brackets next to the country name, shows the number of waste PAMs reported; DE, BG and IT are not included as they did not report any PAMs in this category. Source of data: EEA, 2024a.

Table 7.4 analyses the reported PAMs on a more detailed level by summarising and clustering the most promising actions implemented or planned. It becomes then visible that most Member States take measures to reduce methane emissions by amending feeding practices. Also, the use of biogas in the agricultural sector is promoted and financially supported in several countries.

Table 7.4: Summary of agricultural policies reported by MS addressing CH₄ mitigation.

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Feeding	Age Structure	Breeding	Biogas	Pasture	Manure	Organic Farming	Dietary Shift
BE	Belgium established a Covenant “Enteric emissions of cattle” with the aim to reduce enteric emissions by 2030. Partners of the covenant take measures to both optimize feed rations and feed efficiency as well as improving farm management and receive compensation for economic losses.	x							

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Feeding	Age Structure	Breeding	Biogas	Pasture	Manure	Organic Farming	Dietary Shift
HR	Croatia reported a set of measures to reduce CH ₄ emissions, which concern feeding practises, improved manure management facilities, use of biogas plants for electricity production, establishing a cow-calf breeding system involving extensive fattening on pastures. It also plans to improve the breeding and selection program, with the aim to selecting genetically cows with lower CH ₄ emitting potential. One PAM is dedicated to research with the aim to analyse current eating habits and changing these to consume less meat.	x		x	x	x	x		X
DK	Denmark has an Energy policy agreement in place providing subsidies for biogas use in CHP plants, but also for supplying it to the natural gas grid. It further introduced an aid scheme to produce biogas and other green gasses within the Climate Agreement. Fully implemented the scheme aims at reducing emissions by 0,7 mil. tonnes CO ₂ e/yearly by producing 10 PJ biogas and e-methane.				x				
EE	Estonia increased the number of animals grazed extensively without encouraging an increase in overall animal population. Further, in line with the REPower EU program (EC, 2022), investment towards an increased use of biomethane as a renewable energy source have been made.				x	x			
ES	Spain addresses the implementation of agricultural policies in general, and improvements in the management of manure, such as frequent emptying of slurry and coverage of slurry ponds, and interventions to increase organic farming.						x	x	
FI	Finland has implemented two relevant measures aiming at the use of biogas as an alternative to fossil fuels, reducing the CH ₄ emission rate through refining feeding practises and using emission-reducing feed additives. Among the planned measures, is to promote organic farming, scaling-up the plant-protein sector, gender selection of semen to reduce the number of bull calves. Not a measure in itself but also taken into account is the increasing life expectancy of cows, which reduces the need for new heifers.	x	x	x	x			x	x

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Feeding	Age Structure	Breeding	Biogas	Pasture	Manure	Organic Farming	Dietary Shift
FR	France has several measures in place to promote the production and consumption of organic products. It also supports agricultural methanisation projects and their connection to local gas networks. Beyond that, research activities for the use plant protein is funded.				x			x	x
HU	Hungary has a measure in place enabling farmers to build new and modern manure or slurry storage facilities, with 100% insulation of soil and walls.						x		
IE	Ireland plans to implement several measures focusing on the breeds with favourable genetic traits for milk production efficiency and lower emissions, on reducing the slaughter age of cattle, and also the age for first calving. Additionally feed additives should contribute to less modify rumen fermentation. Additives to slurry or livestock manure enhance anaerobic digestion, by optimising the biodegradability and resulting thereby in lower methane generation.	x	x	x			x		
LV	Latvia has planned several measures addressing the feed and its digestibility, extended grazing at pastures and promotion of organic farming. Also, the installation of biogas production and purification facilities on farms is foreseen.	x			x	x			
LT	Lithuania informs farmers about the effect of changing the composition of certain feed on GHG emissions while maintaining productivity and encourages farmers to graze animals extensively in meadows. It also plans to support dietary shift towards more organic food and vegetarian diets.	x				x			
LU	Luxembourg aims for a reduction of its number of cattle and supporting herewith the farm's fodder self-sufficiency. Another measure encourages the use of feed additives primarily in dairy cows to reduce methane emissions from digestion. Also, the exploitation of biogas shall be increased in line with the national Strategy for biogas.	x			x				

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Feeding	Age Structure	Breeding	Biogas	Pasture	Manure	Organic Farming	Dietary Shift
MT	Malta plans to set up dewatering facilities at potentially two sites to manage farm slurries.						x		
NL	Netherlands gradually reduce the crude protein content in dairy feed ratios and promote meadow grazing.	x				x			
PL	Poland supports farmers to apply organic farming practises.							x	
PT	Portugal has a regulatory measure to reduce the carbon intensity of livestock activity through better digestibility of the diet of animals produced in intensive and extensive systems and the treatment systems of livestock effluents.	x							
RO	Romania has an order in place regarding the organization of the activity of improvement and exploitation of meadows at the national level, in the medium and long term. It further plans - supporting the Global Methane Pledge- to improve the feed quality for livestock, increase methane recovery from anaerobic fermentation of manure and use modern methods for fertilizer application.	x			x	x			
SK	Slovakia has a measure in place to support to increase the implementation of organic farming practises, as part of the Rural Development Plan. It further plans to provide support for biogas plants for cattle and pig farms, and to increase the digestibility of the animal feed ratio by changing animal's feeding plans.	x			x			x	
SI	Slovenia has measures in place to increase efficiency in animal production through funded breeding programmes and to increase the proportion of grazing animals. Incentives are provided for the construction of biogas plants and shall be continues for small and micro biogas plants.	x		x	x	x			
SE	Sweden introduced a support scheme for biogas production through anaerobic digestions of manure.				x				
AT, CY, CZ, GR	The PAMs reported by these Member States address mainly the general implementation of EU agricultural policies, such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the Rural Development Program.								
DE, BG, IT	These countries did not report on PAMs, which affect the agriculture sector.								
		12	2	4	11	7	5	5	3

Table 7.4 shows clearly that many Member States are addressing methane from different angles. Most of them report that changing the feeding practises, which also includes the use of specific additives, are becoming a common practise. Influencing the age structure of the cattle is less prominent. However, the increased grazing practises are part of the solution in many countries, together with support schemes and promotion of the production and consumption of organic products. Some countries also explore possibilities to influence the breed by preferring cows with a genetically lower CH₄ emission potential.

An increased use of biogas from agricultural activities but also others, to diversify the energy mix, is largely under implementation, and supported by funding various schemes, and will contribute to lower emissions from manure storage and treatment.

Relevant PAMs addressing CH₄ emissions from the waste sector

Methane emitted in the waste sector, is mainly a result of biological decomposition of organic material under anaerobic conditions. This situation may occur in landfills when material is highly compacted and hardly aerated. The policies and measures implemented, adopted or planned by Member States are largely driven by the EU waste policy framework. Important elements of these are:

- The Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC): introducing the waste hierarchy principles prioritizing prevention, reuse, recycling, and other recovery methods before disposal and leading to reduced amounts of waste landfilled.
- The EU Landfill Directive limiting the amount of municipal waste being landfilled to 10% by 2035, setting technological and operational standards for different classes of landfills and restrictions for the landfilling of biodegradable waste (total organic carbon of waste lower than 3%).
- The Circular Economy Action Plan (COM(2020) 98 final) addresses the entire life cycle of products with the aim to keep resources in the economy as long as possible and prevent waste. Regarding methane, the actions addressing the reduction of food waste, are most relevant. A proposal for a targeted revision of the Waste Framework Directive (COM/2023/420 final) foresees the introduction of reduction targets for food waste from processing and manufacturing, as well as from retail and consumption.

The policies and measures addressing CH₄ emissions in the waste sector reported by Member States in 2023 and 2024 have been analysed with a view to the objectives selected (Figure 7.6), which show that enhanced recycling and reduced landfilling are major aims. Enhanced CH₄ collection and use is less often selected, which can be explained this is in most countries already in place and well established.

Figure 7.6: Policies and Measures reported by EU Member States for the waste sector and the selected objective(s).

Note: The number in brackets next to the country name, shows the number of waste PAMs reported; BG and IT are not included as they did not report any PAMs in this category.
Source of data: EEA, 2024a.

Table 7.5: Main action areas of PAMs reported by MS addressing CH₄ from the waste sector shows for each Member State, the main action areas to address emissions from the waste sector. Areas most promising for reducing methane emissions are the prevention of waste, separate bio waste collection, reduction of landfilling of biodegradable waste and minimisation of food waste.

Methane emissions from wastewater treatment are in the EU less relevant, as most wastewater treatment plants follow aerobic treatments. Only anaerobic sludge treatment may be a significant source of methane of the generated gas is not recovered and flared.

Table 7.5: Main action areas of PAMs reported by MS addressing CH₄ from the waste sector.

MS	Action Areas
AT	Separation of bio-waste, collection and use of landfill gas, minimise food waste, setting composting standards.
BE	Biomass energy strategy.
HR	Waste prevention, recycling, reduction of food waste, separate waste collection, landfill gas collection, reduce landfilling of biodegradable waste, promote circular economy.
CY	Reduce landfilling of biodegradable waste, separate waste collection
CZ	Separate waste collection, recycling, reduce landfilling of biodegradable waste

MS	Action Areas
DK	Adjust waste incineration capacity, recycling, tax system for incineration and landfilling, taxes on packaging, methane recovery from landfills, oxidation layer on landfills
EE	Reduce landfilling of biodegradable waste, separate waste collection, recycling
FI	Biogas, recycling, reduce landfilling of biodegradable waste, waste prevention, waste tax, separate collection
FR	Adapt natural gas network for biomethane, waste prevention (extended producer responsibility), separate waste collection extended, biowaste sorting obligation, regional waste prevention and management plans, minimise food waste, fight planned obsolescence, incentive pricing for waste collection from households, different taxes on waste treatment options, circular economy targets.
DE	Reduce landfilling of biodegradable waste, separate biowaste collection, recycling, aeration of landfills, improved landfill gas collection, minimise food waste, separate waste collection, reduce emissions from digesters, minimise food waste.
GR	Reduce landfilling of biodegradable waste, separate biowaste collection, recovery of biogas/landfill gas.
HU	Waste prevention, separate waste collection, wastewater management, network of waste management facilities.
IE	EU Landfill Directive.
LV	Separate biowaste collection, increased use of refused derived fuel, increased bio waste treatment.
LT	Increased biowaste treatment, biogas production, better waste separation and collection, increased landfill tax, wastewater management, minimise food waste, promote circular economy, manage household composting.
LU	Support circular economy, waste management at company level, waste incineration, methane recovery at landfills, use of biomass as fuel, separate biowaste collection, single-use plastic ban, wastewater management, sewage sludge treatment.
MT	Waste incineration, promote circular economy.
NL	Improve air quality in general through the Clean Air Agreement from 2020, targeting all sectors, participating provinces and municipalities receive support for their implementation plans which contain various measures targeting various sectors
PI	Biogas plants, minimise food waste, wastewater management, waste prevention, waste separation.
PT	Promote circular economy, waste prevention, recycling.
RO	Prevent electronic waste, composting/anaerobic digestion of waste, recycling
SK	Separate waste collection, reduce landfilling of biodegradable waste, recycling, biofiltration for landfill gas, mechanical biological treatment plants, wastewater management.
SI	Waste prevention, extended producer responsibility, separate waste collection, waste tax, use of compost on agricultural land, landfill gas collection, wastewater management.
ES	Support biogas use, promote circular economy, reduce landfilled waste, waste prevention, minimise food waste.

MS	Action Areas
SE	Tax on landfilled waste, ban on landfilling organic waste, landfill gas collection, support manure-based biogas, separate biowaste collection.

Source: EEA, 2024b.

7.1.4 Reflections on the methodologies used to calculate CH₄ emissions

This section looks at the IPCC methodologies used to calculate CH₄ emissions for the categories, and points at methodological issues which need to be considered to reflect occurring changes in calculated numbers.

The CH₄ emissions reported by Member States annually are calculated following the IPCC Guidelines 2006³⁸, which specify the methodologies, activity data and emission factors to be applied. Usually there are three tiers (methodologies) provided. Tier 1 is the basic method, Tier 2 intermediate and Tier 3 most demanding in terms of complexity and data requirements. Tiers 2 and 3 are sometimes referred to as higher tier methods and are generally considered to be more accurate. Tier 1 methods for all categories are designed to use readily available national or international statistics in combination with the provided default emission factors and additional parameters that are provided and therefore should be feasible for all countries. If a category has been identified as key category, it has a significant influence on a country's total inventory of greenhouse gases in terms of the absolute level of emissions and removals, the trend in emissions and removals, or uncertainty in emissions and removals. Higher tier methods (T2 or T3) should be used to calculate emissions from key categories (2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Chapter 1).

Simple methods (T1) are based on default emission data and activity data from mostly international data sources, and produce rather conservative estimates with a higher uncertainty, than Tier 2 or 3 which are based on country specific data derived from national statistics, scientific literature, surveys, expert judgement or measurements. Tier 3 often involves country specific modelling or measurements, e.g. on plants.

Table 7.6 shows the key categories identified in the EU National Inventory 2024 (EEA, 2024c) for CH₄ stating the share of tiers used. For the categories with the highest share – enteric fermentation, manure management and solid waste disposal, it shows that more than 80% of the CH₄ emissions are calculated with higher tiers – meaning that country specific circumstances are considered leading to more reliable and accurate results.

Table 7.6: Overview of higher tier methods used by Member States to calculate CH₄ emissions.

Category Name	Share of higher Tier used	Share in EU CH ₄ total (2022)
1.A.3.b Road Transportation: Gasoline (CH ₄)	97%	0.2%
1.A.4.b Residential: Biomass (CH ₄)	50%	2.8%
1.A.4.b Residential: Solid Fuels (CH ₄)	8%	0.5%
1.B.1.a Coal Mining and Handling: Operation (CH ₄)	69%	6.1%
1.B.2.a Oil: Operation (CH ₄)	31%	0.2%
1.B.2.b Natural Gas: Operation (CH ₄)	63%	2.9%
3.A Enteric Fermentation (CH ₄)	96%	44.2%

⁽³⁸⁾ <https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/>

Category Name	Share of higher Tier used	Share in EU CH ₄ total (2022)
3B. Manure Management (CH ₄)	80%	11.0%
5.A Solid Waste Disposal (CH ₄)	100%	18.2%
5.D Wastewater treatment (CH ₄)	45%	3.9%

Source: EEA, 2024c.

7.1.5 Outlook on future CH₄ emission trends

EU Member States are required under the Energy Governance Regulation to report every two years on their projected GHG emissions. The data used for the assessment below is the dataset published by the EEA in 2024 (EEA, 2024b).

Based on the MS projections, the total CH₄ emissions in the EU are projected to decrease by 21% between 2022 and 2050, under the consideration of policies and measures already implemented (with existing measures = WEM scenario³⁹). Considering additionally measures planned for implementation (with additional measures = WAM scenario⁴⁰), CH₄ emissions are expected to decrease by a further 5%.

From a Member States perspective (see Figure 7.7 and Table 7.7) no major changes are expected regarding the contribution of the Member States to EU total emissions. The highest reductions are projected by France, which also has the highest share. Romania projects the highest relative reductions (more than 40%). Slight increases until 2050 are only reported by Greece.

⁽³⁹⁾ A WEM (or WM) scenario covers existing policies and measures' means implemented policies and measures and adopted policies and measures, 'implemented policies and measures' means policies and measures for which one or more of the following applies at the date of submission of the integrated national energy and climate plan or of the integrated national energy and climate progress report: directly applicable Union or national law is in force, one or more voluntary agreements have been established, financial resources have been allocated, human resources have been mobilised, 'adopted policies and measures' means policies and measures for which an official government decision has been made by the date of submission of the integrated national energy and climate plan or of the integrated national energy and climate progress report and there is a clear commitment to proceed with implementation (REGULATION (EU) 2018/1999, Art.2.2, 2.3 and 2.4).

⁽⁴⁰⁾ A WAM scenarios includes 'planned policies and measures' means options that are under discussion and that have a realistic chance of being adopted and implemented after the date of submission of the integrated national energy and climate plan or of the integrated national energy and climate progress report (REGULATION (EU) 2018/1999, Art.2.5).

Figure 7.7: Projected CH₄ emissions from Member States presenting the WEM scenario from 2022-2050.

Source of data: EEA, 2024b.

Table 7.7: Share and trend of MS projected CH₄ emissions (WEM scenario).

	Share in 2022	Share in 2050	Absolute Change 2022-2050 [kt CH ₄]	Relative Change 2022-2050	Trend 2022-2050
AT	1.6%	1.6%	- 48.36	-20.8%	
BE	1.9%	2.0%	- 39.80	-14.4%	
BG	1.6%	1.6%	- 52.67	-22.1%	
CY	0.3%	0.2%	- 10.55	-27.5%	
CZ	3.1%	2.7%	- 139.02	-30.2%	
DE	12.4%	13.3%	- 284.96	-15.4%	
DK	2.1%	2.1%	- 60.96	-19.5%	
ES	9.8%	9.2%	- 374.50	-25.6%	
EE	0.3%	0.3%	- 3.97	-9.3%	
FI	1.3%	1.2%	- 56.90	-29.3%	
FR	14.8%	14.3%	- 508.98	-23.1%	
GR	2.6%	3.4%	11.42	2.9%	
HR	1.0%	0.7%	- 56.52	-39.2%	
HU	1.9%	1.8%	- 78.55	-27.3%	
IE	5.2%	6.5%	- 5.49	-0.7%	
IT	11.0%	10.0%	- 466.23	-28.3%	
LT	0.7%	0.7%	- 32.79	-29.5%	
LU	0.2%	0.2%	- 1.69	-7.3%	
LV	0.7%	0.8%	- 8.28	-8.4%	
MT	0.1%	0.1%	- 0.66	-5.6%	
NL	4.4%	4.7%	- 98.94	-15.0%	
PL	12.0%	13.5%	- 193.30	-10.8%	
PT	2.4%	2.1%	- 105.04	-29.3%	
RO	6.2%	4.6%	- 378.70	-41.1%	
SK	0.9%	0.7%	- 39.00	-30.6%	
SI	0.5%	0.5%	- 14.00	-17.7%	
SE	1.2%	1.2%	- 35.76	-20.2%	
EU-27	100.0%	100.0%	-3084.2	-20.7%	

Source of data: EEA, 2024b.

When looking at the projected trend of contributing sector (Table 7.8), highest emission reductions are expected in the waste sector, due to a continuous decrease of depositing waste with high biodegradable carbon contents in landfills and flaring of landfill gas or biogas for energy purposes. Agriculture will continue being the sector responsible for the highest share of CH₄ emissions, with an expected reduction of 5-6%. With the further replacement of fossil fuels for combustion a decrease of fugitive emissions and CH₄ from combustion processes goes along. Increases in the LULUCF sector are expected, mainly due to increased wetland areas. CH₄ emissions from industrial processes are currently rather negligible, which will not change in the future.

Table 7.8: Share and trend of sectors contributing to CH₄ total emissions in the EU for 2022-2050.

	Share in 2022	Share in 2050	Absolute Change 2022-2050 [kt CH ₄]	Relative Change 2022-2050	Trend 2022-2050
1. Energy (excl. 1B Fugitives)	5.8%	3.6%	- 438.47	-50.4%	
1.B. Fugitive emissions from fuels	10.2%	10.8%	- 249.07	-16.3%	
2. Industrial processes	0.4%	0.5%	1.32	2.3%	
3. Agriculture	55.4%	65.8%	- 458.58	-5.5%	
4. Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF)	3.6%	5.4%	98.52	18.3%	
5. Waste	24.6%	14.0%	- 2 009.51	-54.8%	
EU total	100.0%	100.0%	- 3 055.78	-20.5%	

Source of data: EEA, 2024b.

7.1.6 Relevant policies on EU level and Policy Recommendations

In the past, the reduction of methane emissions has merely been addressed by the EU policy framework not explicitly but integrated to other policy objectives. But with increasing urgency of bringing greenhouse gas emissions down, a focus is put on methane, as its global warming potential is 28 times higher than the one of carbon dioxide⁴¹ and has a lifetime of about 12 years, which is comparably short for a greenhouse gas, but long as an air pollutant. So, cutting methane emissions will have a net cooling effect within a relatively short period and lower the formation of ground-level ozone.

As already mentioned, there are sets of sectoral policies for waste and agriculture, and overarching policies. Methane emissions of the waste sector are addressed by the **Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)**, the **EU Landfill Directive**, the **Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive ((EU) 2024/3019)** and the **Circular Economy Action Plan (COM(2020) 98 final)**, which already led to decreases in methane emissions of 44% in the waste sector between 1990 and 2022. The relevance of monitoring and managing food waste is addressed in the Waste Framework Directive from 2008, laying down an obligation for Member States to include food waste prevention into their waste prevention programmes and to monitor and assess the implementation of their food waste prevention ((EU)2019/1597).

The **Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** of the EU is about the entire agri-food value aiming to achieve economic sustainability by ensuring viable farm income and resilience, enhancing market orientation and increasing competitiveness, and improving the farmers' position in the value chain. Tackling climate change is one of the key objectives of the CAP and integrated in national CAP strategic plans.

One pillar of the EU Green Deal is the **Farm to Fork** (EU, 2020a) strategy aiming to make food systems fair, healthy and environmentally friendly, looking at the whole cycle of food production, processing, distribution, consumption and waste prevention. Regarding the reduction of methane emissions, the strategy promotes investments in anaerobic digesters for biogas production from agriculture waste and residues, the placing on the market of sustainable and innovative feed additives, a dietary shift and the prevention of waste.

In 2020, The European Commission adopted the **methane strategy** (EU, 2020b) with the aim to improve measurement and reporting of methane emissions and lay out measures how reduce emissions in the energy, the agriculture and the waste sector.

Methane, being always a major component of biogas, experienced also a recognition in the last few years as a sustainable alternative to fossil gas, contributing to a lower dependency on foreign gas and

⁽⁴¹⁾ 5th IPCC Assessment report, GWP values for 100-year time horizon

lower greenhouse gas emissions. The EU plans to scale up the use of biomethane (**Biomethane Action Plan**), the purified version of biogas, as part of the REPower EU Plan (EC, 2022). The proposed actions aim at expanding the production of biogas to a sustainable volume which can be upgraded into biomethane and promoting biomethane production from waste and residues, rather than from food and feedstocks, which can lead to land use change related issues. These actions should also facilitate the sustainable upgrading and safe injection of biomethane into the gas grid. How these actions may impact the level of methane emissions will largely depend on the minimised occurrence of leakages during production and distribution. However, carbon dioxide from combustion of fossil fuels will be avoided.

Another important, relatively new EU legislation is the **EU Methane Regulation** ((EU)2024/1787), which requires fossil energy infrastructures operators to measure methane emissions regularly, to prevent avoidable emissions and minimize leaks from fossil fuel operations. This regulation is expected to have an impact on fugitive methane emissions from fuels, which currently has a share of about 10% in total EU methane emissions (see Table 7.8).

Methane is also addressed on global level, through the **Global Methane Pledge**⁴², which was launched at the COP26 in November 2021. This pledge has been signed by 159 parties of the UNFCCC and the EU. These countries commit to collectively reduce methane emissions by at least 30% below 2020 levels by 2030. During the last COP meeting in 2024, additional finance was mobilized and accelerated actions across different actors, governments as well as the private sector.

With the ongoing discussion to include reduction commitments for methane in the **Gothenburg Protocol**, methane is getting also from an air pollution perspective more attention. Such an amendment would increase the pressure to achieve progress but also increase the reporting burden for a pollutant which is already reported under a different obligation.

Methane is addressed through a variety of sector specific but also general plans and policies, whereby emphasis should be put on sustainable actions, which address the cause of the pollution and not alleviate symptoms (Table 7.9). In the waste sector, much progress has already been made in by avoiding the landfilling of organic waste instead of intensifying landfill gas collection systems.

Table 7.9: Potential solutions to substantial reduction of CH₄ emissions.

Source of Methane Emissions	End of Pipe - Solution	Transformative Solution
Enteric fermentation	Changes in food, new breeds, changes in age structure, feed additives	Minimise consumption of meat and dairy products. Increased consumption of synthetic/cultured meat
Fugitive emission from the use of fossil fuels	Avoid leakages	Phase out the use of fossil fuels
Waste management	Pre-treatment of waste, active aeration in composting, closed anaerobic digestion	Minimise waste generation: circular economy, no food waste

7.2 Non methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC)

As mentioned in Section 5, non methane volatile organic compounds are a group of chemicals that contain carbon in their molecular structure, e.g. alcohols, aldehydes, alkanes, aromatics, halocarbons and ketones. They differ widely in their chemical composition but show a similar behaviour in the

⁽⁴²⁾ <https://www.globalmethanepledge.org/>

atmosphere. NMVOCs are emitted from many biogenic (mainly from vegetation) and anthropogenic sources, such as combustion, solvent use and production processes. Once emitted to the atmosphere, they contribute to tropospheric ozone formation, while some compounds (e.g., benzene and butadiene) are also hazardous to human health, highlighting the importance of monitoring emission changes.

7.2.1 Trends by Member States

NMVOC emissions decreased in the EU27 from 16,404 kt to 6,291 kt between the years 1990 and 2022, which is a reduction of 61.6 %. Under the NEC Directive, which is currently undergoing a revision, Member States are obliged to reduce NMVOC emissions among other air pollutants.

All countries reported decreases of NMVOC emissions in that period. The total EU emission trend is largely determined by Germany, France and Italy (Figure 7.8) – the countries with the largest absolute reductions between 1990 and 2022 (Table 7.10).

Figure 7.8: Trend of NMVOC emissions across EU Member States from 1990-2022.

Note: the figure displays the 10 biggest contributors to NMVOC emissions in the EU. ‘Other’ sums up all other remaining countries; please see Annex 1 to this report for the whole dataset.
 Source of data: EU submission under the Air convention, Annex I (EEA, 2024e).

Table 7.10: Information on trend and share of NMVOC emissions of EU Member States.

	Share in 1990	Share in 2005	Share in 2022	Absolute Change 1990-2022 [kt]	Relative Change 1990-2022	Trend 1990-2022
AT	2.0%	1.6%	1.6%	- 228.73	-69.6%	
BE	2.3%	2.2%	2.1%	- 254.43	-66.1%	
BG	2.7%	1.1%	1.2%	- 373.37	-83.0%	
CY	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	- 6.99	-48.8%	
CZ	5.1%	4.0%	4.5%	- 549.04	-65.8%	
DE	24.0%	15.7%	16.4%	- 2 894.84	-73.7%	
DK	1.3%	1.7%	1.9%	- 100.29	-45.8%	
ES	6.3%	7.8%	8.7%	- 488.80	-47.3%	
EE	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%	- 37.99	-59.0%	
FI	1.4%	1.6%	1.2%	- 158.20	-67.7%	
FR	17.8%	19.1%	16.9%	- 1 855.01	-63.5%	
GR	1.9%	3.6%	2.2%	- 181.47	-56.8%	
HR	1.1%	1.2%	1.0%	- 112.79	-64.9%	
HU	1.9%	2.0%	1.9%	- 195.99	-62.4%	
IE	1.0%	1.3%	1.8%	- 46.19	-29.4%	
IT	12.0%	14.1%	13.1%	- 1 147.26	-58.2%	
LT	0.7%	0.6%	0.7%	- 70.09	-59.9%	
LU	0.2%	0.2%	0.2%	- 21.06	-67.8%	
LV	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%	- 52.97	-62.6%	
MT	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	- 2.20	-44.8%	
NL	3.7%	2.9%	3.8%	- 364.33	-60.1%	
PL	5.1%	8.4%	9.7%	- 231.62	-27.5%	
PT	1.6%	2.1%	2.4%	- 106.77	-41.1%	
RO	2.6%	3.7%	3.7%	- 197.51	-45.6%	
SK	1.5%	1.4%	1.3%	- 163.94	-66.5%	
SI	0.4%	0.5%	0.5%	- 36.82	-56.3%	
SE	2.2%	2.2%	2.1%	- 234.24	-63.9%	
EU-27	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	- 10 112.93	-61.6%	

Source of data: EU submission under the Air convention, Annex I (EEA, 2024e).

In the following table the emission trends of countries with a specifically high decrease (in absolute terms) and the underlying reasons are described in more detail:

Countries with substantial decreases
<p>Germany (-73.7%)</p> <p>Germany achieved the largest reduction in NMVOC emissions in category 1.A.3.b.i – Road Transport: Passenger cars are due to the implementation of catalytic-converter use and engine improvements resulting from ongoing tightening of emissions laws and improved fuel quality. Additionally, the implementation of the Technical Instruction on Air Quality Control⁴³, which is affecting the storage</p>

⁽⁴³⁾ TA-Luft 2002:

https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/1/dokumente/taluft_stand_200207241.pdf

Countries with substantial decreases

of petrol and fuelling of motor vehicles, as well as a reduction in petrol consumption in Germany leads to decreases of NMVOC emissions.

As a result of regulatory provisions on the limitation of emissions of volatile organic compounds due to the use of organic solvents in certain facilities, NMVOC emissions show a substantial decrease in printing and the use of solvents and solvent-containing products since the year 1999 (Category 2D – Solvent and Product Use) (DE IIR 2024).

France (-63.5%)

In France, the substantial decreases of NMVOC emissions were achieved mainly in road transport due to the installation of catalytic converters and activated carbon filters in gasoline vehicles, as well as the shift to diesel vehicles.

Also, the implementation of regulations to reduce NMVOC emissions in the industry sector and the substitution of products with lower concentration of solvents or solvent free products affect the decrease in NMVOC emissions in France (FR IIR 2024).

Italy (-58.2%)

Main reductions of NMVOC emissions in Italy were achieved by the introduction of products with low solvent content in paints, and the reduction of the total amount of organic solvent used for metal degreasing and in glues and adhesives; furthermore, abatement equipment in the industrial painting sector and the replacement of open loop with closed loop laundry machines were established.

Also decreasing NMVOC emissions in the transport sector are contributing significantly to the overall reduction in Italy. These are mainly driven by the gradual adjustment of the national fleet to the European legislation, which introduced the use of catalytic device to reduce exhaust and evaporative emissions from cars. Additionally, incentives were provided for the replacement of both the fleet of passenger cars and of mopeds and motorcycles with low-emission vehicles, the use of fuels different from gasoline (LPG and natural gas), the implementation of urban traffic plans (e.g. the establishment of restricted traffic areas, car-free days), checks on exhaust pipes of cars and voluntary agreements with manufacturers of mopeds and motorcycles to place mopeds with low emissions on the market (IT IIR 2024).

7.2.2 Trends by Categories

In 1990, the main source of NMVOC emissions in the EU was road transportation. Because of the introduction of Euro emission standards⁴⁴, the continuous renewal of the vehicle fleet and improvements in storage of petrol⁴⁵, emissions from this source decreased significantly by 90.2% (Figure 7.9).

⁽⁴⁴⁾ Directive 98/69/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1998/69/oj/eng>; Directive 2005/55/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32005L0055>; Directive 2005/78/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32005L0078>;

⁽⁴⁵⁾ Directive 94/63/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1994/63/oj/eng>

Figure 7.9: Share of NMVOC emissions per sector 1990 and 2022.

Source of data: EEA, 2024e.

Table 7.11: Trend and share of sectors contributing to EU total NMVOC emissions.

	Share in 1990	Share in 2005	Share in 2022	Absolute Change 1990-2022 [kt NMVOC]	Relative Change 1990-2022	Trend 1990-2022
Energy Industries (1A1)	0.5%	0.7%	1.0%	13	-17.4%	
Energy consumption (1A2, 1A4, 1A5 - excl. mobile)	14.5%	16.4%	18.3%	1 220	-51.4%	
Transport (1A3, 1A4, 1A5)	34.3%	20.1%	8.7%	5 082	-90.2%	
Fugitive Emissions (1B)	6.5%	5.8%	4.7%	766	-71.9%	
Industrial Processes (2)	31.0%	39.2%	41.3%	2 492	-48.9%	
Manure Management (3B)	9.4%	12.8%	18.5%	381	-24.6%	
Other Agriculture (3C-3J)	3.3%	4.3%	6.5%	136	-25.0%	
Waste (5)	0.5%	0.8%	0.9%	24	-29.3%	
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	10 114	-61.6%	

Source of data: EEA, 2024e.

Nowadays, the emission trend is dominated by NMVOC emissions from residential heating combustion (subcategory 1A4bi) and solvent use (the domestic solvent use including fungicides (subcategory 2D3a) and the coating applications (subcategory 2D3d) and manure management of dairy and non-dairy cattle (subcategory 3B1). These categories account for 56% of all NMVOC emissions in the EU in 2022 and have decreased by 40% since 1990.

Based on the EMEP/EEA Guidebook (EMEP/EEA, 2023), solvent use and coating applications release a wide range of compounds including aromatic hydrocarbons (toluene, xylenes, ethylbenzene, benzene, trimethylbenzenes, styrene), esters (butyl acetate, ethyl acetate), ketones (acetone, methyl ethyl ketone), alcohols (ethanol, methanol), glycol ethers, and alkanes used as propellants in aerosol products (propane, butane, isobutane) or as solvents (n-hexane, n-heptane, white spirit). Most of these compounds are included in the 45 NMVOC species listed in Annex VII of the revised AAQD (see Section 5, Table 5.1), notably all BTEX compounds, trimethylbenzenes, key ketones, alcohols, and relevant alkanes. Toluene and m,p-xylene, which collectively contribute approximately 28% to the Maximum Ozone Formation Potential (Salameh et al., 2024), and which are among the species required for monitoring. Given the dominance of these sources in current EU NMVOC emissions, monitoring strategies should prioritise the associated compounds. As detailed in Section 5, the revised

AAQD requires Member States to establish VOC monitoring where appropriate, with network design reflecting prevalent emission sources. For regions where residential heating, solvent use, and coating applications are significant contributors to ozone formation, this implies prioritising routine measurements of BTEX compounds, trimethylbenzenes, acetone, and methyl ethyl ketone at urban and industrial sites. Such targeted monitoring would provide essential data to assess the effectiveness of emission reduction measures under the VOC Solvents Directive⁴⁶ and the Industrial Emissions Directive⁴⁷, while supporting the development of evidence-based ozone mitigation strategies.

The overall decreasing emission trend at EU level, is not valid for all countries. The analysis of emission trends for the years between 1990-2022 shows, that among countries the picture is quite diverse (see Table 7.12). This table displays the categories where the highest absolute changes – decreases or increases, occurred, and list the number of countries for which the category is among the top 3.

Table 7.12: Most relevant categories in Member States for increasing and decreasing NMVOC emissions.

	Number of Member States, where the category is among the top 3 increasing categories	Number of Member States, where the category is among the top 3 decreasing categories
Road transport: passenger cars	0	25
Residential heating	2	0
Domestic solvent use including fungicides	13	0
Coating applications	2	14
Manure Management - Cattle	6	3

NMVOC emissions from residential heating mainly occur from the burning of firewood. Overall decreases have been achieved due to the replacement of more efficient and lower-emitting appliances as well as a decrease of energy demand in households due to reconstruction activities (SK IIR 2024). The domestic solvent use including fungicides (subcategory 2D3a) and the coating applications (subcategory 2D3d) represent 36% and 29% of all NMVOC emissions from solvent use (category 2D) in 2022, respectively. These emissions result mainly from the evaporation of organic solvents in paints. NMVOCs, such as butane and propane are also used in propellants (EMEP/EEA, 2023). While emissions from the domestic solvent use including fungicides have increased between 1990 and 2022 in the EU by 26%, substantial reductions have been achieved in the NMVOC emissions from coating applications. Emissions from this source have decreased by 64% (-1175kt NMVOC) since 1990 because of the implementation of legal regulations, such as the VOC solvents directive⁴⁶, the directive on industrial emissions⁴⁸ and the Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive⁴⁹, which represent the main policy instruments for reducing industrial VOC emissions. NMVOC emissions from the manure management originate from feed (especially silage) and the degradation of digested and undigested fats, carbohydrates and protein in the rumen and the manure. Therefore, the emissions of NMVOC from this source are directly affected by the rate of feeding and manure management (e.g. amount of formic acid added to silage, silage heaps and livestock feeding,

⁽⁴⁶⁾ Council Directive 1999/13/EC of 11 March 1999 on the limitation of emissions of volatile organic compounds due to the use of organic solvents in certain activities and installations

⁽⁴⁷⁾ Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control)

⁽⁴⁸⁾ Directive 2010/75/EU: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/75/oj>

⁽⁴⁹⁾ Directive 2010/75/EU: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/75/2024-08-04>

manure management during livestock housing and storage, straw added to manure, duration of manure storage and techniques used for manure application (EMEP/EEA, 2023).

7.2.3 Analysis of relevant policies and measures at MS level

Member States are required to report on their policies and measures, according to the NEC Directive. Article 6 of the directive sets out the obligation for Member States to draw, adopt and implement their respective National Air Pollution Control Programme (NAPCP) including their selected policies and measures, in order to fulfil their emission reduction commitments.

Policies and measures, contained in the national air pollution control programmes must be updated within 18 months of the submission of the latest national emission inventory or national emission projections.

To assess to what extent policies and measures are included, only measures which target NMVOC are selected. In total 492 measures out of 809, target NMVOC alone or a combination of other air pollutants including NMVOC (see Figure 7.10). When NMVOC among other pollutants is targeted, PAMs affect mostly the transport sector and energy consumption, followed by energy supply. If the PAM only addresses NMVOC, it becomes apparent that industrial processes and energy supply are the most targeted sectors, which are the major emitting sources.

Figure 7.10: PAMs addressing NMVOC emissions per sector

Source of data: EEA, 2024d.

For a further analysis on Member State level, the relevant policies are identified by the selected objectives. Policies and measures, which seem to be especially relevant regarding their potential impact, are described in more detail.

Relevant PAMs addressing NMVOC emissions from the energy sector

Within the energy sector, energy consumption and energy supply are most relevant regarding policies and measures addressing NMVOC emissions.

Overall, in both energy supply and energy consumption sector, the objectives ‘Demand management/reduction’ and ‘Efficiency improvements of buildings’ are the most important ones (Figure 7.11).

In sector energy supply, the objective to increase renewable energy is most relevant. It has been selected in 70 PAMs reported by 15 Member States. 90 PAMs (reported by 10 Member States) are

addressing the most relevant objective ‘demand management/reduction’ in sector energy consumption.

Figure 7.11: Policies and Measures reported by EU Member States for the energy consumption and energy supply sectors and the selected objectives.

Note: The number in brackets next to the country name, shows the number of energy PAMs reported; AT, BG, DK, FI, FR, LU, NL, PT and SE are not included as they did not report any PAMs in this category
Source: EEA, 2024d.

Table 7.13 analyses the reported PAMs on a more detailed level by summarising and clustering the most promising actions implemented or planned. It becomes then visible that most Member States take measures to increase the share of renewable energy. Also, the switch to less carbon intensive fuels and improvements in efficiency are promoted and financially supported in several countries.

Table 7.13: Summary of energy supply and consumption policies reported by MS addressing NMVOC.

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Increase in renewable Energy	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Efficiency improvement in the energy and transformation	Reduction of losses	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Enhanced non-renewable low carbon generation (nuclear)	Demand management/reduction	Efficiency improvements of buildings	Efficiency improvement of appliances
CY	The promotion of Renewable Energy Systems as well as the introduction and use of Natural gas in the internal market	x	x	x						

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Increase in renewable Energy	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Efficiency improvement in the energy and transformation	Reduction of losses	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Enhanced non-renewable low carbon generation (nuclear)	Demand management/reduction	Efficiency improvements of buildings	Efficiency improvement of appliances
	for electricity production are reported PAMs regarding the energy consumption and supply sectors.									
CZ	Czechia's PAMs mainly aim on the awareness raising for correct operating and maintaining of combustion sources and health risks associated with combustion of solid fuels.	x	x		x	x				
EE	Estonia reported a set of PAMs, addressing the NMVOC reduction in the energy sector, including the renovation, construction and/or replacement of inefficient of district heating boilers and heating pipelines, fuel exchange, investments in more sustainable technologies (e.g. wind parks, hydrogen technologies, production and usage of biomethane) and VAT incentives	x	x	x				x		
DE	NMVOC emissions from the energy supply and consumption in Germany are tackled by draft legal regulations to increase renewable energy in heating systems.	x								
GR	PAMs in Greece, concerning NMVOC emissions in the sectors energy supply and consumption, are associated with the implementation of the EU Directives 94/63/EC (control of emissions of volatile organic compounds from the storage of petrol and its distribution) and 2009/126/EC (recovery of petrol vapor) and the reduction of lignite mining for use in electricity generation.	x	x		x					
IE	Ireland promotes the deployment of solar energy systems as well as the replacement of coal fired electricity generation with natural gas fired electricity generation.	x	x							
IT	Italy implemented changes in incentivization rules on bioenergy.	x								

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Increase in renewable Energy	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Efficiency improvement in the energy and transformation	Reduction of losses	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Enhanced non-renewable low carbon generation (nuclear)	Demand management/reduction	Efficiency improvements of buildings	Efficiency improvement of appliances
LV	Latvia's PAMs for the energy supply and energy consumption sectors include financial support programs for district heating or local central heating, the use of renewable energy sources and technologies (sun, wind, heat pumps), connection of households, public buildings and industrial installations to district or local central heating system as well as the extension of District Heating Networks and the development of new systems.	x		x						
LT	Lithuania has reported a set of PAMs concerning NMVOC emissions in the energy sector, including: -Limit the burning of solid fossil fuels (coal, lignite, peat) by legal means -Incentives to install renewable energy sources -Renovation of buildings -Financial incentives to change the heat production devices installed in households -Awareness campaigning including measures and solutions for increasing energy efficiency -Development of the hydrogen market and infrastructure -Implement local and RES-based Combined Heat and Power (CHP) projects. -Use of residual heat in District Heating (DH) systems. -Installation of heat storage tanks, heat pumps. -Construction of solar collector systems for district heating activities and of boilers burning biofuel from logging residues -Deployment of alternative fuels in industrial plants	x	x	x	x			x	x	
MT	Malta reported on schemes on solar water heaters in the residential sector and on encourage battery integration in photovoltaic systems.	x							x	

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Increase in renewable Energy	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Efficiency improvement in the energy and transformation	Reduction of losses	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Enhanced non-renewable low carbon generation (nuclear)	Demand management/reduction	Efficiency improvements of buildings	Efficiency improvement of appliances
PL	Poland reports PAMs on supporting investment projects in the field of construction (expansion or modernization of existing production facilities or industrial equipment), the expansion of the district heating network and the energetic use of geothermal resources. Additionally, co-financing the purchase and installation of photovoltaic installations, wind installations, heat pumps and hybrid installations, the support of offshore wind farms and the commission of nuclear power units are reported to tackle NMVOC emissions in the energy sector.	x		x			x		x	
RO	The modernization, rehabilitation, upgrading and extension or establishment of centralized heat supply systems of localities, financing high-efficiency cogeneration based on natural gas, supporting the installation of photovoltaic/photothermal panels at household level and small-scale renewable energy production, transport and storage capacities of energy demand in public buildings are reported by Romania.	x		x		x				
SK	Slovakia's reported PAMs in the energy sector are dealing with measures, such as control systems for devices using solid fuels, switching to District Heating Systems, thermal insulation combined with the introduction of a biomass gasification boiler or condensing gas boilers, replacing high emissions boilers by more energy efficient ones and phasing out of coal mining.	x			x	x		x	x	x
SI	Slovenia plans to increase the connection of buildings in urban areas to the district heating systems and increase the electricity and heat production from renewables.	x	x			x	x			

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Increase in renewable Energy	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Efficiency improvement in the energy and transformation	Reduction of losses	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Enhanced non-renewable low carbon generation (nuclear)	Demand management/reduction	Efficiency improvements of buildings	Efficiency improvement of appliances
ES	<p>Spain addresses NMVOC emissions in the energy sector (supply and consumption) by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Financial support instruments for the use of renewable energy in the industrial sector, -Pre-feasibility studies for thermal biogas application projects, -Direct biomethane in transport -Repowering of wind farms, -Renovation of mini-hydroelectric plants -Innovative wind turbine blade recycling facilities. -Integration of thermal renewables into the building sector -New hydroelectric energy storage capacity -Self-consumption with renewables -Promote biomass energy with sustainability criteria, <p>Additionally the 2021-2026 Electricity Transmission Grid Development Plan sets out that renewable energy coverage of electricity consumption is expected to reach 81% by 2030.</p>	x	x	x	x			x		x

Relevant PAMs addressing NMVOC emissions from the Industrial Processes sector

Within the Industrial Processes (IPPU) sector, the objective to install abatement technologies is most relevant and has been selected in 33 PAMs reported by 10 Member States, followed by the objective ‘Efficiency improvement in industrial end-use sectors’ (Figure 7.12).

Figure 7.12: Policies and Measures reported by EU Member States for the industry processes sector and the selected objectives.

Note: The number in brackets next to the country name, shows the number of industry PAMs reported; AT, BG, CZ, DE, DK, FI, FR, IE, IT, LU, NL, PL, PT, SK and SE are not included as they did not report any PAMs in this category
 Source: EEA, 2024d.

Table 7.14 analyses the reported PAMs on a more detailed level by summarising and clustering the actions implemented or planned.

It becomes then apparent that most Member States apply legal frameworks to reduce NMVOC emissions by increasing measurements, introducing and promoting reduction technologies (e.g. by applying the best available techniques (BAT)) and by growing the share and use of renewable energies.

PAMs dealing with the reduction of NMVOC emissions from solvents use, one of the main contributors of NMVOC emissions in the EU in 2022, are reported by most of the countries. Many of them are dealing with the implementation of the Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive⁵⁰, the directive on industrial emissions⁵¹ and the directive on the limitation of emissions of volatile organic compounds due to the use of organic solvents in certain paints and varnishes and vehicle refinishing products⁵².

⁽⁵⁰⁾ Directive 2010/75/EU: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/75/2024-08-04>
⁽⁵¹⁾ Directive 2010/75/EU: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/75/oj>
⁽⁵²⁾ Directive 2004/42/EC: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2004/42/2021-07-16>

Table 7.14: Summary industry processes policies reported by MS addressing NMVOC.

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Improved control of fugitive emissions from industrial processes	Installation of abatement technologies	Demand management/reduction	Deployment of pollution abatement technologies on vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Reduction of losses	Other industrial processes	Increase in renewable energy	Efficiency improvement in industrial end-use sectors
BE	PAMs are aiming at the shift towards lower and more efficient Best Available Technique - Associated Emission Level (BAT-AEL) values for companies using or producing solvents.	x	x						
HR	Research should help identify cost-effective measures, measures that have a positive impact on economic development, employment, research that help transfer knowledge about best available techniques and good practice.		x	x	x	x			
EE	A production plant must comply to the best available technologies (BAT). The requirements of the Industrial Emissions Act include emission limit values, monitoring and emission reduction measures through the implementation of BATs if an environmental permit is issued.	x	x				x		
GR	Reported PAMs are dealing with the implementation of Directives 2010/75/EU (reduction of emissions into the air, water and soil), 2004/42/EC (restrictions on the composition, of consumer products, such as decorative paints and varnishes and car refinishing products) and Directive 1999/13/EC (limit emissions of volatile organic compounds due to the use of organic solvents).	x	x						
HU	PAMs related to industrial processes are dealing with technology-specific emission limit values for activities which are not covered by IED in national legislation, a review of emission limit values set before 2011 and a change according to the state of the art as well as the development and promotion of a tax incentive scheme to promote the use of emerging techniques.	x	x						

	Summary of relevant policies and measures per country	Improved control of fugitive emissions from industrial processes	Installation of abatement technologies	Demand management/reduction	Deployment of pollution abatement technologies on vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Reduction of losses	Other industrial processes	Increase in renewable energy	Efficiency improvement in industrial end-use sectors
LV	Latvia reported PAMs connected to the reduction of NMVOC emissions in the IPPU sector are including: -More efficient control of polluting activities in the Industry -Revision of existing permits and the application of stricter emission requirements -Installation of vapor recovery systems in arbors for oil products and hazardous chemicals -Implementation of measures by operators -Raise of fines to prevent operators from breaching environmental requirements	x	x				x		
LT	PAMs dealing with the reduction of NMVOC emissions in the sector 'Industry Processes' include the introduction and application of NMVOC emission reduction technology compliant with Best Available Techniques (BAT) as well as the limitation of emissions of volatile organic compounds due to the use of organic solvents in installations. The country also reported the application of stricter emission limit values for combustion plants, boilers and heaters, financial incentives to apply measures for NMVOC emissions reduction and the promotion and use of renewable energy sources.	x	x	x	x	x			
MT	The Environmental Authorisations Regulations provide a framework for environmental authorizations, laying down the thresholds, procedure and guidance for the Environment and Resources Authority to authorize and regulate any activity, operation, intervention, project or land use that may influence the environment. Provisions include operating conditions on emissions to air, effluent discharges, emissions to land, waste storage, acceptance, handling and treatment.	x	x				x		

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Improved control of fugitive emissions from industrial processes	Installation of abatement technologies	Demand management/reduction	Deployment of pollution abatement technologies on vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Reduction of losses	Other industrial processes	Increase in renewable energy	Efficiency improvement in industrial end-use sectors
RO	Romania reports the promotion of green technologies and the implementation of circular economy principles in the manufacturing industry as well as an improvement of the reporting and recording for solvents and use of the products and the use of solvents in households.						x		
SI	The country reports of the reduction of solvent content in road paints in its submitted PAMs dealing with the reduction of NMVOC emissions in the industry sector.						x		
ES	Spain provides a set of PAMs including the promotion in investment in high-energy-efficiency technologies, the implementation of best available technologies (BAT) in industry, as well as energy management systems and the increase in the share of renewable energy used in the industrial sector through financial support instruments.		x					x	x

Relevant PAMs addressing NMVOC emissions from the agriculture sector

Overall, six Member States are reporting 38 PAMs that are dealing with NMVOC emission reduction within the agricultural sector.

Most relevant objectives in this sector are ‘improved livestock management and rearing installation and ‘other agriculture’ (19 reported PAMs reported by 5 Member States, respectively), followed by the objective ‘Other activities improving cropland management’ (Figure 7.13).

Figure 7.13: Policies and Measures reported by EU Member States for the agriculture sector and the selected objectives.

Note: The number in brackets next to the country name, shows the number of agriculture PAMs reported; AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, FI, FR, GR, HU, IE, IT, LU, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SK and SE are not included as they did not report any PAMs in this category
Source: EEA, 2024d.

Table 7.15 analyses the reported PAMs on a more detailed level by summarising and clustering the actions implemented or planned.

It shows that most Member States, that have reported PAMs in this sector, aim to reduce NMVOC emissions in the agricultural sector by improving the efficiency of fertilizers, capacity building and training programs as well as improvements in livestock management.

Table 7.15: Summary agriculture policies reported by MS addressing NMVOC.

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Improved animal waste management systems	Improved livestock management and rearing installations	Low-emission of application fertilizer/manure on	Other activities improving cropland management	Other agriculture
HR	Croatia's PAMs mainly aim on the covering storage (liquid) manure, education and encouraging agricultural producers, the implementation of measures relating to the reduction of ammonia emissions and the	x	x	x	x	

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Improved animal waste management systems	Improved livestock management and rearing installations	Low-emission application of fertilizer/manure on	Other activities improving cropland management	Other agriculture
	improvement of livestock breeding, livestock production and animal nutrition.					
EE	NMVOE emissions from the agricultural sector in Estonia are tackled by the support for a conversion to organic farming, the cultivation of catch crops, the replacement of mineral fertilizers by organic fertilizers, reconstruction or construction of new livestock facilities and provide investments into renewable energy through investments in bioenergy and promote its production. Additionally, Estonia reports PAMs dealing with the provision of higher economic added value to bio-resources, the increase the number of animals grazed extensively and support of regional soil protection.	x	x	x	x	x
LV	Latvia's reported PAM is aiming on new strategies for capacity building and more efficient performance of the State environmental Service.	x	x		x	x
LT	The countries reported PAMs to reduce NMVOE emissions from the agricultural sector include the promotion of catch crops, financial incentives to produce biogas from livestock and the design of requirements for animal farms regarding available new technical solutions to manage air emissions.	x	x		x	x
SI	The funding of practices directly reducing ammonia emissions, the improvement of efficiency in use of livestock fertilizers and mineral fertilizers as well as the implementation of training programs to reduce ammonia are the main PAMs reported by Slovenia, aiming to reduce NMVOE emissions from the agricultural sector.	x	x	x	x	x
ES	PAMs in Spain, concerning NMVOE emissions in the agricultural sector, include the prevention of open burning of pruning residues from woody crops, the modernization of existing facilities and the renewal of machinery and/or replacement of tractors and seed drills.					x

7.2.4 Reflections on the methodologies used to calculate NMVOC emissions

The NMVOC emissions reported by Member States annually are calculated following the EMEP/EEA Guidebook 2023 (EMEP/EEA, 2023), which specify the methodologies, activity data and emission factors to be applied. Usually there are three tiers (methodologies) provided. An explanation of the different tier methods is already provided in section 7.1.4.

Table 7.16 shows the key categories identified in the EU Informative Inventory Report 2024 (EEA, 2024) for NMVOC stating the share of tiers used. These key categories account for 81% of the overall NMVOC emissions in the EU in 2022. As presented in Table 7.16, 64%-100% of these emissions are calculated with higher tier methods, meaning that country specific circumstances are considered, which leads to more reliable and accurate results.

Table 7.16: Share of higher tiers for NMVOC emissions in the top 5 key categories in the EU in 2022.

Category Name	Share of higher Tier used	Share in EU NMVOC total (2022)
1A4bi Residential: Stationary	98%	15%
2D3a Domestic solvent use including fungicides	100%	12%
2D3d Coating applications	93%	10%
3B1a Manure management - Dairy cattle	99%	8%
3B1b Manure management - Non-dairy cattle	99%	6%
2D3g Chemical products	100%	5%
2D3i Other solvent use (please specify in the IIR)	100%	4%
3De Cultivated crops	95%	4%
2H2 Food and beverages industry	92%	3%
1A3bv Road transport: Gasoline evaporation	100%	2%
3Da2a Animal manure applied to soils	100%	2%
1A3bi Road transport: Passenger cars	100%	2%
2D3h Printing	98%	2%
2D3e Degreasing	95%	1%
3B4gii Manure management - Broilers	100%	1%
1B2av Distribution of oil products	64%	1%

Source of data: EU Member State submissions under the Air Convention from 2024

7.2.5 Outlook on future NMVOC emission trends

Under the NEC Directive, EU Member States are required to report projected air emission data biennially for the years 2020, 2025, 2030 and – where available – also for the years 2040 and 2050, beginning in 2017.

The data used for the assessment below is based on the Member States submissions in 2023. Unfortunately, 9 Member States (Belgium, Cyprus, Ireland, Finland, Hungary, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Italy and Poland) did not provide NMVOC emission data for the year 2020 within their projection submission; this data was gap filled with data provided in their emission inventories as submitted in 2024.

Based on the MS projections, the total NMVOC emissions in the EU are projected to decrease by 11% between 2020 and 2030, under the consideration of policies and measures already implemented (with existing measures = WEM scenario). As many countries did not provide projections considering

additional measures (with additional measures = WAM scenario), an assessment cannot be provided at this level.

From a Member States perspective (see Table 7.17 and Figure 7.14) no major changes are expected regarding the contribution of the Member States to EU total emissions.

Three Member States (Ireland, Luxembourg and Malta) expect increases in NMVOC emissions until the year 2030, mainly in the sectors manufacturing industries – iron and steel, the food and beverages industry, the domestic solvent use, coating applications, printing and the manure management of dairy cattle.

The highest absolute reductions are projected by Italy, mainly influenced by reductions of NMVOC emissions in stationary combustion in the commercial and the residential sectors. Lithuania projects the highest relative reductions (more than 51%).

Figure 7.14: Projected NMVOC emissions from Member States presenting the WEM scenario for the years 2020, 2025 and 2030.

Source of data: EEA, 2024g.

Table 7.17: Share and trend of MSs projected NMVOC emissions (WEM scenario).

	Share in 2020	Share in 2030	Absolute Change 2020-2030	Relative Change 2020-2030
AT	1.7%	1.7%	- 12.09	-10.9%
BE	2.2%	2.0%	- 26.34	-18.8%
BG	1.4%	1.5%	- 4.20	-4.7%
CY	0.1%	0.1%	- 1.64	-19.3%
CZ	4.7%	3.3%	- 112.07	-37.3%
DE	16.3%	18.2%	- 4.05	-0.4%
DK	1.7%	1.9%	- 0.55	-0.5%
ES	8.5%	9.1%	- 20.98	-3.9%
EE	0.4%	0.4%	- 3.06	-12.5%
FI	1.3%	1.3%	- 12.19	-14.4%
FR	14.8%	15.6%	- 53.28	-5.7%
GR	2.2%	2.2%	- 14.13	-10.0%
HR	1.1%	1.1%	- 6.99	-9.9%
HU	1.9%	2.0%	- 8.69	-7.1%
IE	1.8%	2.1%	5.52	5.0%
IT	12.8%	12.1%	- 126.92	-15.6%
LT	0.7%	0.4%	- 24.11	-51.5%
LU	0.1%	0.2%	0.57	6.2%
LV	0.6%	0.6%	- 2.36	-6.6%
MT	0.0%	0.0%	0.06	2.4%
NL	4.3%	4.3%	- 30.64	-11.3%
PL	11.2%	10.9%	- 92.86	-13.0%
PT	2.1%	2.1%	- 15.47	-11.4%
RO	3.8%	2.7%	- 86.93	-36.4%
SK	1.4%	1.5%	- 2.80	-3.2%
SI	0.5%	0.5%	- 3.80	-12.3%
SE	2.2%	2.2%	- 15.50	-11.2%
EU-27	100.0%	100.0%	- 675.49	-10.6%

Source of data: EEA, 2024g.

7.2.6 Relevant policies on EU level and Policy Recommendations

In previous years, the reduction of NMVOC emissions have been addressed by several policies on EU- and global level, that aim on reducing NMVOC emissions either directly or indirectly to lower the formation of ground level ozone.

The **Gothenburg Protocol**⁵³ was adopted in 1999 and amended in 2019, with the main objective to control emissions of sulphur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, ammonia, PM_{2.5} (fine particles) and NMVOCs, which are caused by anthropogenic activities. This includes national reduction commitments to be achieved by 2020 and beyond for the above-mentioned pollutants.

⁽⁵³⁾ [ECE.EB.AIR.114.ENG.pdf](#)

The **Geneva Protocol**⁵⁴, concerning the control of emissions of NMVOCs or their transboundary fluxes was adopted in 1991. It required a 30% reduction in VOCs by 1999, where the base year can be chosen between 1984 and 1990.

The **NEC Directive**⁵⁵ sets emission reduction commitments into force for five important pollutants - including NMVOC emissions - for each Member State. The reduction commitments are aligned with the ones defined in the Gothenburg Protocol.

The **revised Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive (IED 2.0)**⁵⁶ aims to prevent industrial pollution from harming health and environment and applies to industrial plants as well as to intensive pig and poultry farms. The directive promotes and facilitates investments into innovative and transformative techniques (e.g. Best Available Techniques).

To limit the content of VOCs in paints, varnishes and vehicle refinishing products, the **paints directive**⁵⁷ was introduced. It provides the technical specifications for certain paints, to achieve a reduction in NMVOC emissions in the EU.

The reduction of NMVOC is addressed through a variety of specific sectors but also general plans and policies. Much progress has been achieved in previous years in the road transport sector and in the use of solvents due to the implementation of several programmes. In other areas, such as the residential heating, further decrease in NMVOC emissions can be accomplished by continuously improvement of heating systems and investments in more sustainable technologies (Table 7.18).

Table 7.18: Potential solutions to substantial reduction of NMVOC emissions.

Source of NMVOC Emissions	End of Pipe - Solution	Transformative Solution
Residential heating	Maintenance and exchange of old heating devices; shift to fuels with less NMVOC emissions (e.g. natural gas)	Change heating systems (e.g. renewable energy, extension of district heating systems...), renovation of buildings
Solvent use	Promotion of the production of products (paints) with low content of organic solvents	Shift to best available technologies in industrial plants
Manure management	Changes in feeding techniques, silage management, improvement in manure management during livestock housing and storage	Minimise consumption of meat and dairy products

7.3 Nitrogen oxide (NO_x)

NO_x is one of the main precursors of ground-level ozone and comprises two gases: nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). The main anthropogenic sources are related to fuel combustion from fuel bound nitrogen and thermally produced NO_x at high temperatures. Besides that, the production and application of nitrogen fertilizer, and N-fixing crops contribute to NO_x releases to the atmosphere. Natural sources include lightnings in the upper troposphere and microbial activity soils.

⁽⁵⁴⁾ Geneva Protocol: <https://unece.org/environment-policy/air/protocol-concerning-control-emissions-volatile-organic-compounds>

⁽⁵⁵⁾ Directive (EU) 2016/2284: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/2284/oj>

⁽⁵⁶⁾ Directive 2010/75/EU: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/75/2024-08-04>

⁽⁵⁷⁾ Directive 2004/42/EC: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2004/42/2021-07-16>

7.3.1 Trends by Member States

Among other pollutants, Member States of the EU are obliged to reduce their NO_x emissions under the NEC Directive. In the EU, NO_x emissions decreased between 1990 and 2022 by 64% (from 15,102kt NO_x in 1990 to 5,395kt NO_x in 2022).

The emission trend on EU levels is mainly influenced by France, Germany, Italy and Spain (see Figure 7.15), who contributed most to the total emission reductions over the time period, but all Member States reduced their NO_x emissions since 1990 (see Table 7.19).

Figure 7.15: Trend of NO_x emissions across EU Member States from 1990-2022

Note: the figure displays the 10 biggest contributors to NO_x emissions in the EU. 'Other' sums up all other remaining EU countries; please see Annex 1 to this report for the whole dataset
Source of data: EU submission under the Air convention, Annex I (EEA, 2024e).

Table 7.19: Information on trend and share of NO_x emissions of EU Member States.

	Share in 1990	Share in 2005	Share in 2022	Absolute Change 1990-2022 [kt]	Relative Change 1990-2022	Trend 1990-2022
AT	1.4%	2.3%	2.1%	- 101.75	-47.1%	
BE	2.8%	3.1%	2.5%	- 295.04	-69.0%	
BG	2.0%	1.7%	1.8%	- 198.69	-67.4%	
CY	0.1%	0.2%	0.2%	- 5.98	-33.4%	
CZ	5.0%	2.9%	2.9%	- 600.25	-79.4%	
DE	18.8%	14.9%	17.5%	- 1 900.28	-66.9%	
DK	2.0%	1.9%	1.6%	- 209.07	-70.7%	
ES	0.5%	0.4%	0.4%	- 51.29	-68.6%	
EE	8.7%	12.3%	10.9%	- 724.15	-55.2%	
FI	2.0%	1.9%	1.8%	- 207.48	-67.6%	
FR	14.4%	15.0%	12.9%	- 1 479.60	-68.0%	
GR	2.7%	4.5%	4.3%	- 177.36	-43.2%	
HR	0.7%	0.8%	0.8%	- 57.16	-55.5%	
HU	1.6%	1.7%	1.9%	- 143.52	-58.7%	
IE	1.1%	1.6%	1.8%	- 72.71	-43.5%	
IT	14.1%	12.1%	11.5%	- 1 504.50	-70.8%	
LT	1.0%	0.6%	0.9%	- 104.02	-67.8%	
LU	0.3%	0.5%	0.2%	- 29.39	-71.9%	
LV	0.7%	0.4%	0.6%	- 65.96	-66.9%	
MT	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	- 2.51	-34.7%	
NL	4.5%	4.0%	3.6%	- 486.56	-71.4%	
PL	7.4%	7.9%	9.8%	- 588.38	-52.7%	
PT	1.7%	2.6%	2.5%	- 123.78	-47.6%	
RO	3.1%	3.1%	3.8%	- 267.77	-56.9%	
SK	1.9%	1.8%	2.1%	- 178.01	-61.5%	
SI	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%	- 49.77	-66.0%	
SE	0.9%	1.0%	1.0%	- 81.86	-60.0%	
EU-27	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	- 9 706.97	-64.3%	

In the following table the emission trends of countries with a specifically high decrease (in absolute terms) and the underlying reasons are described in more detail:

Countries with substantial decreases
<p>Germany (-67%; -1 900kt NO_x)</p> <p>Germany achieved the largest reduction in NO_x emissions in category 1.A.3.b.i – Road Transport: Passenger cars and 1.A.3.b.iii – Heavy Duty vehicles, due to constantly improving fuels, the use of catalytic converters and increasingly stricter regulations resulting in technical improvements. The long-term trend in category 1.A.1.a – Public electricity and heat production is also decreasing, mainly influenced by the declining consumption of lignite in the early nineties and the decrease of hard coal consumption from 2014 onwards (DE IIR 2024).</p>
<p>France (-68%; -1 480kt NO_x)</p> <p>In France, the substantial decreases of NO_x emissions were achieved mainly in categories 1.A.1.a – Public electricity and heat production and 1.A.3–Road transport due to the installation of catalytic purification systems, structural changes in the energy mix (e.g. nuclear power program) and the improvement of industrial facilities. Additionally, European emission standards⁵⁸ were introduced,</p>

⁽⁵⁸⁾ Directive 98/69/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1998/69/oj/eng>; Directive 2005/55/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32005L0055>; Directive 2005/78/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32005L0078>;

Countries with substantial decreases

setting the maximum pollutant emission limits for road vehicles and led to a renewal of the vehicle fleet (FR IIR 2024).

Italy (-71%; -1 505kt NO_x)

Reductions in NO_x emissions between the years 1990 and 2022 in Italy are mainly driven by reductions in the transport sector (-79% in category 1.A.3.b.i and -75% in category 1.A.3.b.iii). This decrease has been achieved by the introduction of catalytic converters to reduce vehicle emissions provided by European Directives⁵⁹ and subsequent modifications and integrations. Additionally, policies to further encourage the reduction of NO_x emission, such as incentives to renew the public and private fleet, the purchase of electric vehicles, promotion for the expansion of rail, maritime and urban transport systems and programmes for sustainable mobility, have been introduced.

NO_x emissions from category 1A1a –Public electricity and heat production have decreased by 93% between 1990 and 2022 due to the conversion of the use of natural gas instead of fuel oil as well as a significant reduction in the use of coal fuels for energy production. More stringent emission limits for new plants, incentives for the improvement of energy efficiency and the promotion of renewable energy and energy savings have led to further reductions in this sector (IT IIR 2024).

7.3.2 Trends by Categories

The main sources of NO_x emissions in the EU originate from the transport sector, followed by fuel combustion activities in the energy sector. The share of total NO_x emissions from these sectors decreased from 52% in 1990 to 47% in 2022. This was influenced by the harmonized application of Euro emission standards in the road transport sector⁶⁰, which led to the introduction of improved exhaust emission controls, the progressive introduction of abatement technologies and technology shifts in industrial plants as well as the shift from solid or liquid fuels to gaseous fuels in public electricity and heat production.

⁽⁵⁹⁾ Directive 91/441/EC <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/1991/441/oj> and Directive 94/12/EC (<http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/1994/12/oj>)

⁽⁶⁰⁾ Directive 98/69/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1998/69/oj/eng>; Directive 2005/55/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32005L0055>; Directive 2005/78/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32005L0078>

Figure 7.16: Trend of NO_x emissions per sector 1990-2022.

Source of data: EEA, 2024e.

Table 7.20: Trend and share of sectors contributing to EU total NO_x emissions.

	Share in 1990	Share in 2005	Share in 2022	Absolute Change 1990-2022 [kt NMVOC]	Relative Change 1990-2022	Trend 1990-2022
Energy Industries (1A1)	22.2%	18.8%	14.1%	- 2 592	-77.4%	
Energy consumption (1A2, 1A4, 1A5 - excl. mobile)	16.4%	16.6%	20.9%	- 1 351	-54.5%	
Transport (1A3, 1A4, 1A5)	52.0%	54.2%	47.6%	- 5 287	-67.3%	
Fugitive Emissions (1B)	0.2%	0.3%	0.4%	- 16	-42.5%	
Industrial Processes (2)	2.2%	2.4%	2.6%	- 192	-57.8%	
Manure Management (3B)	0.4%	0.4%	0.8%	- 18	-30.6%	
Other Agriculture (3C-3J)	6.2%	6.7%	12.3%	- 267	-28.7%	
Waste (5)	0.4%	0.5%	1.4%	- 16	27.6%	
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	- 9 707	-64.3%	

Source of data: EEA, 2024e.

In 2022, the trend of NO_x emissions was still dominated by the transport sector, in particular categories 1A3bi–Road transport: passenger cars and 1A3biii–Road transport: Heavy duty vehicles and buses.

Table 7.21 displays the categories where the highest absolute changes – decreases or increases, occurred, and list the number of countries for which the category is among the top 3.

The analysis shows that in all countries NO_x emissions from category 1A3bi are decreasing, while category 1A3biii is under the top 3 most relevant categories for an increase in emissions in Poland and Romania. Luxembourg is the only Member State that reported increasing NO_x emissions in public electricity and heat production.

Table 7.21: Most relevant categories in Member States for increasing and decreasing NO_x emissions.

	Number of Member States, where the category is among the top 3 increasing categories	Number of Member States, where the category is among the top 3 decreasing categories
Road transport: passenger cars	0	22
Road transport: Heavy duty vehicles and buses	2	19
Public electricity and heat production	1	19

7.3.3 Analysis of relevant policies and measures at MS level

As already discussed in section 7.2.3, Member States are required to report on their policies and measures, according to the NEC Directive. Article 6 of the Directive sets out the obligation for Member States to draw, adopt and implement their respective NAPCP including their selected policies and measures, in order to fulfil their emission reduction commitments.

Policies and measures, contained in the NAPCP must be updated within 18 months of the submission of the latest national emission inventory or national emission projections.

To assess to what extent policies and measures that had impact on NO_x emissions are included, only measures which are targeting NO_x are selected. In total 467 measures out of 809, target NO_x alone or a combination of other air pollutants including NO_x (see Figure 7.17). When NO_x among other pollutants is targeted, PAMs target mostly the transport sector, followed by energy consumption and energy supply. If the PAM only addresses NO_x, the transport sector is the most targeted sector, which is the major emitting source of this pollutant.

Figure 7.17: PAMs addressing NO_x emissions per sector.

For a further analysis on Member State level, the relevant policies are identified by the selected objectives per transport and energy sector. Policies and measures, which seem to be especially relevant regarding their potential impact, are described in more detail, clearly demonstrating the linkage to reducing the greenhouse gas carbon dioxide, primarily from fuel combustion.

Relevant PAMs addressing NO_x emissions from the transport sector

In transport sector, the objective ‘demand management/reduction’ is most relevant. It has been selected in 94 PAMs reported by 19 Member States. 90 PAMs (reported by 10 Member States) followed by the objective ‘alternative fuels for vehicles, vessels and aircrafts (including electric)’, which has been addressed in 82 PAMs, selected by 19 Member States (Figure 7.18).

Technical abatement solutions like selective catalytic reduction (e.g. by using AdBlue) and Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR) are standard technologies, which might be the reason why countries hardly report PAMs related to the deployment of pollution prevention technologies. It is the objective the least selected.

Figure 7.18: Policies and Measures reported by EU Member States for the transport sector and the selected objectives.

Note: The number in brackets next to the country code, shows the number of transport PAMs reported; AT, BG, CY, FI, FR, LU and NL are not included as they did not report any PAMs in this category
Source: EEA, 2024d.

Table 7.22 analyses the reported PAMs on a more detailed level by summarising and clustering the most promising actions implemented or planned. It becomes then visible that most Member States take measures to introduce alternative fuels, promote the shift to public transportation and manage and/or reduce the demand of fossil fuels.

Table 7.22: Summary of transport policies reported by MS addressing NO_x.

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Demand management/reduction	Improved behaviour	Alternative fuels for vehicles, vessels and aircraft (including electric)	Modal shift to public transport or non-motorised transport	Deployment of pollution abatement technologies on vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Other transport	Efficiency improvements of vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Improved transport infrastructure	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels
BE	Belgium's PAMs regarding NO _x emissions in the transport sector are including the gradual ban on most polluting vehicles, deployment of electric vehicles through incentives, the conversion of public buses to electric or hybrid vehicles and the establishment of charging points for electric vehicles.		x	x			x		x	
HR	Croatia reported to implement research to identify cost-effective measures with a positive impact on economic development, employment and research for best available techniques and good practices as well as the integration of emission reduction activities in areas where air quality has been impaired.	x		x		x		x		x
CZ	A National Recovery Plan is in place that finances support for the acquisition of alternatively powered vehicles for municipalities and regions and organisations established by them.			x						
EE	Estonia submitted a series of PAMs, including activities to develop convenient and modern public transport (e.g. additional passenger trains, new trams, domestic ferries), promotion of biomethane and increase of share of biofuels, the promotion of the use of electricity in passenger cars and buses as well as the improvement of the efficiency in the transport system.	x	x	x	x			x	x	
DE	PAMs reported aim to increase the share of electrical mileage until 2030 significantly.			x			x			
GR	Greece PAMs concerning NO _x emissions, include the fleet replacement with vehicles of low emissions and high energy efficiency, the improvement of public transport and the railroad infrastructure, the promotion of alternative fuels,			x	x		x		x	

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Demand management/reduction	Improved behaviour	Alternative fuels for vehicles, vessels and aircraft (including electric)	Modal shift to public transport or non-motorised transport	Deployment of pollution abatement technologies on vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Other transport	Efficiency improvements of vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Improved transport infrastructure	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels
	electromobility and the implementation of CO ₂ emission ceilings for automobile manufactures.									
HU	Information campaigns on transport related health effects, energy- and cost saving ways of car usage and benefits of alternative transport (e.g. electric vehicles, public transport) as well as the promotion of the usage of low/zero emission vehicles and the revision of environmental classification system for motor vehicles are reported PAMs by Hungary.	x	x	x	x			x		
IE	The Electric Vehicle Deployment Programme by SEAI (Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland) is an initiative aimed at promoting the adoption and deployment of electric vehicles (EVs) in Ireland. The program provides financial incentives and support to individuals, businesses, and public sector organizations for the purchase of EVs, including cars, vans, and bikes. Additionally, the program supports the development of public charging infrastructure, offering grants for the installation of EV charging points.			x						
IT	Italy addresses NO _x emissions in the transport sector by the improvement of local public transport (e.g. low emission vehicles, modal shift, fiscal incentives, shared mobility, smart parking and smart working), the promotion of Intelligence Transport Systems (ITS) for duty vehicles and promotion of the use of electric vehicles, the transposition of the RED II directive ⁶¹ and the support to local initiatives aimed to reduce the circulation of more polluting vehicles in urban areas.	x		x	x			x		

⁶¹ Directive (EU) 2018/2001: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/2001/oj>

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Demand management/reduction	Improved behaviour	Alternative fuels for vehicles, vessels and aircraft (including electric)	Modal shift to public transport or non-motorised transport	Deployment of pollution abatement technologies on vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Other transport	Efficiency improvements of vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Improved transport infrastructure	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels
LT	<p>Lithuania plans to reduce the use of fossil fuels by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Promoting alternative fuels -Promoting the purchase of clean heavy vehicles -Promoting the use of electric vehicles -Creation of public transport charging and/or recharging infrastructure -Renewal of transport fleet through green procurement -Promotion of sustainable mobility -Eco-friendly driving -Development of green hydrogen production -Electrification of railways -Sustainable airport infrastructure -Campaigns to inform the public -Sustainable urban mobility 	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
MT	<p>Malta plans to address NO_x emissions in the transport sector by the increase of Intelligent Transport systems in traffic management, free public transport fares for youth, students and elderly population, incentives for more efficient internal combustion engines, infrastructure interventions (e.g. smart parking systems, reform in public service garages, development of a bicycle strategy), the introduction of electric vehicles such as busses, taxis, Government fleet and a car sharing scheme.</p>	x	x	x	x		x			
PL	<p>Poland reports PAMs on the development of low- and zero-carbon collective transport, road transport infrastructure, electromobility, energy efficiency and emission level of vehicles and the promotion of biofuel use.</p>	x		x	x	x			x	

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Demand management/reduction	Improved behaviour	Alternative fuels for vehicles, vessels and aircraft (including electric)	Modal shift to public transport or non-motorised transport	Deployment of pollution abatement technologies on vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Other transport	Efficiency improvements of vehicles, vessels and aircraft	Improved transport infrastructure	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels
RO	Romania's PAMs regarding NO _x emissions in the transport sector are including the development of green public transport, electric public transport routes, the improvement of primary and secondary road connectivity and increasing the attractiveness of rail passenger transport (including the development of urban railway systems and increasing the efficiency of the Romanian railways).				x		x	x	x	
SK	The PAM reported by Slovakia aims to replace an average 2016 diesel vehicle (a weighted average of diesels in the fleet in 2016) with either a battery electric vehicle (BEV) with a plug-in hybrid electric vehicle (PHEV) or other alternatively fuel vehicles			x						
SI	Additional funds for railway infrastructure, additional improvement of public transport, additional support to cycling and walking, additional measures for promoting electric mobility are planned to be introduced by Slovenia.	x	x	x				x	x	
ES	Spain plans to promote more efficient modes and car fleet renovation, the introduction of advanced biofuels, the promotion of electric vehicles and the provision of charging stations for alternative fuels.	x		x	x		x	x		

Relevant PAMs addressing NO_x emissions from the energy sector

Within the energy sector, energy consumption and energy supply are most relevant regarding policies and measures addressing NO_x emissions.

Overall, in both energy supply and energy consumption sector, the objectives 'Demand management/reduction' (94 PAMs) and 'Increase in renewable energy' (61 PAMs) are the most important ones (Figure 7.19).

Similar to the transport sector, PAMs addressing the installation of abatement technologies are less relevant. This can be explained because the use of EGR to reduce thermal NO_x formation, as well as

the selective catalytic reduction (SCR) and selective non-catalytic reduction (SNCR), are already standard technologies in industrial installations having remarkable contributed to historical NO_x emission reduction and are now less relevant.

Figure 7.19: Policies and Measures reported by EU Member States for the sector energy supply and energy consumption and the selected objectives.

Note: The number in brackets next to the country name, shows the number of energy PAMs reported; AT, BG, CY, DK, FI, FR, LU, NL and SE are not included as they did not report any PAMs in this category
 Source: EEA, 2024d.

Table 7.23 provides an analysis on reported PAMs in a more detailed level by summarising and clustering the most promising actions implemented or planned by Member States. It becomes then visible that most Member States take measures to improve energy efficiency in appliances and buildings and manage and/or reduce the demand of fossil solid fuels. It should be noted that also the combustion of biomass results in NO_x emissions, although in a lower extent compared to coal.

Table 7.23: Summary of energy supply and consumption policies reported by MS addressing NO_x.

Summary of relevant policies and measures per country		Increase in renewable energy	Switch to less carbon-intensive fuels	Efficiency improvement in the energy and transformation sector	Reduction of losses	Enhanced non-renewable low carbon generation	Demand management/reduction	Efficiency improvements of buildings	Efficiency improvement of appliances	Efficiency improvement in services/tertiary sector	Installation of abatement technologies
BE	Belgium's PAMs of the energy sector aim to support renewable electricity production, improving energy efficiency, strengthening emission limits for combustion plants, tax regime for buildings to provide price signals consistent with the polluter-pays principle and renovation strategy for public, private, residential, and non-residential buildings.	x	x					x	x	x	
HR	Croatia reported to implement research to identify cost-effective measures with a positive impact on economic development, employment and research for best available techniques and good practice as well as the integration of emission reduction measures for pollutants within planning documents and projects for energy renewal of buildings						x	x	x		
CY	Research should help identify cost-effective measures, measures that have a positive impact on economic development, employment, research that help transfer knowledge about best available techniques and good practice.	x	x	x							x
CZ	Czechia's PAMs mainly aim on the efficient use of natural gas networks with emphasis on decarbonised fuels, limiting power and heat losses during transmission and distribution, reducing the share of solid fossil fuels in primary energy sources, increasing energy efficiency on the consumption side, priority use of waste heat and the expansion of the use of non-combustion Renewable Energy Sources.	x	x		x		x	x	x		

EE	Estonia reported a set of PAMs addressing NO _x reduction in the energy sector, including energy efficiency in buildings (e.g. residential investment fund, reconstruction of buildings, Kindergarten renovation), renovation of district heating boilers and fuel change, energy and resource efficiency in industries, renewable energy support (wind parks, solar energy) and renovation of depreciated and inefficient heat pipelines.	x	x	x	x		x	x			
DE	Germany's PAMs mainly focus on the phase-out of coal-fired power generation and the switch to less carbon intensive fuels.	x	x								x
GR	Greece reported to implement the improvement of energy efficiency, an increase of natural gas usage in the industry and the domestic tertiary sector as well as an increase of RES in the electricity production industry.	x	x		x	x	x	x	x		x
HU	Hungary's reported PAM aims to help improve and upgrade the energy efficiency of buildings by replacing doors and windows, using thermal insulation, using renewable energy sources through subsidies and regulatory incentives and to start an ESCO (Energy Services Company) program for private customers with limited investment opportunities.							x			
IE	Ireland's PAMs for NO _x emissions deal with the efficiency improvements of appliances (heat pumps, better energy homes, smart meter roll out), the increase of renewable energy (e.g. solar power) and carbon taxes.	x	x				x	x			
IT	Italy addresses NO _x emissions in the energy sector by the promotion of energy efficiency in buildings and heating/cooling systems, the promotion of behavioural changes (education, smart meters), energy efficiency in new buildings, fiscal incentives for renovation, promotions of renewable energy (biomass) and the phase out of electricity production by burning coal.	x					x	x	x	x	
LV	Latvia's reported PAMs include new emission limit values set for small and medium combustion plants and a financial support programme, which includes a fiscal policy (e.g. real estate tax credits) for households to promote the connection to central heating systems and the extension of district heating networks.	x		x			x	x			

LT	Lithuania reported PAMs to reduce NO _x emissions from the energy sector include RES and the deployment of alternative fuels, emission limits for small combustion plants, renovation and modernization of buildings, replacement of heating systems and boilers with more efficient technologies and reduction of tax benefits for solid fossil fuels.	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
MT	Malta plans to address NO _x emissions in the energy sector by electricity tariffs, biofuels substitution obligations, financial support for solar PVs and solar water heater schemes.	x	x				x	x			
PL	Poland plans to implement priority programmes in energy and district heating, an update of requirements for solid fuel boilers, support renewable energy (e.g. offshore wind) and nuclear power generation and the improvement of the building energy efficiency system.	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	x
PT	Portugal's PAMs include the promotion of the network development for alternative fuel stations and an increasing energy efficiency.		x				x				
RO	Romania is reporting PAMs mainly focusing on the promotion of renewable energy sources (solar panels, heat pumps), the establishment of centralized thermal energy supply systems, the expansion of the gas transmission and distribution network, the improvement and information campaigns to increase energy efficiency.	x		x			x	x	x		
SK	Slovakia's reported PAMs in the energy sector are dealing with the connection of households to district heating systems, thermal insulations of residential buildings and the transition of solid fuel heating systems to other low emission systems.	x			x		x	x	x		
SI	To reduce NO _x emissions, Slovenia plans to implement additional funds available for industry, improvements in the building sector (e.g. banning of fuel oil in new buildings, setup of sustainability criteria for buildings, allocation of additional funds for renovation of buildings, etc.), increased production of electricity and heat from renewable sources and the replacement of old wood boilers.	x	x			x					

ES	Spain addresses NO _x emissions in the energy sector by the promotion of renewable and alternative gases, Technology renewal plan for existing renewable power generation projects, promotion of energy efficiency in the building sector, incentives programmes for installations in buildings or heating networks, the development of green hydrogen and demand and flexibility management.	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
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7.3.4 Reflections on the methodologies used to calculate NO_x emissions

The annual report of NO_x emissions by Member States is calculated following the EMEP/EEA Guidebook 2023 (EMEP/EEA, 2023), which specifies application of methodologies, activity data and emission factors. Usually there are three tiers (methodologies) provided. An explanation of the different tier methods is already provided in section 77.1.4.

Table 7.24 shows the key categories identified in the EU Informative Inventory Report 2024 (EEA, 2024) for NO_x stating the share of tiers used. These key categories account for 81% of the overall NO_x emissions in the EU in 2022. 81%-100% of these emissions are calculated with higher tier methods, meaning that country specific circumstances are considered, which leads to more reliable and accurate results. Only one category – 3Da1 Inorganic fertilizers – which contribute 7% to the total NO_x emissions in the EU, is calculated mainly with a tier 1 methodology.

Table 7.24: Share of higher tiers for NO_x emissions for the EU key categories in 2022.

Category Name	Share of higher Tier used	Share in EU NO _x total (2022)
1A3bi Road transport: Passenger cars	100%	18%
1A1a Public electricity and heat production	100%	11%
1A3biii Road transport: Heavy duty vehicles and buses	100%	11%
1A3bii Road transport: Light duty vehicles	100%	7%
3Da1 Inorganic N-fertilizers (includes also urea application)	4%	7%
1A4bi Residential: Stationary	99%	6%
1A3dii National navigation (shipping)	81%	5%
1A4cii Agriculture/Forestry/Fishing: Off-road vehicles and other machinery	95%	4%
3Da2a Animal manure applied to soils	100%	4%
1A2f Stationary combustion in manufacturing industries and construction: Non-metallic minerals	85%	3%
1A2gviii Stationary combustion in manufacturing industries and construction: Other	94%	3%
1A4ai Commercial/Institutional: Stationary	94%	2%
3Da3 Urine and dung deposited by grazing animals	73%	2%

7.3.5 Outlook on future NO_x emission trends

As indicated in section 7.2.5, under the NEC Directive, EU Member States are required to report projected air emission data biennially for the years 2020, 2025, 2030 and – where available – also for the years 2040 and 2050, beginning in 2017.

Based on the MS projections, the total NO_x emissions in the EU are projected to decrease by almost 30.9% between 2020 and 2030, under the consideration of policies and measures already implemented (with existing measures = WEM scenario). As many countries did not provide projections considering additional measures (with additional measures = WAM scenario), an assessment cannot be provided at this level. The data used for this assessment is based on the Member States submissions in 2023.

From a Member States perspective (see Table 7.25 and Figure 7.20) no major changes are expected regarding the contribution of the Member States to EU total emissions. Only two Member States (Malta⁶² and Romania) foresee an increase in NO_x emissions. Romania expects increases in NO_x emissions until the year 2030, mainly in the transport sector (Road transport: Passenger cars - 1A3bi, Light duty vehicles - 1A3bii, Heavy duty vehicles and buses - 1A3biii).

The highest absolute reductions are projected by Germany, mainly influenced by reductions of NO_x emissions in the electricity and heat production and the transport sector. Lithuania projects the highest relative reductions (44%).

Figure 7.20: Projected NO_x emissions from Member States presenting the WEM scenario for the years 2020, 2025 and 2030.

Source of data: EEA, 2024g.

⁶² For this assessment, the projections submitted by Malta under the LRTAP convention in 2023 have been considered, which were the latest at the time of writing the report. In 2026, Malta submitted updated projections which indicate that Malta will reduce its NO_x emissions by 2030.

Table 7.25: Share and trend of MSs projected NO_x emissions (WEM scenario).

	Share in 2020	Share in 2030	Absolute Change 2020-2030	Relative Change 2020-2030
AT	2.3%	2.1%	- 45.65	-36.7%
BE	2.6%	2.9%	- 32.26	-22.7%
BG	1.6%	1.8%	- 15.52	-18.1%
CY	0.2%	0.2%	- 4.32	-35.7%
CZ	2.7%	2.4%	- 58.13	-39.1%
DE	17.8%	15.8%	- 381.06	-38.8%
DK	1.7%	1.5%	- 35.88	-38.9%
ES	10.3%	10.2%	- 183.06	-32.1%
EE	0.4%	0.5%	- 3.54	-15.2%
FI	1.9%	1.8%	- 38.17	-36.2%
FR	13.1%	12.5%	- 245.06	-34.0%
GR	4.1%	4.0%	- 72.64	-32.3%
HR	0.8%	1.0%	- 5.24	-11.7%
HU	2.0%	2.5%	- 11.37	-10.6%
IE	1.7%	1.7%	- 28.19	-29.8%
IT	10.6%	10.2%	- 197.73	-33.8%
LT	1.0%	0.8%	- 23.49	-44.1%
LU	0.3%	0.2%	- 6.39	-43.1%
LV	0.6%	0.7%	- 5.36	-15.9%
MT	0.1%	0.1%	0.04	0.9%
NL	3.8%	3.9%	- 64.89	-30.7%
PL	10.7%	11.5%	- 154.74	-26.1%
PT	2.4%	2.2%	- 50.50	-37.9%
RO	3.7%	5.6%	5.13	2.5%
SK	1.0%	1.3%	- 5.16	-9.1%
SI	0.5%	0.6%	- 4.13	-16.2%
SE	2.1%	2.1%	- 36.04	-31.3%
EU-27	100.0%	100.0%	- 1 703.34	-30.9%

Source of data: EEA, 2024g.

7.3.6 Relevant policies on EU level and Policy Recommendations

Similar to NMVOC emissions (see section 7.2.6), the reduction of NO_x emissions has been addressed in several policies on both the EU and global levels to lower the formation on ground level ozone.

The **Sofia Protocol**⁶³, concerning the control of emissions of Nitrogen Oxides or their transboundary fluxes was adopted in 1988. Parties are requested to introduce pollution control measures for major existing stationary sources and to apply national emissions standards to major new stationary and mobile sources, based on best available technologies that are economically feasible, where 1987 is the general reference year.

⁶³ Sofia Protocol: https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2021-10/1988.NOX_e.pdf

As outlined in section 7.2.6, the **Gothenburg Protocol** was adopted in 1999 and amended in 2019, with the main objective to control emissions of sulphur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, ammonia, PM_{2.5} (fine particles) and NMVOCs, which are caused by anthropogenic activities. This includes national reduction commitments to be achieved by 2020 and beyond for the above-mentioned pollutants.

The **NEC Directive**⁶⁴ sets emission reduction commitments into force for five important pollutants - including NO_x emissions - for each Member State. The reduction commitments are aligned with the ones defined in the Gothenburg Protocol.

The **revised Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive (IED 2.0)**⁶⁵ aims to prevent industrial pollution from harming health and environment and applies to industrial plants as well as to intensive pig and poultry farms. The directive promotes and facilitates investments into innovative and transformative techniques (e.g. Best Available Techniques).

The **MCP Directive** (limitation of emissions of certain pollutants into the air from medium combustion plants)⁶⁶ lays down rules to control air emissions of SO₂, NO_x and dust from medium combustion plants and defines emission limit values.

To reduce air emissions from road transportation, **European emission standards**⁶⁷ were introduced, setting the maximum pollutant emission limits for road vehicles⁶⁸.

The reduction of NO_x is addressed through a variety of sector specific but also general plans and policies. Much progress has been achieved in previous years in the road transport sector and the energy sector. Further reductions in NO_x emissions can be accomplished by a further shift from the combustion of fossil fuels for energy production to renewable energy sources, while noting that biomass combustion also generates NO_x emissions, and by reducing fossil fuel-based motorised transport (Table 7.26).

Table 7.26: Potential solutions to substantial reduction of NO_x emissions.

Source of NO _x Emissions	End of Pipe - Solution	Transformative Solution
Electricity and heat production/Industrial installations	Use of abatement technologies, such as Selective non catalytic reduction/Selective catalytic reduction (SNCR/SCR) Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR).	Shift from the combustion of fossil fuels to renewable energy sources
Road Transport	Use of abatement technologies, such as SCR and EGR	Limit fossil fuel-based transport; promotion of electric vehicles; reduce need for individual motorized transport, expansion of public transport

⁶⁴ Directive (EU) 2016/2284: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/2284/oj>

⁶⁵ Directive 2010/75/EU: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/75/2024-08-04>

⁶⁶ Directive (EU) 2015/2193 <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2015/2193/oj>

⁶⁷ Directive 98/69/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1998/69/oj/eng>; Directive 2005/55/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32005L0055>; Directive 2005/78/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32005L0078>;

⁶⁸ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/comparison-of-nox-emission-standards?activeTab=570bee2d-1316-48cf-adde-4b640f92119b>

7.4 Comparison of reported inventory data with national emissions available in EDGAR

According to the UNFCCC, Parties are required to report on their national GHG emissions, and under the UNECE Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution, specifically the Gothenburg Protocol, Parties are required to report on their air pollutants. The EU as a Party to both, has transposed these commitments in EU legislation, the EU Energy Governance Regulation for GHGs and the NEC Directive for air pollutants. Hence, national inventories from all EU Member States are reported annually to the European Commission via EIONET data flows. The data are collected and quality checked by the EEA and its ETCs, and publicly accessible. But there are also other data sources for GHGs and air pollutant emission estimates, one of them is the EDGAR database⁶⁹ (Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research) developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. EDGAR provides independent emission estimates compared to what reported by European Member States or by Parties under the UNFCCC, using international statistics and a consistent IPCC methodology. EDGAR provides both emissions as national totals and grid maps at 0.1° x 0.1° resolution at global level, with yearly, monthly and up to hourly data.

The national inventories are primarily used to monitor progress in achieving emission reduction targets, while EDGAR is often used by the international research community, as it has a world-wide coverage, applying a consistent approach across all countries, covers emissions from 1970 onwards and provides a spatial distribution of emissions. Such data bases are needed for integrated assessment modelling to develop future emission scenarios under the consideration of different policy options. Historical emissions are used to calibrate the models.

In Figure 7.21 to Figure 7.26, the differences in total national CH₄, NO_x and NMVOC emissions for the year 2022 and the relative change between 1990 and 2022 is displayed.

The main discrepancies, which are sometimes considerable, are mainly linked to three sectors, namely fugitive emissions, agriculture, and waste. Several factors contribute to these differences (Banja, 2025a, Banja, 2025b and Lamb, 2025), including:

- Timing – The comparison depends on the versions of EDGAR and national inventories used, as updates in activity data occur at different points in time.
- Methodologies – EDGAR primarily applies Tier 1 methods, with some Tier 2 elements, while national inventories may use more advanced tiers (Tier 2/Tier 3)
- Quality of reporting – In some cases, sectoral fuel allocations (the activity data) in UNFCCC submissions differ from those found in the EDGAR main data sources.
- Emission factors – Many EU countries, especially those with more detailed inventories, use country-specific emission factors as part of higher tiers methodologies.
- Underlying uncertainties – When comparing EDGAR emission estimates and national GHG inventories, it must be considered that uncertainty in EDGAR emission estimates are higher for CH₄ and N₂O than for CO₂. Generally, CO₂ emission estimates are based on more reliable data sources than CH₄ and N₂O.

⁽⁶⁹⁾ <https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

Figure 7.21: Total NMVOC emissions for the year 2022 with data from EDGAR and National Inventories.

Source of data: EEA, 2024e; JRC, 2024c.

Figure 7.22: Relative change in total NMVOC emissions between 1990 and 2022 with data from EDGAR and National Inventories.

Source of data: EEA, 2024e; JRC, 2024c.

In 2017, a disaggregation of the NMVOC emission data contained in the EDGAR database was carried out, providing now spatialized emissions for NMVOCs species and species groups (such as Alkanols, ethane, propane, butanes, pentanes, etc.) as included in Annex VII of the revised AAQD by applying region- and source-specific NMVOC speciation profiles. This improvement is essential for assessing the effectiveness of potential air pollution control strategies and policies, because then the chemical transformation of different NMVOC species can be simulated (Huang et al, 2017). The main source for NMVOC emissions is the production and use of solvents reported in the sector industry. Tier 1 calculations are based on per capita emission factors, while higher tier method consider production, import/exports and consumption leading to more accurate results. The observed differences are mainly attributed to NMVOC emissions from the industry sector.

Figure 7.23: Total CH₄ emissions for the year 2022 with data from EDGAR and National Inventories.

Source of data: EEA, 2024c; JRC, 2024a.

Figure 7.24: Relative change in total CH₄ emissions between 1990 and 2022 with data from EDGAR and National Inventories.

Source of data: EEA, 2024c; JRC, 2024a.

Regarding differences in methane emissions, it must be noted that emissions from wetlands are considered in national inventories only if it is considered managed land. The same applies to emissions from fire associated with anthropogenic activities (Lamb et al., 2025). All emissions associated with unmanaged land are not accounted for in the national inventories.

Figure 7.25: Total NO_x emissions for the year 2022 with data from EDGAR and National Inventories.

Source of data: EEA, 2024c; JRC, 2024c.

Figure 7.26: Relative change in total NO_x emissions between 1990 and 2022 with data from EDGAR and National Inventories.

Source of data: EEA, 2024c; JRC, 2024c.

Regarding the differences in total NO_x emissions, the overall correlation between data from national inventories and EDGAR is good for most MS. In 2022, differences of more than 50% are noted for Cyprus, Finland and Sweden, where emissions from EDGAR were higher.

Concluding, the purpose of use is decisive for the data source to be used. National inventories are compiled by the countries themselves following a bottom-up approach according to the IPCC Guidelines. In the EU, these emission estimates are largely based on higher tier methods, making use of country specific activity data and technology specific emission factors. The emissions included in the EDGAR database cover all countries worldwide, make use of mostly tier 1 methods using international datasets as activity data and default emission factors. The coverage of gases, sectors and country territories differs to a certain extent. The unique feature of EDGAR is the high spatial resolution downscaling country-specific and sector-specific emissions, essential for designing regional or local mitigation policies (Crippa et al, 2024b).

7.5 Section highlights

Ground-level ozone formation depends on the availability of precursor gases (**methane (CH₄), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOCs), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x)**) in the presence of sunlight. However, interpreting emission trends in terms of ozone formation is complex: **ozone chemistry is non-linear**, VOCs vary widely in their reactivity and atmospheric lifetime, and **biogenic VOC sources (which are not reported in inventories) play a significant role**. Member States report CH₄ emissions under the Energy Governance Regulation and NMVOCs and NO_x under the NEC Directive. **Discussions are ongoing to include CH₄ in the next revision of the Gothenburg Protocol**, recognizing its dual relevance as both a greenhouse gas and an ozone precursor.

Among the three precursors, methane stands out for its potent climate impact, with a **global warming potential 28 times higher than CO₂**. With an atmospheric lifetime of about 12 years, **reducing CH₄ emissions delivers rapid benefits for both climate and air quality**. **EU27 CH₄ emissions decreased by 39% between 1990 and 2022**, driven mainly by Germany, Poland, and Romania. The largest reductions occurred in the **waste sector (-44%)** due to the EU Landfill Directive limiting biodegradable waste disposal, and in **fugitive emissions from fossil fuels** linked to coal phase-out and improved gas infrastructure. Emissions from wastewater treatment also declined as aerobic treatment replaces anaerobic systems. **Enteric fermentation remains the largest source (44% of EU total)**, with emissions down 24% due to reduced livestock numbers and improved feeding practices. However, emissions from biological waste treatment have grown eightfold since 1990 as composting and anaerobic digestion expand, and manure management emissions are rising in several countries. **Four Member States (Cyprus, Spain, Ireland, Malta) reported overall increases**, mainly from waste disposal and livestock. Member States report **727 CH₄-related measures** targeting mainly agriculture and waste, **including improved feeding practices and additives, biogas production from manure, extended grazing, and promotion of organic farming**. In the waste sector, efforts focus on separate biowaste collection, reduced landfilling of biodegradable waste, landfill gas recovery, and circular economy initiatives. At EU level, several policy frameworks address methane: **the 2020 EU Methane Strategy, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the REPower EU Plan** encouraging biomethane. **The Methane Regulation (2024/1787)** now requires fossil energy operators to measure and minimize emissions, though the expansion of biogas must be accompanied by stringent measures to prevent leakages. Internationally, **the Global Methane Pledge commits signatories to a collective 30% reduction by 2030**. Looking ahead, CH₄ emissions are projected to **decrease by 21% between 2022 and 2050** under existing measures, with **agriculture remaining the dominant source** and Greece being the only Member State projecting a slight increase.

Turning to NMVOCs, these diverse carbon-containing chemicals contribute to tropospheric ozone formation, with **some compounds (benzene, butadiene) also posing direct health risks**. EU27 NMVOC

emissions **decreased by 62% between 1990 and 2022**, with all Member States reporting reductions. Germany, France, and Italy achieved the largest decreases, **with the most significant progress in road transport (-90%)** due to Euro emission standards, catalytic converters, and improved fuel quality. While road transport was the main source in 1990, **today residential heating (mainly wood burning), solvent use, coating applications and manure management dominate, accounting for 56% of EU emissions in 2022**. Despite overall progress, emissions from domestic solvent use **including fungicides rose by 10%** since 1990, while emissions from industrial coating applications declined by 64% thanks to the VOC Solvents Directive and the Industrial Emissions Directive. Member States report **492 NMVOC-related measures** under the NEC Directive, with key strategies **including increasing renewable energy, improving building efficiency, switching to less carbon-intensive fuels, and installing abatement technologies (Best Available Techniques - BAT)**. At EU level, the NEC Directive sets binding national emission ceilings, the Gothenburg Protocol establishes international commitments, the revised Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive promotes cleaner techniques, and the Paints Directive limits VOC content in consumer products. NMVOC emissions are projected to **decrease by 11% between 2020 and 2030** under existing measures, though **Ireland, Luxembourg, and Malta project slight increases** from solvent use and food industry emissions.

The third key precursor, **nitrogen oxides (NO_x)**, includes NO and NO₂ and originates mainly from **fuel combustion**. **EU NO_x emissions decreased by 64% between 1990 and 2022**, with all Member States reporting reductions and Germany, France, Italy, and Spain contributing most to total reductions. **The transport sector remains the main source, though its share decreased from 52% (1990) to 47% (2022)** due to Euro emission standards, catalytic converters, and fleet renewal. Significant reductions also occurred in public electricity and heat production through fuel switching (coal to gas), improved technologies, and abatement equipment. Member States report **467 NO_x-related measures**, primarily targeting transport and energy, with key strategies including **demand management, promotion of alternative fuels and electric vehicles, modal shift to public transport, and infrastructure improvements**. Technical abatement technologies (selective catalytic reduction, exhaust gas recirculation) are already standard in industrial installations. At EU level, **the Sofia Protocol (1988) and Gothenburg Protocol** established international commitments, while **the NEC Directive** sets binding national ceilings, **the revised Industrial Emissions Directive** promotes BAT, **the Medium Combustion Plants Directive** sets emission limits, and **European emission standards** regulate road vehicle emissions. NO_x emissions are projected to **decrease by 31% between 2020 and 2030** under existing measures, with only **Malta and Romania foreseeing slight increases, mainly from transport**.

Beyond national inventories, it is worth noting that the **EDGAR database** provides an alternative global emission dataset using Tier 1 methods and international statistics. Discrepancies between national inventories and EDGAR are particularly notable for **fugitive emissions, agriculture, and waste sectors**, arising from differences in timing, methodologies, emission factors, and inherent uncertainties. The unique value of EDGAR database lies in its **global coverage, consistent methodology, and high-resolution spatial distribution** essential for regional modelling, **while national inventories remain the reference for monitoring progress toward emission reduction targets**.

In conclusion, **significant progress has been achieved in reducing ozone precursor emissions across Europe over the past three decades**, driven by EU regulations, technological improvements, and sectoral policies. However, challenges remain for all three precursors: **CH₄ emissions from biological waste treatment are rising eightfold** and four Member States report overall increases; **NMVOC emissions from domestic solvent use continue to grow** while Ireland, Luxembourg, and Malta project further increases from solvent use and the food industry; and for **NO_x, Malta and Romania foresee rising emissions from transport**, while biomass combustion (often promoted as a renewable energy source) also generates significant NO_x emissions. The greatest mitigation potential lies in structural changes: **cleaner energy and heating, electrified transport, reduced meat consumption, less waste, and comprehensive application of Best Available Techniques**. Continued monitoring of both

atmospheric concentrations and emission trends remains essential, though interpretation in terms of ozone formation requires consideration of the complex, non-linear chemistry involved.

8 Literature review of the maturity of CH₄ inverse modelling

The analysis of precursor emissions, particularly methane, reveal significant challenges in accurately quantifying emission sources and their spatial and temporal variability. While emission inventories provide essential baseline information, discrepancies exist between national inventories and global datasets such as EDGAR (see Section 7.4), and even greater gaps emerge when comparing with atmospheric observations. That reinforces the need for more robust verification methods. To address these uncertainties and improve emission estimates, inverse modeling approaches have emerged as powerful tools for reconciling bottom-up inventories with atmospheric measurements. The following bibliographic review examines maturity and applications of methane inverse modelling methodologies across different spatial scales. These techniques enable more precise emission flux estimates by integrating atmospheric observations with CTM, thereby bridging the gap between inventory-based and measurement-based approaches.

Methane inverse modelling has reached varying levels of maturity depending on spatial scale and monitoring approach. This section offers a comprehensive overview of current detection capabilities, recent technological progress, and persisting knowledge gaps in methane monitoring applications.

Table 8.1: Maturity overview of methane inverse modelling by spatial scale.

Scale	Range	Maturity level	Applications
Global/regional	>100 km	High	National inventories, Paris Agreement
Urban/basin	10-100 km	Medium-High	Production regions, metropolitan areas
Facility (large)	<10 km, >500 kg/h	Medium-High	Super-emitters, major facilities
Facility (medium)	<10 km, 50-500 kg/h	Medium	Component-level, biogas plants
Facility (small/diffuse)	<10 km, <50 kg/h	Low-Emerging	Agriculture, small leaks

The field is experiencing rapid advancement driven by three concurrent developments: new high-resolution satellite missions (such as TROPOMI and MethaneSAT) launched or planned for 2024-2027; integration of machine learning techniques for automated CH₄ plume detection; and improved low-cost sensor technologies enabling dense network deployments. These advances enable significant improvements in methane monitoring capabilities over the next five years, with facility-scale applications representing the primary area of ongoing development.

8.1 Monitoring capabilities

Methane monitoring capabilities are presented in the following, as they play a crucial role in inverse modelling approaches for accurate emission flux estimations.

8.1.1 Satellite systems

Building on the remote sensing capabilities described for VOCs in Section 5.2, satellite monitoring of methane relies on similar instruments and methodologies. TROPOMI, which provides formaldehyde

retrievals for VOC proxy monitoring, also delivers daily global methane mapping, while upcoming missions such as Sentinel-5 will enhance observations of both trace gases.

TROPOMI delivers continuous daily global mapping at 5.5×7 km² resolution with a 3% success rate over land, while GOSAT offers high-quality data suited for long-term trend analysis (Lorente et al., 2021). Operating aboard Sentinel-5, the TROPOMI instrument remains the only satellite providing daily global methane concentration maps, measuring CH₄ in shortwave infrared bands with high precision. These systems have demonstrated substantial detection capabilities. In 2021, TROPOMI identified emissions from 94 persistent emission clusters and hundreds of transient sources, with 35% attributed to urban areas and landfills, 24% to gas infrastructure, 21% to oil infrastructure, and 20% to coal mines (Schuit et al., 2023). Daily satellite observations reveal methane enhancements over production regions that correlate strongly with in-situ measurements and production patterns (Schneising et al., 2020). Current point source imagers including the GHGSat constellation and hyperspectral sensors have detection thresholds in the 100-10000 kg/h range, enabling monitoring of large point sources (Jacob et al., 2022).

Satellite monitoring capabilities are rapidly expanding with new missions. MethaneSAT, launched in 2024, employs an imaging spectrometer covering 1.61-1.68 μm wavelengths with 100m × 400m resolution over a 260 km swath, enabling global mapping every 3-4 days. Its detection limit of 5 kg/h/km² allows for basin-scale emission quantification at 4-5 km grid resolution (IEA, 2024). Future area flux mappers, including GOSAT-GW, Sentinel-5, GeoCarb, and CO2M, will further enhance capabilities for high-resolution emission quantification (Jacob et al., 2022). In addition, high-resolution satellites including GHGSat (25 × 25 m²), PRISMA and Sentinel-2, and Landsat can identify exact sources responsible for TROPOMI-detected plumes (Varon et al., 2021; Guanter et al., 2021), enabling precise source localization for follow-up investigations.

Nevertheless, notable limitations persist across satellite platforms. Measurements face challenges in offshore areas, mountain ranges, snowy regions, and high latitudes. Cloud cover impairs observations even with partial coverage, proving particularly problematic in equatorial regions such as Nigeria and Venezuela (IEA, 2024). Additionally, variable bias issues affect global TROPOMI inversions (Shen et al., 2021), requiring ongoing calibration and validation efforts.

8.1.2 Ground-based networks

Ground-based monitoring facilities provide essential observational constraints through spatially distributed time-series measurements, enabling both forward and inverse modelling at global, continental, and regional scales. State-of-the-art inversions that combine in-situ observations from multiple monitoring stations with Lagrangian particle dispersion models have successfully estimated regional CH₄ emissions (Raju et al., 2022). However, current CH₄ ground-based infrastructure faces limitations in terms of station density and spatial coverage. For instance, only Germany currently reports CH₄ measurements to the EEA e-reporting database. These constraints, like those identified for VOC monitoring (see Section 5), limit the ability to resolve emissions at sub-national scales.

Co-location of CH₄ with other gas species offers a pathway to improved source attribution. Monitoring NMVOCs alongside methane helps distinguish petroleum and gas sources, though emission ratios vary considerably and remain poorly characterised (Peischl et al., 2015, 2016). As detailed in Section 5, systematic in-situ VOC monitoring has evolved over several decades through programmes such as EMEP and WMO GAW. The revised AAQD has expanded the list of target compounds to 46 VOC species and for the first time references CH₄ as an ozone precursor requiring monitoring. That reflects the growing recognition of the connection between greenhouse gas and air quality monitoring. Among the VOCs measured, toluene, m,p-xylene, 1-butene, n-butane, and i-pentane collectively contribute over 50% to the Maximum Ozone Formation Potential (Salameh et al., 2024), highlighting the importance of targeting specific high-reactivity compounds. However, challenges remain: no single analytical method can detect all species, effective monitoring requires specialised equipment, and the number of reporting stations has declined over the past decade for several compound groups. Despite these

limitations, the co-location of CH₄ and NMVOC measurements at EMEP and research stations offers significant advantages for both climate policy and ozone mitigation strategies.

To address the spatial coverage gaps, low-cost metal oxide (MOx) sensors, including devices such as Figaro TGS2600, TGS2611, and MQ4, enable finer-scale spatiotemporal measurements within existing methane monitoring infrastructure. These sensors demonstrate maturity for leak detection applications but remain limited for quantitative inversions. Their performance varies across seasons and requires calibration to account for temperature, humidity, and CO cross-sensitivities (Eugster et al., 2012; Lin et al., 2023). Performance characteristics vary significantly with CH₄ concentration levels. The TGS2611 and MQ4 sensors show sufficient accuracy for detecting major leaks in urban areas with enhancements above 1 ppm, sometimes exceeding 10 ppm (Furuta et al., 2022). Moderate accuracy has been achieved in the 2-10 ppm CH₄ range (RMSE <0.6 ppm), though sensor response varies over time, potentially due to cross-sensitivities with non-targeted gases (Furuta et al., 2024). Mobile monitoring using low-cost sensor arrays combined with random forest models achieved high correlation with reference instruments and detected 80% of methane spikes above 2.5 ppm (Silberstein et al., 2024). However, important limitations constraint sensor applicability. Concentrations in the background to 2.5 ppm range represent poor applications for this technology, with sensors performing better under high-variability conditions. These devices require calibration across a wide range of temperature and humidity conditions to accurately determine absolute methane concentrations (Collier-Oxandale et al., 2018). Additional challenges include cross-sensitivity to other gases, particularly CO (Lin et al., 2023), and sensor drift over time necessitating frequent recalibration. Despite these limitations, deploying large networks of ground-based methane sensors offers promising opportunities including urban leak detection and monitoring.

8.1.3 Mobile and airborne platforms

Mobile and airborne measurement platforms have reached high maturity for source detection and medium maturity for emission quantification. Mobile greenhouse gas surveys employing Gaussian plume modelling based on repeat passes through emission plumes successfully estimate total emissions from facilities such as biogas plants (Bakkaloglu et al., 2021). Similarly, aircraft-based measurements provide critical validation and characterization of facility-scale emissions across diverse infrastructure types (Alvarez et al., 2018). These mobile approaches offer several distinct advantages for methane monitoring. They enable rapid assessment of multiple facilities within a single campaign, allowing efficient regional-scale characterization. The platforms are highly effective at detecting intermittent emissions that static monitoring systems might miss (Varon et al., 2021). Furthermore, the mass balance technique employed by aircraft campaigns enables comprehensive quantification of facility-level emissions, capturing both stack and fugitive sources simultaneously (Lavoie et al., 2017).

8.2 Inverse modelling methodologies

Methane inverse modelling has evolved into a sophisticated field employing diverse methodological approaches, each offering distinct advantages and limitations for estimating emissions fluxes across various spatial and temporal scales.

First, high-resolution three-dimensional variational inverse modelling using CTMs enables optimization of both emissions and isotopic signatures, although computational demands remain substantial and posterior uncertainties are difficult to quantify. While Monte Carlo ensembles are needed to derive robust posterior statistics, the high computational cost of single inversions currently prohibits this comprehensive uncertainty quantification. Variational systems require high computational costs and lack posterior uncertainties, which remain expensive to compute formally. Moreover, spatial errors in prior emissions combined with CTM errors can significantly impact inversion performance, as single inversion frameworks cannot simultaneously correct overall bias and spatial distribution when both error types occur (Yu et al., 2021).

Then, analytical inversions offer an alternative approach by optimizing methane emissions to fit observations within a Bayesian framework, providing closed-form expressions of information content and straightforward generation of inversion ensembles (Qu et al., 2024). These methods present several advantages over variational approaches, including significantly lower computational costs that enable year-to-year tracking of emissions rather than optimizing mean values over entire periods. Their computational efficiency makes them particularly suitable for regional to global scale applications.

Adjoint model, such as the GEOS-Chem adjoint model, enables four-dimensional variational (4D-Var) analysis to test how effectively heterogeneous CH₄ fluxes can be resolved using high-resolution satellite data (Yu et al., 2021). This approach supports alternative formalisms beyond traditional scale factor optimization and can overcome limitations associated with missing sources. The method successfully resolves monthly emissions at 25 km spatial resolution, providing detailed temporal and spatial characterization. A 4D-Var analysis of TROPOMI data can improve monthly emission estimates at 25 km resolution even with spatially biased priors or CTM errors, achieving 42-93% domain-wide bias reduction (Yu et al., 2021).

Finally, machine learning techniques are increasingly integrated into inversion frameworks to enhance data processing and interpretation. Two-step machine learning methods employing convolutional neural networks and support vector classifiers successfully distinguish methane plumes from retrieval artifacts in satellite data (Schuit et al., 2023). These approaches support diverse applications across the methane monitoring workflow. Additional applications include feature engineering for source classification and emission rate quantification (Maasackers et al., 2022). More broadly, AI-based models are emerging as valuable tools that address limitations of conventional techniques across different stages of methane research (Mohammadimanesh et al., 2025), demonstrating the growing maturity and flexibility of machine learning in atmospheric inverse modelling.

8.3 Performance assessment by scale and sector

Methane inverse modelling capabilities vary significantly across spatial scales, with performance and maturity level ranging from well-established global applications to emerging facility-scale monitoring and remaining challenges for small and diffuse sources.

At global and regional scales (>100 km), methane monitoring has achieved operational maturity. Current satellite systems (GOSAT since 2009, TROPOMI since 2017) provide robust observational foundations for quantifying national emissions in support of the Paris Agreement (Jacob et al., 2022). CTM optimize emissions across multiple source categories, while analytical inversions enable year-to-year emission tracking rather than simple temporal averaging (Qu et al., 2024). Ensemble regional inversions successfully quantify national-scale emissions over decadal timescales (Ishizawa et al., 2024), providing the scientific foundation for international climate policy and emission reporting.

Moving to finer spatial resolution, urban and basin scales (10-100 km) present greater challenges but show promising results. TROPOMI satellite data combined with CTM enable daily monitoring at moderate spatial resolution, proving particularly effective for oil and gas production regions and metropolitan areas (Hemati et al., 2024). Measurements reveal substantial underreporting. Emissions from oil and gas basins exceed bottom-up inventories (Shen et al., 2023), while city-level emissions measure 1.4-2.6 times higher than reported values (Maasackers et al., 2022). Key challenges include mixed source attribution in urban environments, complex boundary layer dynamics affecting source localization, and limited ground-based validation networks restricting fine-scale characterization.

At facility scale (<10 km), multiple approaches successfully detect and quantify large emitters. Aircraft measurements show oil and gas facility emissions 21-120 times greater than reports (Lavoie et al., 2017), while satellite methods detect strongly emitting landfills (3-29 t/h) exceeding inventory estimates. Machine learning applied to TROPOMI detected 2974 super-emitter plumes in 2021 (in average 44 t/h) (Schuit et al., 2023). Point source imagers (GHGSat) cover the 100-10000 kg/h

detection range (Jacob et al., 2022), with high-resolution satellites identifying exact emission locations (Varon et al., 2021).

For medium sources (50-500 kg/h), targeted measurements reveal systematic underestimation. Oil and gas component-level studies show emissions 5-7 times higher than inventories for valves and connectors (Rutherford et al., 2021), while facility studies indicate 1.5-2 times greater emissions overall (Alvarez et al., 2018). Biogas plant measurements detect leakages of 3.0-9.9 kg/h representing 8-10% of production (Reinelt et al., 2021), with mobile surveys measuring 0.1-58.7 kg/h (Bakkaloglu et al., 2021). DIAL technology (Differential Absorption Lidar) enables improved characterization through sustained monitoring (DESNZ, 2025). In addition, wastewater treatment facilities show emissions of 166-381 g per population equivalent annually (Bühler et al., 2022). Major limitations include limited long-term monitoring programs, insufficient characterization of operational variables affecting emissions, and incomplete understanding of temporal variability patterns.

Finally, small and diffuse sources (<50 kg/h) remain the most challenging to monitor. Oil and gas small leaks fall below satellite thresholds, with no standardized protocol providing accurate supply chain-specific estimates (Wang et al., 2022). Moreover, agricultural emissions from livestock, manure management, and rice cultivation are spatially distributed and temporally variable, fundamentally challenging inverse modelling designed for point sources. Specialized monitoring approaches are needed but undeveloped.

8.4 Cross-scale integration framework

Integrating measurements across spatial scales presents both opportunities and challenges for methane emission quantification. Multiscale measurement frameworks demonstrate potential for improving the accuracy of oil and gas methane estimates (Wang et al., 2022). Validation hierarchies extending from satellite observations down to ground-based measurements provide essential quality assurance (Jacob et al., 2022; Maasackers et al., 2022).

Temporal variations make emission measurements challenging. Emissions fluctuate over multiple timescales, from daily cycles to long-term operational changes. Short-term measurements often miss important events like maintenance activities or intermittent large releases, which can dominate total emissions despite being sporadic. Weather conditions also affect emissions significantly. Therefore, monitoring programs must run long enough to capture these variations while maintaining sufficient time resolution to detect temporary emission events.

Creating measurement-based emission inventories requires integrating multiple data sources. This process compiles facility-level measurements across major producing basins and develops representative emission profiles for different facility types. Several integration strategies have emerged. Combining bottom-up inventories with top-down atmospheric constraints enables mutual validation and identifies discrepancies. Integrating multiple satellite platforms exploits complementary strengths in resolution, coverage, and sensitivity. Data fusion of ground-based and airborne measurements provides cross-validation at appropriate scales. Advanced approaches merge satellite data, company reporting, and production records to create more comprehensive emission estimates than any single source could provide.

8.5 Section highlights

Methane inverse modelling has achieved **high maturity at global and regional scales**, with robust methodologies enabling national emission quantification in support of international climate agreements. **Urban and basin-scale inversions demonstrate medium to high maturity**, particularly for oil and gas production regions where extensive observational campaigns have validated inversion approaches. However, **facility-scale inversions remain at emerging to medium maturity**, exhibiting

significant capabilities for large point sources exceeding 500 kg/h but facing significant challenges when characterizing smaller sources and diffuse emitters.

Despite these advances, several critical gaps constrain the full realization of monitoring capabilities. Current **measurement methods vary too much between different facilities**, making reliable comparisons impossible. **Temporal variability characterization from diurnal cycles to interannual trends remains insufficient**, particularly for intermittent super-emitter events that can dominate total emissions despite their sporadic nature. **Systematic uncertainty quantification at all spatial scales is limited by prohibitive computational costs** that prevent routine application of ensemble approaches essential for robust policy decisions. From a technological perspective, **satellite measurements struggle in offshore areas, mountainous terrain, and high latitudes, while small leaks below 100 kg/h fall beneath detection thresholds. Low-cost sensor networks face drift, cross-sensitivity to interfering with gases, and performance degradation at background concentrations below 2.5 ppm.** Emerging satellite missions (MethaneSAT, GOSAT-GW, CO2M) lack comprehensive validation infrastructure needed to ensure data quality.

At the sector level, challenges vary substantially. The oil and gas sector shows systematic biases in component-level emission factors compared to official inventories. The waste sector relies on outdated landfill decay models incompatible with modern waste composition, while biogas facilities lack long-term monitoring. Agricultural emissions require specialized approaches for diffuse, temporally variable sources not yet developed at operational scales. Urban environments face attribution difficulties from overlapping multiple sources and limited ground-based validation networks.

The field is experiencing rapid advancement. **New high-resolution satellite missions launched or planned for 2024-2027 will expand observational capacity and temporal coverage.** The integration of enhanced **satellite observations, sophisticated inverse modelling techniques, and emerging sensor networks** promises **significant improvements in methane monitoring** over the next years. Facility-scale monitoring represents the forefront, where technological capabilities are rapidly maturing but methodological frameworks and operational deployment remain in progress. **Priority actions include developing standardized measurement protocols, characterizing temporal variability patterns, implementing systematic uncertainty quantification, enhancing isotopic source attribution capabilities, and establishing comprehensive validation networks for emerging platforms.**

9 Conclusions

This report presents a comprehensive analysis of ozone in relation to its precursors (NO_x, NMVOCs and CH₄) within the context of the revised AAQD, establishing a complete linkage between the regulatory framework and scientific understanding of the challenges raised by ozone pollution in Europe. Ozone pollution remains a major public health challenge in Europe, with approximately 70,981 deaths attributable to ozone across 41 European countries, including 62,676 within the EU27 (Soares et al., 2025). At the ecosystem level, only 9.2% of European agricultural land met the long-term objective for vegetation protection in 2023⁷⁰, indicating persistent risk of vegetation damage from ozone exposure.

The revised AAQD represents a significant policy advancement in aligning European air quality standards with the latest scientific evidence. Key improvements include the reduction of allowed exceedances for the target value from 25 to 18 days per year by 2030, the lowering of the long-term objective for human health protection from 120 µg/m³ to 100 µg/m³ by 2050 to align with the WHO guidelines. The revised AAQD makes compulsory the implementation of air quality plans for ozone when exceedances of the target value occurred and mandates enhanced assessment of transboundary contributions. Furthermore, the revised AAQD expands the list of VOC precursors from 30 to 46 (45 NMVOCs plus methane) and, for the first time, explicitly recognises methane as an ozone precursor reflecting advances in scientific understanding of ozone formation chemistry. Case study analysis reveals that application of the new assessment criteria could lead to an increase in the number of sampling points required in certain Member States, particularly for zones with high population density.

Over the past three decades, Europe has achieved significant reductions in ozone precursor emissions: NO_x decreased by 64%, NMVOCs by 62%, and CH₄ by 39% between 1990 and 2022. These reductions were driven by EU regulations, technological improvements, and sectoral policies. For NO_x, strict regulations on transport and industry delivered consistent progress, with major contributions from France, Germany, Italy, and Spain. For NMVOCs, regulatory measures on solvent use and industrial processes proved effective, including directives on industrial emissions and limitations on VOCs in paints and varnishes. For methane, the largest reductions occurred in fugitive emissions from the energy sector and in the waste sector through implementation of the EU Landfill Directive. However, challenges persist across all three precursors: emissions from biological waste treatment have grown eightfold as composting and anaerobic digestion expand; domestic solvent use continues to rise; and four Member States (Cyprus, Spain, Ireland and Malta) report overall CH₄ increases. Agriculture remains the dominant source of CH₄, with enteric fermentation alone accounting for 44% of EU total, while residential heating, solvent use, coating applications and manure management now represent 56% of NMVOC emissions.

The overview of the European VOC monitoring reveals significant disparities in measurement capabilities between Member States. Although the revised AAQD recommends monitoring 46 specific VOC species many countries still lack adequate infrastructure for comprehensive monitoring. Long-term, continuous time series are mainly available for aromatic hydrocarbons (benzene, toluene, xylenes), while measurements of alkenes, oxygenated VOCs, terpenes, and methane are more limited in spatial coverage and continuity. Notably, only Germany currently reports CH₄ measurements to the EEA e-reporting database. The analysis identified substantial gaps particularly for highly reactive species such as isoprene, α-pinene, and other biogenic VOCs, as well as anthropogenic compounds like styrene and 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene. The lack of formaldehyde data may also limit efforts to validate satellite-derived concentration levels. Strategic challenges include the need for enhanced capabilities to distinguish between biogenic and anthropogenic VOC sources, improved spatial coverage in rural

⁽⁷⁰⁾ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/exposure-of-europes-ecosystems-to-ozone?activeAccordion=ecdb3bcf-bbe9-4978-b5cf-0b136399d9f8>

areas where biogenic emissions dominate, and better temporal resolution to capture diurnal and seasonal variations.

Nevertheless, establishing a European monitoring network compliant with the revised AAQD is technically feasible, building on existing programmes such as EMEP, WMO/GAW, and research infrastructures like ICOS and ACTRIS. These programmes provide a strong foundation in measurement expertise, quality assurance procedures, and data management systems. Network design should align with dominant emission sources: for NMVOCs, this means prioritising BTEX compounds, trimethylbenzenes, and key ketones at urban and industrial sites; for methane, monitoring should focus on agricultural regions with high livestock densities, areas with significant biogas production, and regions with remaining fossil fuel infrastructure. Compliance is achievable through a tiered network design combining core continuous monitoring sites equipped with advanced instrumentation, supplementary sites using simpler methods to improve spatial coverage, strong integration with existing research infrastructures, and integration of satellite observations with ground-based measurements to support top-down verification of emission inventories.

Analysis of air quality plans reveals a heterogeneous approach across European countries. Croatia adopted a national action plan and regional plans for cities including Pula, with measures targeting traffic, port activities, shore power for ships, and energy efficiency; monitoring data suggests a slight decrease in exceedance days over 2019-2023. France has developed regional atmosphere protection plans (PPA) and territorial climate air energy plans (PCAET) integrating ozone reduction within a multi-pollutant approach. Spain, particularly affected in the Mediterranean basin, commissioned an in-depth scientific study to develop a future National Ozone Plan, identifying NMVOCs with the highest contribution to ozone formation and demonstrating through modelling that national measures alone cannot achieve the EU long-term objective without combined international strategies. Cross-cutting analysis reveals that most existing plans lack approaches specifically dedicated to ozone with sufficient integration of transboundary contributions, highlighting the complexity of non-linear chemical processes that require enhanced European coordination. To support the development of effective plans, source apportionment tools such as the CAMS Air Control Toolbox now provide daily diagnostics for major European cities, identifying contributions from traffic, industry, shipping, residential, agriculture, and natural sources.

Future projections indicate that achieving reduction targets will require reinforced and diverse measures across sectors. For methane, a 21% decrease is projected between 2022 and 2050 under existing measures, with agriculture remaining the dominant source; efforts must focus on improved livestock management, fertiliser efficiency, and reduction of emissions from biological waste treatment. For NMVOCs, an 11% reduction is projected between 2020 and 2030, requiring continued measures in solvent use and application of Best Available Techniques. For NO_x, a 31% reduction is expected between 2020 and 2030, depending on strengthened vehicle emission standards, energy transition, and improved industrial efficiency. Transformative solutions, including dietary shifts, circular economy approaches, fossil fuel phase-out, transport electrification, and comprehensive application of BAT, offer the greatest long-term mitigation potential beyond incremental technical improvements.

Finally, methane inverse modelling has achieved high maturity at global and regional scales, supporting national emission verification under international climate agreements. Satellite missions, including MethaneSAT, GOSAT-GW, and Sentinel-5, are expanding observational capacity, offering promising prospects for more precise monitoring when integrated with ground-based networks. Priority actions include developing standardised measurement protocols, characterising temporal variability, implementing systematic uncertainty quantification, and establishing comprehensive validation networks for emerging platforms.

Moving forward, the convergence of enhanced monitoring capabilities of ozone precursors, improved emission quantification through inverse modelling and coordinated European strategies in the development of air quality plans will be essential to address the persistent challenge of ozone pollution.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
ACTRIS	The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure	https://www.actris.eu/
AAQD	Ambient Air Quality Directive	
ACT	Air Control Toolbox	
AQ	Air Quality	
AOT	Accumulated Ozone over Threshold of 40 ppb	
BAT	Best Available Techniques	
BTEX	Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, Xylenes	
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service	https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/
CEN	European Committee for Standardization	
CH ₄	Methane	
CHP	Combined Heat and Power	
CLRTAP	Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution	
CO	Carbon monoxide	
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide	
CTM	Chemistry Transport Model	
DNPH	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine	
EDGAR	Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research	https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
EGR	Exhaust Gas Recirculation	
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme	https://www.emep.int/
ESA	European Space Agency	https://www.esa.int/
ETC	European Topic Centre	
EU	European Union	
FID	Flame Ionization Detector	
GAW	Global Atmosphere Watch Programme	https://community.wmo.int/site/knowledge-hub/programmes-and-initiatives/global-atmosphere-watch-programme-gaw
GC	Gas Chromatography	
GCM	Global Climate Model	
GHG	Greenhouse Gas	
GOSAT	Greenhouse gases Observing SATellite	
GWP	Global Warming Potential	
HCHO	Formaldehyde	
HPLC	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography	
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System	
IEA	International Energy Agency	https://www.iea.org/
IED	Industrial Emissions Directive	
IIR	Informative Inventory Report	
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change	https://www.ipcc.ch/

JRC	Joint Research Centre	https://commission.europa.eu/about/departments-and-executive-agencies/joint-research-centre_en
LTO	Long-term objective	
MethaneSAT	Methane Satellite	
MIR	Maximum Incremental Reactivity	
MOFP	Maximum Ozone Formation Potential	
MS	Member States	
MSD	Mass Spectrometry Detector	
NAPCP	National Air Pollution Control Programme	
NEC	National Emission reduction Commitments	
NH ₃	Ammonia	
NID	National Inventory Document	
NIR	National Inventory Report	
NMHC	Non-Methane Hydrocarbons	
NMVOG	Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compound	
NO	Nitrogen oxide	
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide	
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides	
O ₃	Ozone	
OMI	Ozone Monitoring Instrument	
OVOC	Oxygenated Volatile Organic Compounds	
PCAET	Plans Climat-Air-Énergie Territoriaux (Territorial Climate Air Energy Plans)	
PM	Particulate Matter	
PM10	Particulate Matter with diameter ≤ 10 µm	
PM2.5	Particulate Matter with diameter ≤ 2.5 µm	
POCP	Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential	
PPA	Plans de Protection de l'Atmosphère (Atmosphere Protection Plans)	
PREPA	Plan de Réduction des Émissions de Polluants Atmosphériques	
PTR-MS	Proton Transfer Reaction Mass Spectrometry	
SAPRC	The California Statewide Air Pollution Research Centre	
SCR	Selective Catalytic Reduction	
SNCR	Selective Non-Catalytic Reduction	
SOA	Second Organic Aerosol	
SO ₂	Sulphur dioxide	
SPO	Sampling Point	
TCCON	Total Carbon Column Observing Network	
TD	Thermal Desorption	
TROPOMI	TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument	
TV	Target Value	
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe	https://unece.org/fr
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change	https://unfccc.int/fr

VOC	Volatile Organic Compound
WAM	With Additional Measures (scenario)
WEM	With Existing Measures (scenario)
WMO	World Meteorological Organization https://wmo.int/
WHO	World Health Organization

References

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Annex 1 Data on sampling point reported to EEA (e-Reporting)

Table A1.1: Number of sampling points reporting in a country per VOC listed in Table 2.5, and from this number which ones have time series for 10 or 3 years, at least.

country iso2 code	compound	VOC group	number of SPOs		
			Total	>= 3 years of data	>= 10 years of data
FR	Acetaldehyde/Ethanal	Aldehyde	8	0	1
FR	Formaldehyde	Aldehyde	8	0	1
FR	Ethane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	Ethane	Alkanes	4	0	4
LT	Ethane	Alkanes	1	0	0
PL	Ethane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	Ethane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	i-Butane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FR	i-Butane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	i-Butane	Alkanes	4	0	4
LT	i-Butane	Alkanes	1	0	0
PL	i-Butane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	i-Butane	Alkanes	1	0	1
AT	i-Hexane	Alkanes	1	1	1
DK	i-Hexane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	i-Hexane	Alkanes	1	0	1
GB	i-Hexane	Alkanes	4	0	4
PL	i-Hexane	Alkanes	1	1	1
AT	i-Octane	Alkanes	1	1	1
DK	i-Octane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	i-Octane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FR	i-Octane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	i-Octane	Alkanes	4	0	4
PL	i-Octane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	i-Octane	Alkanes	1	0	1
AT	i-Pentane	Alkanes	1	1	1
ES	i-Pentane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FR	i-Pentane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	i-Pentane	Alkanes	4	0	4
PL	i-Pentane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	i-Pentane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	n-Butane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FR	n-Butane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	n-Butane	Alkanes	4	0	4
LT	n-Butane	Alkanes	1	0	0
PL	n-Butane	Alkanes	1	1	1

SE	n-Butane	Alkanes	1	0	1
AT	n-Heptane	Alkanes	1	1	1
DK	n-Heptane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	n-Heptane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FI	n-Heptane	Alkanes	1	0	0
FR	n-Heptane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	n-Heptane	Alkanes	4	0	4
PL	n-Heptane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	n-Heptane	Alkanes	1	0	1
AT	n-Hexane	Alkanes	1	1	1
DK	n-Hexane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	n-Hexane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FR	n-Hexane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	n-Hexane	Alkanes	4	0	4
LT	n-Hexane	Alkanes	1	0	0
PL	n-Hexane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	n-Hexane	Alkanes	1	0	1
AT	n-Octane	Alkanes	1	1	1
DK	n-Octane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	n-Octane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FR	n-Octane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	n-Octane	Alkanes	4	0	4
PL	n-Octane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	n-Octane	Alkanes	1	0	1
AT	n-Pentane	Alkanes	1	1	1
DK	n-Pentane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	n-Pentane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FR	n-Pentane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	n-Pentane	Alkanes	4	0	4
PL	n-Pentane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	n-Pentane	Alkanes	1	0	1
FR	Propane	Alkanes	1	0	0
GB	Propane	Alkanes	4	0	4
PL	Propane	Alkanes	1	1	1
SE	Propane	Alkanes	1	0	1
ES	1,3-Butadiene	Alkenes	1	0	1
FR	1,3-Butadiene	Alkenes	1	0	0
GB	1,3-Butadiene	Alkenes	5	0	5
LT	1,3-Butadiene	Alkenes	1	0	0
PL	1,3-Butadiene	Alkenes	1	1	1
SE	1,3-Butadiene	Alkenes	1	0	1
ES	1-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	1
FR	1-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	0
GB	1-Butene	Alkenes	4	0	4
LT	1-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	0

PL	1-Butene	Alkenes	1	1	1
SE	1-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	1
AT	1-Pentene	Alkenes	1	1	1
DK	1-Pentene	Alkenes	1	0	1
ES	1-Pentene	Alkenes	1	0	1
FR	1-Pentene	Alkenes	1	0	0
GB	1-Pentene	Alkenes	4	0	4
LT	1-Pentene	Alkenes	1	0	0
PL	1-Pentene	Alkenes	1	1	1
SE	1-Pentene	Alkenes	1	0	1
AT	2-Pentene	Alkenes	1	1	1
DK	2-Pentene	Alkenes	1	0	1
ES	2-Pentene	Alkenes	1	0	1
PL	2-Pentene	Alkenes	1	0	1
ES	cis-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	1
FR	cis-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	0
GB	cis-2-Butene	Alkenes	4	0	4
LT	cis-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	0
PL	cis-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	1	1
SE	cis-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	1
FR	Ethylene	Alkenes	1	0	0
GB	Ethylene	Alkenes	4	0	4
PL	Ethylene	Alkenes	1	1	1
SE	Ethylene	Alkenes	1	0	1
FR	Propene / Propylene	Alkenes	1	0	0
GB	Propene / Propylene	Alkenes	4	0	4
PL	Propene / Propylene	Alkenes	1	1	1
SE	Propene / Propylene	Alkenes	1	0	1
ES	Trans-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	1
FR	Trans-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	0
GB	Trans-2-Butene	Alkenes	4	0	4
PL	Trans-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	1	1
SE	Trans-2-Butene	Alkenes	1	0	1
FR	Acetylene	Alkynes	1	0	0
GB	Acetylene	Alkynes	4	0	4
PL	Acetylene	Alkynes	1	1	1
SE	Acetylene	Alkynes	1	0	1
AT	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	1	1
BG	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	2	0	2
DK	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
ES	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
FR	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	0
GB	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	4	0	4
LT	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	0
PL	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	1	1

SE	1.2.3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
AT	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	1	1
BG	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	2	0	2
DK	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
ES	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
FR	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	0
GB	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	4	0	4
LT	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	0
PL	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	1	1
SE	1.2.4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
AT	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	1	1
BG	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	2	0	2
DK	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
ES	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
FI	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	3	1	2
FR	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	0
GB	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	4	0	4
LT	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	0
PL	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	1	1
SE	1.3.5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
AL	Benzene	Aromatics	2	0	0
AT	Benzene	Aromatics	16	10	16
BE	Benzene	Aromatics	38	15	35
BG	Benzene	Aromatics	4	0	1
CH	Benzene	Aromatics	2	0	2
CY	Benzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
CZ	Benzene	Aromatics	24	0	24
DE	Benzene	Aromatics	62	27	54
DK	Benzene	Aromatics	3	0	1
EE	Benzene	Aromatics	4	4	4
ES	Benzene	Aromatics	145	86	132
FI	Benzene	Aromatics	3	1	2
FR	Benzene	Aromatics	136	24	87
GB	Benzene	Aromatics	40	0	37
GR	Benzene	Aromatics	9	0	7
HR	Benzene	Aromatics	5	3	4
HU	Benzene	Aromatics	13	12	13
IE	Benzene	Aromatics	2	0	1
IT	Benzene	Aromatics	196	122	191
LT	Benzene	Aromatics	5	1	5
LU	Benzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
LV	Benzene	Aromatics	13	1	3
MK	Benzene	Aromatics	2	0	0
MT	Benzene	Aromatics	3	1	2
NL	Benzene	Aromatics	1	0	0

NO	Benzene	Aromatics	12	7	12
PL	Benzene	Aromatics	80	31	67
PT	Benzene	Aromatics	12	1	11
RO	Benzene	Aromatics	93	1	90
SE	Benzene	Aromatics	5	3	4
SI	Benzene	Aromatics	3	2	3
SK	Benzene	Aromatics	12	9	12
AT	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	1	1	1
DE	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	5	3	4
DK	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
ES	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	35	11	34
FI	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	3	1	2
FR	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	85	1	35
GB	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	5	0	5
GR	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
HU	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	12	12	12
IE	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
IT	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	19	4	17
MT	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
NL	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	1	0	0
PL	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	1	1	1
PT	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	2	0	2
SE	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	1	0	1
SI	Ethyl benzene	Aromatics	2	2	2
AT	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	1	1	1
DE	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	16	13	15
DK	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	1
ES	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	48	11	44
FI	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	3	1	2
FR	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	85	1	34
GB	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	5	0	5
GR	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	1
HU	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	11	11	11
IE	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	1
IT	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	12	2	11
LT	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	0
MT	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	2	1	2
NL	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	0
PL	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	1	1	1
PT	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	2	0	2
SE	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	1
SI	m.p-Xylene	Aromatics	2	2	2
AT	o-Xylene	Aromatics	1	1	1
DE	o-Xylene	Aromatics	16	13	15
DK	o-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	1

ES	o-Xylene	Aromatics	31	11	30
FI	o-Xylene	Aromatics	3	1	2
FR	o-Xylene	Aromatics	87	1	34
GB	o-Xylene	Aromatics	5	0	5
GR	o-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	1
HU	o-Xylene	Aromatics	11	11	11
IE	o-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	1
IT	o-Xylene	Aromatics	28	8	26
MT	o-Xylene	Aromatics	2	1	2
NL	o-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	0
PL	o-Xylene	Aromatics	1	1	1
PT	o-Xylene	Aromatics	2	0	2
SE	o-Xylene	Aromatics	1	0	1
SI	o-Xylene	Aromatics	2	2	2
AT	Toluene	Aromatics	1	1	1
CH	Toluene	Aromatics	2	0	2
DE	Toluene	Aromatics	43	25	40
DK	Toluene	Aromatics	3	0	1
ES	Toluene	Aromatics	65	11	60
FI	Toluene	Aromatics	3	1	2
FR	Toluene	Aromatics	96	1	43
GB	Toluene	Aromatics	5	0	5
GR	Toluene	Aromatics	1	0	1
HU	Toluene	Aromatics	12	12	12
IE	Toluene	Aromatics	1	0	1
IT	Toluene	Aromatics	30	9	28
LT	Toluene	Aromatics	1	0	0
LU	Toluene	Aromatics	1	0	1
LV	Toluene	Aromatics	5	0	1
MT	Toluene	Aromatics	3	1	2
NL	Toluene	Aromatics	1	0	0
PL	Toluene	Aromatics	1	1	1
PT	Toluene	Aromatics	1	0	1
SE	Toluene	Aromatics	2	0	2
SI	Toluene	Aromatics	2	2	2
DE	Methane	Methane	10	0	10
DK	Isoprene	Terpenes	1	0	1
ES	Isoprene	Terpenes	1	0	1
FR	Isoprene	Terpenes	1	0	0
GB	Isoprene	Terpenes	4	0	4
PL	Isoprene	Terpenes	1	1	1
SE	Isoprene	Terpenes	1	0	1

Figure A1.1: The monitoring history of aldehydes in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.2: The monitoring history of alkanes in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.3: The monitoring history of alkenes in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.4: The monitoring history of alkynes in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.5: The monitoring history of trimethylbenzene (aromatics) in the e-Reporting

Figure A1.6: The monitoring history of benzene (aromatics) in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.7: The monitoring history of ethyl benzene (aromatics) in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.8: The monitoring history of m,p-Xylene (aromatics) in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.9: The monitoring history of o-Xylene (aromatics) in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.10: The monitoring history of toluene (aromatics) in the e-Reporting.

Figure A1.11: The monitoring history of terpenes (isoprene) in the e-Reporting.

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